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PRAECTICE

POTENTIALS OF AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES IN EAST AFRICA WITH A FOCUS ON CIRCULAR WATER-ENERGY-NUTRIENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract	<p>Agroecology holds great potential to address food system challenges and enhance food security in East Africa. However, the region's unique complexities require tailored indicator frameworks adoptable by smallholder farmers who are the main food producers in the region. The existing agroecological frameworks also fall short in addressing key aspects, such as aquaculture and the circular water-energy-food system, leading to a dearth of evidence on integrated aqua-agriculture (IAA) practices. Therefore, a systematic literature review was carried out to evaluate various agroecological frameworks pertinent to East Africa. The study identified nine promising candidates: SIAF, TAPE, Five-dimensional Presidia, IDEA, MESMIS, SOCLA, OASIS, SAFE, and SAFA. These frameworks underwent screening for applicability, practicality in data collection, socio-economic viability, and environmental sustainability, particularly in the East African context. The frameworks' emphasis on economic viability, social well-being, and environmental conservation aligns with regional priorities and therefore show promise in addressing East Africa's diverse agricultural landscape, contributing to sustainable practices, and improving the well-being of local communities.</p>
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Agroecology holds great potential to address food system challenges and enhance food security in East Africa. However, the region's unique complexities require tailored indicator frameworks adoptable by smallholder farmers who are the main food producers in the region. The existing agroecological indicator frameworks in the literature fail to account for some of the specific smallholder farmers challenges observed in East Africa, and also falls short in addressing key aspects, such as aquaculture and the circular water-energy-food system, leading to a dearth of evidence on integrated aqua-agriculture (IAA) practices. The aim of this review was to define the most suitable indicator set for agroecological practices in East by screening the existing indicator frameworks for their i) applicability to assessments of agroecological practices among small-holder farmers in East Africa; ii) practicality in terms of minimizing data collection costs; iii) socioeconomic viability and iv) environmental sustainability. As a result, a systematic literature review strategy was utilized in the study to identify existing and relevant agroecological indicator frameworks in East Africa. Nine promising AE indicators frameworks including Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework (SIAF), a Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE), The Five-dimensional SF Presidia, indicators of sustainable farm development (IDEA), The Framework for Assessing the Sustainability of Natural Resource Management Systems (MESMIS, for its acronym in Spanish), Sociedad Científica Latinoamericana de Agroecología (SOCLA), Original Agroecological Survey Indicator Systems (OASIS), Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment (SAFE), and Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems (SAFA) were identified. Key findings reveal that the indicator frameworks prioritize a systems approach, emphasizing holistic sustainability. However, concerns arise regarding their adaptability to diverse agroecosystems. The nine frameworks stand out for their multi-scale approach, encompassing field, farm, and landscape levels, crucial for East Africa's varied agricultural landscapes. Additionally, the frameworks' emphasis on economic viability, social well-being, and environmental conservation aligns with regional priorities. For instance, the SAFA framework, developed by FAO and ISEAL Alliance, is lauded for its flexibility, adaptability, and emphasis on good governance. The review highlights how these frameworks cater to East Africa's diverse agricultural practices, offering tools for stakeholders to assess and enhance sustainability. Despite the strengths, limitations are acknowledged, such as the potential complexity of these frameworks, especially for stakeholders unfamiliar with sustainability assessments. Challenges also arise in data availability, resource-intensiveness, and the subjectivity of certain indicators. The need for continuous updates to align with evolving sustainability concepts is recognized. The review provides valuable insights into existing indicator frameworks, offering a comparative analysis of their strengths and limitations in the East African context. Stakeholders are encouraged to select frameworks that align with regional priorities, considering the adaptability, comprehensiveness, and practicality of each. The synthesis aims to inform development of relevant indicators to East Africa which will be validated using case studies and stakeholder workshops.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ASDS	Agricultural Sector Development Strategy
CAADP	Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Program
HNVF	High Nature Value Farming
IAA	Integrated Aqua-agriculture
IDA	Index of Agrobiodiversity
IDEA	Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development
NRMS	Natural Resource Management Systems
OASIS	Original agroecological Survey Indicator Systems
ODA	Official Development Assistance
PrAEctiCe	Potentials of agroecological Practices in East Africa
SAFA	Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems
SAFE	Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SOCLA	Sociedad Científica Latinoamericana de Agroecología
TAPE	Tool for Agro-ecology Performance Evaluation
WEAI	Women Empowerment in Agriculture Index

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

As the global population continues to grow and the consequences of climate change and natural disasters become increasingly dire, the prevailing models of food production and consumption have undergone a profound transformation towards industrial farming as a means to address these challenges [1]. However, the practice of industrial agriculture involves the heavy use of fertilizers, which significantly contributes to greenhouse gas emissions and soil degradation. This, in turn, leads to reduced crop yields and a diminished supply of clean water [2]. Moreover, industrial farming falls short of providing a comprehensive solution for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which primarily aim to ensure food security, promote food sovereignty, safeguard ecological sustainability, protect the environment, and address climate adaptation and mitigation [3]. It is widely acknowledged that effecting changes in these systems is imperative to successfully realize the SDGs [4].

The United Nations 2030 Agenda for "Sustainable Development - Transforming Our World," which went into effect in 2016, put the 17 SDGs on the global agenda [5]. This collection of universal goals, developed in response to the world's critical ecological, social, political, and economic crises, has become a vital guidepost for anybody working on agroecological issues [4]. There is an expanding body of research demonstrating the positive impacts of agroecology, particularly on the environment and household income. These include enhancing livelihoods and local economies, boosting food security and resilience, diversifying food production and diets, promoting health and nutrition, protecting natural resources, biodiversity, and ecosystem functions, enhancing soil fertility and health, adapting to and mitigating climate change, assisting in the empowerment of women, and preserving regional culture and traditional knowledge systems [4, 6, 7], which at the same time are the main challenges affecting successful and sustainable transition to agroecological farming practices.

However, due to various techniques and data, as well as different dimensions and periods, these results in East Africa remain fragmented. Furthermore, the majority of the evidence utilized in East Africa is found in "gray literature," which is generally extremely context-dependent and peer-reviewed [8]. This necessitates the collection of consistent information on the multifaceted performances of agroecology in order to guide policymaking. Several previous studies have concentrated on selecting appropriate indicators for measuring socioeconomic and environmental consequences [9], [10]. Some of the indicators, however, fail to reflect more sophisticated sustainability framings, such as social themes focusing on farmer characteristics. Furthermore, despite the fact that agroecology in East Africa is quite diversified, smallholder farmers who already practice agroecology do not often identify themselves as practitioners.

The agroecological transition is also challenged by a lack of access to appropriate extension services, non-implementation of pro-agroecological policies, the influx of synthetic agricultural inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides, and industrial farming methods that both governments and private institutions aggressively promote to increase cash crop production, putting pressures on the agroecological transition [11, 12]. Failure to include farmers in the evaluation framework process further limits the agroecology framework's relevance and usefulness to farmers in real-world settings. Furthermore, most present techniques are aimed at development agencies and policymakers rather than farmers [13], resulting in extremely detailed, often quite theoretical data collection methodologies that are far removed from the realities of East African farmers. This clearly demonstrates a paucity of East African indicator frameworks and methods that target smallholder agricultural systems.

In addition, the present frameworks do not address aquaculture and the circular water energy food system in sufficient detail to allow for an in-depth examination of consequences. This has resulted in a paucity of evidence on the effects of integrated aqua-agriculture (IAA) practices as an agroecology practise, despite the fact that IAA

practices are critical to a sustainable agroecology production system because they integrate aquaculture with crop production in a mixed farming system, which has many ecological and agricultural added values [7].

This review intends to fill this gap by examining existing agroecological frameworks relevant to East Africa, which will aid in identifying the most appropriate indicator set fitted to the East African environment and capturing IAA practices in detail. The Indicator Framework is designed to aid in the assessment of environmental and socioeconomic implications, with a special emphasis on the effects of climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as financial sustainability. Agroecology consultants in East Africa may utilize the indicator set to identify and monitor the adoption and performance of optimal combinations of agricultural methods, therefore assisting smallholder farmers in their agroecological transition.

1.2 Importance of Sustainability and Agroecological Indicators in East Africa

The significance of sustainability and agroecological indicators in East Africa cannot be overstated, as they are pivotal in ensuring the survival and prosperity of both those engaged in food production and the broader global community. The COVID-19 crisis, a stark reminder of the fragility of our food systems, demonstrated the vulnerability of current practices and value chains [14]. However, the impending challenge of climate change, unfolding over a longer time horizon, presents an even more profound threat to these systems.

Agroecology emerges as a beacon of hope, offering a potentially transformative approach to mitigating and adapting agricultural systems to climate change while bolstering their resilience. Scientific experts, practitioners, activists, and producers are all working to establish it as a method of producing, processing, and eating food that takes into account social, economic, and environmental considerations [15]. Indicators in each of the three pillars must be policy-relevant. They must give accurate information at an appropriate geographical level to aid policymakers in their decisions [16]. Nevertheless, our ability to harness the full potential of agroecological practices hinges on the availability of comprehensive and robust agroecological indicators that facilitate comparative assessments of our farming systems [17].

Further, agroecology is also getting political attention owing to its potential to improve the sustainability of our food systems [18]. According to the World Commission on Environmental Development (1987), sustainability implies meeting the requirements of the current generation without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to fulfill their own needs. In East Africa, millions of livelihoods are intricately linked to nature-rich farming systems, relying on the diverse contributions of the environment for sustenance and income. These contributions are multifaceted and play a fundamental role in ensuring the long-term sustainability of these systems. Yet, all too often, key stakeholders in agriculture remain unaware of or underestimate the profound relevance of these natural contributions. Such oversight can have significant implications for decisions related to land management and agricultural practices.

Therefore, a pressing need exists for the development of localized agroecological indicators specific to East Africa. These indicators serve a critical purpose by enabling us to evaluate how farming practices, particularly those that draw more heavily upon the natural environment, including agroecological approaches, impact the livelihoods and overall well-being of farmers in the region. Recognizing and measuring the interplay between nature and agriculture through tailored indicators is a pivotal step towards building resilient, integrated, intensified, and sustainable food systems that can withstand the challenges posed by climate change and disruptions like the COVID-19 crisis. In essence, sustainability and agroecological indicators in East Africa are not merely instruments for assessment; they represent a lifeline for the region's food security, economic stability, and ecological integrity in an era defined by unprecedented challenges.

2. CONTEXTUALIZING SUSTAINABILITY AND AGROECOLOGY IN EAST AFRICA

2.1 Environmental and Agricultural Challenges in East Africa

Smallholder agriculture in East African countries has been facing numerous constraints. While some are unique to each of the countries, most are similar, implying that common solutions would address them across countries. The constraints discussed below are not new, but rather long-standing and perhaps even chronic. In addition to smallholder farmers, the constraints to some extent also impact large-scale or plantation farmers.

a. Climate Change and Related Food Security Challenges

Climate change, primarily driven by global warming, has emerged as a significant factor contributing to the agricultural challenges faced by East Africa [19]. East Africa's agriculture heavily relies on rain-fed systems, making it highly susceptible to unpredictable shifts in weather patterns. Over the past three decades, the region has experienced a concerning increase in the frequency of both droughts and floods, which have had dire consequences for crop yields and livestock [20].

One of the most pressing issues exacerbated by climate change is the growing vulnerability of East Africa's agricultural lands due to land degradation. The diminishing resilience of the land has intensified the impact of droughts and floods, amplifying their devastating effects. For instance, in 2008, Kenya witnessed a substantial drop of approximately 6 percent in its tea production, primarily attributed to an early-season drought [21]. This drought episode had far-reaching consequences, as it led the Kenyan government to declare a national emergency in early 2009. During this crisis, an alarming 10 million citizens were at risk of food shortages, prompting an urgent appeal for USD 400 million in aid [21]. The emergency situation was further compounded by a combination of factors, including high food prices and the aftermath of post-election violence, which disrupted farming activities in the Rift Valley, a key agricultural region in the country.

Unfortunately, the region's capacity to predict and respond to such climatic challenges remains limited. Unlike countries like India, where sophisticated ground-and-satellite-based systems are employed to forecast medium-term weather and seasonal agricultural output, East Africa lags behind in establishing comprehensive early-warning systems [21]. This crucial gap in forecasting and preparedness hinders the timely mitigation of food security crises caused by climate-related events.

b. Land Tenure, Access Rights and Land Management

The complexities surrounding land tenure and limited land access pose significant obstacles to small-scale agriculture in East Africa [22]. These issues warrant examination from various perspectives, highlighting the multifaceted nature of the challenge. Weaknesses within the land tenure system, such as uncertain land rights, unequal land distribution, and the absence of mechanisms for transferring and consolidating land holdings, collectively contribute to underdeveloped agriculture, high levels of landlessness, food insecurity, and the degradation of natural resources [23].

Moreover, available land in East Africa is often fragmented into small, economically unsustainable parcels, resulting in fragmented production systems and diminished productivity. Farm sizes can be as modest as approximately 2 hectares per household in Tanzania and 2.5 hectares in Uganda and Kenya [24]. While these land holdings in East African countries exceed the continental average of 1.6 hectares, they remain significantly smaller in comparison to North America (121 hectares), Latin America (67 hectares), and Europe (27 hectares) [25].

Complicating matters further is the highly unequal distribution of available land. Households in the highest per capita land quartile in East and Southern Africa control 5 to 15 times more land than households in the lowest quartile. For instance, in Kenya, the mean farm size for the top land quartile was 6.69 hectares, whereas the bottom quartile had access to a mere 0.58 hectares, including rented land [21].

Equally vital is the sustainable management of existing land resources to ensure long-term productivity. Land degradation, particularly through erosion and soil fertility loss, poses a substantial threat to the continuity of agricultural productivity in East Africa, as highlighted by [26]. Over the past few decades, several initiatives, including those supported by the Swedish International Development Agency and other development partners, have aimed to safeguard agricultural land in the region. These endeavors underscore the imperative for clear land-use and agricultural policies, which can provide a comprehensive framework guiding researchers, extension workers, and smallholder farmers in adopting environmentally-friendly practices. Nevertheless, the persistence of issues surrounding property rights and uneven land access continues to exacerbate the problem of land degradation.

c. Financing Agriculture and Access to Credit

Smallholder farmers in East African countries heavily rely on their meager incomes for investment, which often restricts opportunities for expansion. For instance, a survey conducted between May and August 2001 in Tanzania, encompassing 344 rural households, unveiled that half of their total income originated from farming, while approximately 46.6 percent came from non-farm employment (both wages and self-employment), with less than 4 percent attributed to remittances. Unfortunately, due to a lack of collateral and limited credit history, most farmers find themselves excluded from financial support not only from commercial and national development banks but also from formal micro-credit institutions. Consequently, farmers often turn to their own resources, income from friends and relatives, remittances, and informal money lenders to fund their agricultural endeavors [27].

Across East African nations, commercial banks' loans to the agriculture sector have consistently remained disproportionately low when compared to investments in manufacturing, trade, and other service sectors. This discrepancy has hampered the expansion of agricultural activities and the adoption of modern technologies. For example, in Kenya, smallholders frequently cite the lack of capital and access to affordable credit as the primary factors behind low agricultural productivity [28]. In Tanzania, access to formal credit is primarily limited to major urban centers, where stringent collateral requirements are in place [29]. In Uganda, the agriculture sector is hindered by high interest rates that discourage agricultural investments [30]. While micro-finance institutions have made commendable strides in extending financial services to millions of previously unbankable clients through innovative instruments, they have largely struggled to reach the poorest rural areas and smallholder agricultural producers who operate within highly seasonal and risk-prone environments [31]. The successes of these new financing initiatives in serving the financial needs of the poor, including smallholders, deserve acknowledgment.

Moreover, most African governments allocate a meager portion of their budgets to agriculture, averaging only 6 percent of total expenditures since 1980. Some nations allocate as little as 1 percent of their budgets to this critical sector. This low level of public spending is especially concerning, given the dire need for improved rural infrastructure, including energy, roads, and water supply, as well as the imperative to develop efficient input and output markets and robust extension services [32]. Despite an increase in the absolute amount of Official Development Assistance (ODA) directed toward agriculture and rural development in East Africa, the share of development aid allocated to this sector has been on a declining trajectory.

For instance, in 1999, ODA for agriculture and rural development in the region amounted to a mere USD 221 million, which more than doubled to USD 634 million by 2007. However, these figures pale in comparison to the annual estimate of approximately USD 18 billion per year as projected by the NEPAD Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Program (CAADP) to achieve the World Food Summit's objective of halving hunger across the entire African continent [21]. Moreover, the majority of this aid has been focused on rural development and infrastructure,

with relatively less emphasis on agricultural research and extension services. Consequently, the percentage of aid allocated to agriculture and rural development in the region dwindled from 11.8 percent to a mere 3.5 percent between 1995 and 2005, with a modest recovery to 5.4 percent in 2007. Nevertheless, this figure remains exceptionally low compared to the previously observed percentage of ODA allocated to agriculture and rural development (i.e., 11.8 percent in 1995). In essence, the inadequate funding for agricultural operations in East Africa continues to impede the farming activities of smallholder farmers.

d. Access to Input and Output Markets

Efficient access to input and output markets plays a pivotal role in the transformation of the agricultural sector, transitioning it from subsistence to commercial production. It is essential for smallholder farmers to harness the potential of these markets, engage in local-level value addition, and face healthy competition [33]. However, East African nations are grappling with the challenges of marketing both agricultural inputs and outputs, and the existing markets are ill-equipped to cater to the needs of impoverished populations [34].

A survey conducted during the 2005/2006 household assessment in Uganda revealed that 30 percent of surveyed communities lacked passable roads even in dry seasons, and two-thirds of these communities had no access to bus or taxi services [35]. Additionally, in most East African countries, over half of the population resides five hours or more away from a market center.

Turning to agricultural inputs, the average fertilizer application rates for arable crops in East African nations are alarmingly low, estimated at 30 kg/ha/year in Kenya, 5 kg/ha/year in Tanzania, and 1 kg/ha/year in Uganda. These figures are significantly below the global average of 100 kg/ha/year [36]. Furthermore, high input costs and wastage are pervasive issues, leading farmers to reduce their usage of quality inputs like improved seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides. For instance, in 2006, it was reported that only 6.3 percent of agricultural land in Uganda was cultivated with improved seeds, while fertilizers, agro-chemicals, and manure were applied to just 1.0 percent, 3.4 percent, and 6.8 percent of the land, respectively [37]. Similarly, the 2007 Tanzania's Poverty and Human Development Report disclosed that 87 percent of Tanzanian farmers abstained from using chemical fertilizers, 77 percent avoided improved seeds, and 72 percent refrained from using pesticides, herbicides, or insecticides (agrochemicals) due to the prohibitively high costs of agricultural inputs and services [38].

On the output side, a substantial portion of smallholder farmers is engaged in subsistence farming, leading to underdeveloped and inefficient marketing practices. Inadequate storage facilities further exacerbate challenges in marketing and food security. In Africa, significant quantities of agricultural commodities produced by farmers often go to waste due to a lack of proper marketing channels, while smallholder farmers lack the technology necessary for timely consumption [39]. Another notable obstacle on the output side is the limited integration of most smallholders into supermarket chains. This is primarily due to their inability to meet the stringent quality and safety requirements, as well as the delivery schedules demanded by international value chains, preventing them from effectively competing in such markets [40].

e. Infrastructure

The agricultural sector in East Africa continues to face significant challenges due to poor infrastructure [41]. These challenges primarily revolve around the subpar condition of market facilities and transportation systems, encompassing roads and railways. Past infrastructure investments have often yielded limited benefits due to ineffective design and maintenance, exacerbated by the stop-and-start practices of donor-funded initiatives [42].

Among these infrastructure issues, the road system emerges as the most critical bottleneck for agricultural development, affecting the distribution of inputs and the transportation of agricultural produce to and from farms [43]. The lack of an adequate road network compels smallholder farmers to rely on inefficient modes of

transportation, including animal-powered methods. Furthermore, the region's irrigation facilities are underdeveloped, with less than 4 percent of total agricultural output being produced under irrigation in East Africa, in stark contrast to the approximately 33 percent seen in Asia [44]. In East African countries, average post-harvest losses are staggering, estimated at over 40 percent and soaring to as high as 70 percent for certain fruits and vegetables [45].

In Kenya, the underdevelopment of rural roads and critical physical infrastructure has led to exorbitant transport costs for both agricultural products and farm inputs, eroding the competitiveness of local farmers [46]. Additionally, access to electricity in rural areas is often limited and costly, stifling investment in essential amenities such as cold storage facilities, irrigation systems, and agricultural processing units. This lack of infrastructure is particularly detrimental to the marketability of perishable goods like fish, dairy products, and vegetables [47], while also posing significant impediments to trade.

Uganda, for instance, relies on a single rail-line through Kenya to connect with coastal ports. As an illustration of the impact of infrastructure limitations, the Ugandan government reported a drop in coffee exports in January 2009, with a decrease in both volume (8 percent) and value (23 percent, equivalent to USD 10 million). These declines were attributed to logistical challenges and a restricted supply of containers compared to the same month in 2008 [48].

f. Agricultural Extension and Innovation

The provision of research and extension services has faced fragmentation and inefficiency, impeding the widespread adoption of technological advancements. On average, the East African countries allocate less than 0.7 percent of their agricultural GDP to research [49]. In contrast, some developed countries allocate as much as 3 percent of their agricultural GDP to research. In Kenya, during the 1990s, the effectiveness of extension services declined due to several factors, including the inadequacy of the training and visit extension model, delays in adopting alternative approaches, and significant reductions in the operational budgets of the relevant sector ministries [50].

In Tanzania, extension services primarily focused on increasing production through short-term technical packages, often overlooking the specific circumstances of farmers, market dynamics, and sustainability concerns. Despite multiple efforts to strengthen these services, the linkages between research, extension, and training remained weak, and collaboration between public and private partners was limited. The limited diffusion of technology and innovation in both Tanzania and Kenya is evident from their low rankings on the UNDP Technology Achievement Index (TAI), where they were categorized as marginalized with scores of 0.080 and 0.129, respectively [51].

In Uganda, smallholder farming is grappling with new institutional challenges arising from private sector governance structures, such as buyer-driven food chains and supermarkets that uphold high-quality and sanitary standards [52]. The removal of implicit and explicit taxes, combined with the liberalization of the marketing system, substantially increased the share of the producer in the price of export crops, with some cases seeing an increase from 9 percent to as high as 70 percent, especially in the coffee sector. While these measures have positive aspects in removing market distortions, smallholder farmers encounter difficulties when competing in these newly liberalized markets.

g. Policy-Related and Institutional Constraints

Over time, East African countries have implemented a series of economic reforms and introduced agricultural policies and strategic frameworks. However, the expected positive and lasting outcomes from these policies have yet to be realized [53]. The primary remaining policy challenges encompass land tenure and distribution among different population segments, the marketing of agricultural products and inputs, and the regulatory frameworks governing prices. In Kenya, for instance, persistent high levels of public borrowing and elevated lending rates have deterred investment in the agricultural sector [21]. While Tanzania has introduced numerous agricultural reforms

and strategies, including the Agricultural Development Framework in the early 1970s and the Agricultural Sector Development Strategy (ASDS), most of these policies have had limited impact on the majority of smallholder farmers. In Uganda, despite the adoption of the Plan for Modernization of Agriculture in 2002, smallholder farmers still receive a disproportionately small share of developmental resources [54].

Undoubtedly, the government's inability to fully implement these programs is partly due to its weak administrative and technical capacity, especially within the ministries of agriculture. Institutional support for agricultural development in East Africa has been inconsistent and often insufficient. As observed elsewhere in Africa, institutions responsible for agricultural development must be strengthened, with a focus on establishing well-functioning markets and effective risk management [55].

The experiences of successful agricultural reformers highlight the paramount importance of market-oriented reforms in achieving sustained productivity improvements in agriculture. For instance, the substantial increase in rice output and productivity in Vietnam during the period from 1981 to 1994 can be attributed primarily to market reforms, despite only modest growth in most inputs and limited technological changes. A key element in Vietnam's successful market reforms was an institutional change – the reform of land property rights, which significantly enhanced the economic incentives for efficient land use among farmers [56].

Conversely, Tanzania's experience illustrates that while market reforms are essential, they alone are insufficient to boost agricultural productivity. Despite undertaking substantial market-oriented reforms during the 1990s, the country's agricultural performance remained disappointing. The main obstacles to more effective supply responses by farmers to improved incentives were structural in nature, including limited access to markets, credit, and inadequate infrastructure [57]. Consequently, the combined experiences of Vietnam and Tanzania underscore the importance of reforming the institutional framework underpinning agriculture and the synergies between reforms in areas such as infrastructure, market access, and credit availability.

h. Food and Financial Crises

In 2007 and the first half of 2008, there was a global upsurge in food prices, reaching crisis levels. Both nominal and real international prices of major food commodities soared to their highest points in nearly three decades during the first half of 2008 [58]. Although the food market situation varied from country to country, the future trajectory of food prices remained uncertain. Some projections suggested a lasting shift to higher levels, while others considered it a temporary disruption that would eventually revert to long-term price trends [59]. Globally, food prices did decline from their peak but remained elevated compared to pre-crisis levels, with the potential for sharp increases in the future.

This food crisis had extensive repercussions, including macroeconomic instability and an increase in poverty and hunger levels in many African countries. A vulnerability index developed by the African Development Bank in 2007 ranked Kenya as the most vulnerable country among the East African nations studied, with Uganda rated as moderately vulnerable and Tanzania characterized as having low vulnerability [60].

In 2008, the high global food prices contributed to significant inflation in the East African countries under examination, especially in Kenya, where inflation surged from 9.8 percent in 2007 to 25.8 percent in 2008. Inflation also rose in Uganda and Tanzania in 2008, reaching 12 percent and 10.3 percent, respectively, up from 6.1 percent and 7.0 percent in 2007. This inflationary pressure led many smallholder farmers in East Africa to reduce the areas they planted. However, some medium and large-scale farmers capitalized on emerging market opportunities and increased their production. Some producers even shifted from subsistence farming to higher-yielding crops with better returns per unit of land. For instance, in Uganda, some producers began selling high-value food staples like "matoke" and purchased cheaper foods such as maize or cassava flour [61]. By mid-2009, most commodity prices had fallen but they still remained elevated compared to pre-crisis levels.

The causes of the food crisis in East Africa varied from one country to another. Feedback from Food and Crop Assessments and relief agencies indicated that rising fuel prices played a role in driving up food prices across all the countries covered in this study. Escalating transportation costs affected both the prices of agricultural inputs and outputs. In Kenya, for instance, the cost of fertilizer more than doubled, reaching USD 1212 per metric ton in the 2008/2009 production season, up from USD 550 per metric ton the previous year. Additionally, civil unrest in Kenya and northern parts of Uganda had a significant impact. Furthermore, food prices continued to be influenced by production levels, with unfavorable agro-climatic conditions such as drought playing a key role in price increases in Kenya and Tanzania [62].

Interestingly, food trends in East Africa did not always align with global trends. For instance, in 2008, maize prices in Kenya initially fell between May and June to USD 320 per ton before rising to approximately USD 340 in July. In contrast, Tanzania experienced a continuous decline in maize prices, falling from around USD 330 per ton in January to about USD 240 in July 2008. The significant price disparities in cereals between East African countries were a reflection of the fragmented nature of their markets, primarily stemming from government controls and inadequate transport infrastructure [63].

i. Volatility in International Fuel Prices

Over the past two years, international oil prices have exhibited significant volatility. This fluctuation in oil prices poses challenges for smallholder farmers and those living below the poverty line in Africa and other developing nations. East African countries, being net oil importers, are particularly vulnerable to the unpredictability of oil prices. A study conducted in East Africa revealed that a mere 1% increase in global oil prices could lead to a 0.26% increase in the price of maize [64]. High fuel prices contribute to an elevated import bill, resulting in the deterioration of the trade balance, currency depreciation, and unfavorable balance of payment situations [65]. Such balance of payment deficits can lead to a depletion of official foreign exchange reserves.

The recent upsurge in oil prices has prompted some governments and investors to divert attention and allocate limited resources to the production of crops for biofuels. This strategy of promoting biofuel crop production at the expense of food crop cultivation warrants re-evaluation to avoid displacing essential food crops and driving up food prices. However, with the substantial decrease in fuel prices, the attractiveness of biofuel production has diminished, potentially reversing the growth in biofuel crop cultivation [66].

Despite the decrease in oil prices, persistent supply challenges continue to prevent consumers from reaping the benefits of low crude oil prices. Local oil marketers pass on the elevated transport and operational costs to consumers. High oil prices result in increased energy, transport, and production expenses that farmers are unable to fully transfer to buyers, resulting in reduced profits for farmers. Moreover, high fuel prices have had a detrimental impact on budget positions, affecting governments' ability to meet the financial requirements in economic and social sectors [67].

2.2 Role of Agroecology in Addressing Regional Challenges

Eastern Africa, like many regions across the continent, faces numerous challenges within its food systems and agricultural sector. These challenges are multifaceted, encompassing issues related to sustainability, food security, nutrition, gender equality, and economic development [68]. Agroecology, a holistic approach to farming and food production, is emerging as a powerful solution to address these challenges and transform Eastern Africa's agricultural landscape [69].

a. Agroecology for Sustainable Farming Systems

One of the pressing concerns in Eastern Africa is the sustainability of farming systems [70]. Traditional agricultural practices often contribute to carbon emissions, soil degradation, and loss of biodiversity. Agroecology, on the other hand, offers environmentally friendly technologies and methodologies that prioritize soil health, conservation, and sustainable efficiency [71].

Agroecological systems rely on integrated practices such as crop rotation, cover cropping, water harvesting, and conservation methods. These practices promote food systems that not only conserve the environment but also contribute to the long-term sustainability of agriculture [72]. Successful agroecological cases demonstrate how these methods can be scaled up to benefit a significant number of farmers and consumers in Eastern Africa.

b. Addressing Food Security and Nutrition

Eastern Africa grapples with food security and nutrition challenges, which have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic [71]. Beyond merely increasing calorie production, addressing these issues requires a focus on soil health and farmer-managed seed systems. Agroecology offers best practices to tackle food and nutrition insecurity by emphasizing proper nutrition, micronutrient availability, and healthy diets [73].

Unhealthy diets and lifestyles are closely linked to non-communicable diseases, escalating healthcare costs, decreased productivity, and health disparities. Agroecological approaches can play a pivotal role in promoting optimal health, reducing the risk of chronic diseases, and eliminating health inequities and disparities [74].

c. Empowering Women and Youth

Rural women are the backbone of agriculture in Eastern Africa, yet they often face challenges in accessing resources and opportunities for advancement. By promoting gender-inclusive agroecology, the region can tap into the potential of women farmers, boost agricultural yields, and enhance household food security [75]. Presentations in this sub-theme will underscore the contributions of women, their traditional knowledge, and their role in promoting safe and healthy livelihoods through agroecological practices.

Additionally, the youth population in Eastern Africa is significant, and their involvement in agriculture is crucial for the region's future. Through innovative approaches and digital technologies, young people are unlocking the potential of food and agriculture. These innovations not only reduce poverty but also bridge the rural-urban divide, create employment opportunities, and provide access to information, technology, and markets [76].

d. Promoting Organic Trade and Markets

The organic trade sector is rapidly growing globally, offering opportunities for Eastern Africa to tap into this market. By understanding the stimulants and barriers to organic trade, Eastern Africa can harness the potential of this sector for economic growth and sustainability [77].

2.3 Significance of Indicator Frameworks in East African Agriculture

Agroecology indicator frameworks play a crucial role in East Africa, just as they do in many other regions around the world. East Africa faces various agricultural and environmental challenges, including climate change, land

degradation, food security issues, and the need to improve the livelihoods of small-scale farmers. Agroecology, with its focus on sustainable and holistic farming practices, can offer significant benefits in addressing these challenges [78]. Here's the role agroecology indicator frameworks in East African agriculture:

a. Sustainability Assessment

Agroecology indicator frameworks provide a structured way to assess the sustainability of agricultural practices in East Africa. They allow for the measurement of key environmental, social, and economic indicators, which is vital for understanding the impact of different agricultural systems on the region's ecosystems and communities [79]. The results from such assessment frameworks can be used to identify when agroecological practices are effective at meeting multiple locally or globally important outcomes, and when trade-offs arise between development objectives. Establishing these evidence banks provides a valuable resource to catalyze investment in agroecology by both private and public sector actors to transform food systems to meet production, environmental and social goals in tandem [80].

b. Local Relevance

East Africa is characterized by diverse agroecological zones and farming practices. An indicator framework that can be adapted and localized to specific contexts is essential [81]. Agroecology frameworks allow communities to select indicators that are relevant to their unique challenges and priorities, ensuring that interventions align with local needs and aspirations. For instance, most assessment frameworks struggle to balance the trade-off between capturing standardized, globally comparable metrics or capturing metrics that are locally relevant and context-specific. These factors make it challenging to assess the multi-functional and multidimensional performance of Agroecology across food systems in diverse contexts. This is particularly true for frameworks developed in the Global North, which may not be applicable to the conditions present in the Global South [82].

An excellent example is the TAPE framework which was designed to provide an analytical framework for collecting evidence on the environmental, social, economic, health and nutrition, as well as governance aspects of sustainability – at multiple scales and in varying locations and timeframes. While TAPE provides a strong foundation for our work, it relies on a relatively small set of performance indicators linked to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [79], which are not necessarily aligned with local sustainability objectives and performance areas that are of high priority for our project. Therefore, there is a critical need for an AE-specific assessment framework that not only integrates key features of AE, but also encompasses the salient features of local AE endeavors.

c. Resilience to Climate Change

East Africa is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, including droughts and unpredictable weather patterns. The last IPCC report indicates that the rise of CO₂ and associated “greenhouse gasses” could lead to a 1.4 to 5.8 °C increase in global surface temperatures, with subsequent consequences on precipitation frequency and amounts [83]. Temperature and water availability remain key factors in determining crop growth and productivity; predicted changes in these factors will lead to reduced crop yields. Climate-induced changes in insect pest, pathogen and weed population dynamics and invasiveness could compound such effects. Undoubtedly, climate- and weather-induced instability will affect levels of and access to food supply, altering social and economic stability and regional competitiveness [84]. The biggest and most durable benefits will likely result from development of agroecological indicators related to soil health, water management, and crop diversity which can help strengthen the resilience of farmers and rural communities and help them adapt to changing climate conditions.

d. Biodiversity Conservation

The region's rich biodiversity is under threat from unsustainable agricultural practices. In agricultural systems, the level of existing biodiversity can make the difference between the system being stressed or resilient when confronting a biotic or abiotic perturbation. In all agroecosystems, a diversity of organisms is required for ecosystem function and to provide environmental services [85]. When agroecosystems are simplified, whole functional groups of species are removed shifting the balance of the system from a desired to a less desired state, affecting their capacity to respond to changes and to generate ecosystem services [86]. Agroecological approaches, which emphasize biodiversity conservation, can help reverse this trend. Indicator frameworks can measure the impact of agroecology on biodiversity preservation, including the diversity of crop varieties, trees, and beneficial insects.

e. Food Security

East Africa faces food security challenges, with a large portion of the population relying on small-scale agriculture for their livelihoods. Agroecology promotes diversified farming systems, which can improve food production and nutritional diversity [87]. Indicator frameworks can assess the impact of agroecology on crop yields, food access, and dietary diversity relevant for the region.

f. Community Empowerment

Agroecological practices prioritize community involvement and empowerment. It's now widely recognized that local communities should play a central role in every stage of project planning and execution, including the selection, collection, and monitoring of indicators [88]. In essence, these indicators should not only resonate with the local population but also employ straightforward methods for data collection, interpretation, and presentation, making them accessible to non-specialists. This approach enables active participation by local communities throughout the process.

Furthermore, indicators must adapt over time to reflect evolving community engagement and changing circumstances [89]. As a result, indicator frameworks empower communities by giving them ownership over the data and decision-making processes related to their agricultural practices [90]. These frameworks foster a dynamic process that enhances the overall understanding of environmental and social challenges, facilitates community capacity building, and serves as a valuable guide for policymaking and development initiatives.

g. Policy and Investment

Governments, NGOs, and other stakeholders can use data from agroecology indicator frameworks to inform policies and investments [91]. Evidence-based information on the benefits of agroecology can drive support and designing of suitable funding models for sustainable farming practices in the region.

h. Long-Term Impact

Agroecology is not just about short-term gains but also about building resilience and ensuring the well-being of future generations. Indicator frameworks can track the long-term impact of agroecological interventions, helping to demonstrate their value over time [92].

3. CRITERIA FOR SELECTION OF INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS

Selecting appropriate indicator frameworks for agroecological assessments in East Africa involved considering various criteria to ensure their relevance and effectiveness in this specific context. As a result, a systematic literature review (SLR) strategy was utilized in the study to identify existing and appropriate agroecological indicator frameworks in East Africa. SLR is a way of doing a literature review that is commonly used to assess the state of knowledge on a certain issue [93]. Because the SLR technique is more rigorous, systematic, and resilient [93], it is more suited to structuring observations of emerging literatures. Based on well specified research topics and techniques, SLR may also detect gaps and give information through extensive summaries of evidence obtained in certain literature bases [94].

We searched scholarly abstract and reference databases for literature describing existing agroecological indicator systems. Google Scholar, Web of Science™, and Scopus were among them. The databases were chosen because they exclusively contain peer-reviewed research, provide substantial and up-to-date coverage of multidisciplinary academic literature, and enable systematic searches [95]. Other databases, such as Scielo, Landindex, DOAJ, and Dialnet, were explored to search for further information, but they were excluded because they lack advanced research tools and Boolean operators that allow systematic queries. The key terms used in the searches included: Agroecolog*, indicator framework* and East Afric*.

The process was iterative allowing different key terms to be explored. Foremost we used the key terms agroecology and East Africa. East Africa had a dearth of agroecological indicator frameworks. A lot of information had to be borrowed from other countries with existing indicator frameworks which were explained in the context of East Africa. We there decided to expand our search to global level by excluding the key term East Afric*. The phrase agroecology was written in three distinct forms that may arise in the literature: agro ecolog*, agroecolog*, and agro-ecolog*, separated by the Boolean operator "OR".

Despite the fact that the final search keywords were very broad, the results were selected using stringent inclusion/exclusion criteria for relevant research applicable at the local level in East Africa. We entered the key phrases into the Topic search section in Web of Science, and the query keywords into the Title-Abstract-Keyword search area in Scopus. We chose publications published between January 2001 and January 2023. The agroecology research query yielded a large number of results (554 in Scopus, 498 in Web of Science, and 596 in Google Scholar), so we chose to include "indicator framework" as a key term. The term "indicator framework" yielded a representative sample of agroecological indicator frameworks in use. The three abstract and citation databases produced 1648 items.

To create the article database, we used the PRISMA statement [96]. Identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion were the four filtering phases employed (Figure 1). The screening process included a review of the article's information, including titles, document types, and topic areas. This aided us in the initial filtering of the database by removing duplicates (n=416), records that did not meet peer-reviewed journal article standards (introduction, methods, results, discussion, conclusion: n = 49), records that did not contain any of the search terms in their title, abstract, or keywords (n = 87), and records that were not in English (n = 62). As a consequence, we chose 1034 recordings for the next phases.

During the eligibility criterion step, different article attributes were scrutinized in order to include the most relevant articles for in-depth research. We removed records that were inaccessible (n=24), did not pertain to agroecology (n=220), and lacked agroecological indicator frameworks (n=456). This resulted in 334 papers to be screened and analyzed.

FIGURE 1: PRISMA STATEMENT PROCESS UNDERTAKEN FOR THE SELECTION OF RELEVANT ARTICLES

Some of the frameworks designed for evaluating the sustainability of agroecological practices were removed from the 334 records because they were unable to properly assist stakeholders in the sustainability evaluation process. The frameworks ignored the integration of indicators as well as the interdependence of the indicators. Other papers were removed since they were primarily concerned with the environmental implications of farms, which were often combined with economic success.

Furthermore, several of the omitted agroecological indicator frameworks were created with specific purposes and goals in mind. Some frameworks, for example, are exclusively intended to quantify a farm's carbon footprint or soil health, focusing primarily on a certain set of indicators related to the aims while ignoring others. Some of the indicator frameworks were also geared toward specific farming sectors (e.g., floriculture), and thus can only be used in specific farms, whereas others had too many indicators, which if considered, makes data collection and processing difficult to handle at a reasonable cost, redundancies may appear, and the content provided by the indicator set becomes difficult to understand. Conversely, the records with few indicators were also omitted. [97] asserts unequivocally that when only a few indicators are examined, crucial advances may go unnoticed, and trade-offs are not appropriately considered when focusing on a specific area of the system.

We therefore remained with 9 articles (Table 1) which were the most relevant to this study. In-depth screening was further done on the remaining 9 records to document the agro ecological indicator frameworks based on;

- a. Region-specific criteria.
- b. Relevance to East African Agroecological Context
- c. Alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

3.1 Region-Specific Criteria

- a. **Agroecological Diversity:** East Africa encompasses a wide range of agroecological zones, from arid regions to highlands. Generally, the climate and topography range from wet highlands to arid lowlands and coastal areas [98]. This agroecological diversity has significant implications for agriculture and food systems in the region. To effectively address the challenges and harness the opportunities presented by this diversity, the frameworks were screened to ensure they are flexible enough to accommodate this diversity and capture the unique challenges and opportunities presented by different ecosystems.
- b. **Local Stakeholder Involvement:** The framework must emphasize active participation from local communities, farmers, and other stakeholders in its design and implementation. It should align with East African cultural and social norms to encourage community engagement.
- c. **Data Accessibility:** Ensuring that data collection methods and technology are accessible and affordable to local communities is crucial. The framework should not rely on sophisticated equipment or extensive training, making it feasible for non-specialists to use effectively.

3.2 Relevance to East African Agroecological Context

- a. **Biodiversity Conservation:** Given East Africa's rich biodiversity, the framework should prioritize indicators related to the preservation and enhancement of biodiversity. This includes assessing the diversity of crop varieties, trees, and beneficial insects.
- b. **Climate Resilience:** Climate change poses a significant threat to agriculture in the region [99]. The framework should include indicators that measure the resilience of agroecological practices to climate variability and extremes, such as droughts and floods.
- c. **Food Security:** East Africa faces food security challenges, and the framework should incorporate indicators that assess food production, access, and dietary diversity. It should help identify strategies to improve food security for local communities. The agroecosystems should provide sufficient, nutritious and culturally appropriate food for the populace and the framework to evaluate this context should consider ecological, social and economic dimensions to ensure a holistic understanding of food security.
- d. **Soil and Water Management:** Sustainable soil and water management are critical in East Africa [100]. The framework should include indicators related to soil health, erosion control, and efficient water use to maintain agricultural productivity.

3.3 Alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

- **SDG Integration:** The selected framework should align with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It should be designed to measure progress toward specific SDGs related to poverty reduction, hunger eradication, gender equality, and environmental sustainability.
- **Cross-cutting Goals:** The framework should encompass indicators that address multiple SDGs simultaneously. For example, agroecological practices that promote gender equity, such as women's participation in decision-making, can contribute to achieving both gender equality (SDG 5) and sustainable agriculture (SDG 2).
- **Long-term Impact:** The indicators should be capable of measuring the long-term impact of agroecological practices on the achievement of SDGs. This includes assessing their contribution to poverty alleviation, improved nutrition, and reduced environmental degradation over time.

4. IDENTIFICATION OF RELEVANT INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS

The process of identifying relevant indicator frameworks for agroecological assessments in East Africa was critical to ensuring that the chosen frameworks align with the region's specific needs and challenges. This involved a systematic approach that incorporated a literature review, consultations with experts and practitioners, and an initial screening and shortlisting of potential frameworks.

a. Literature Review and Desk Research

The process began with a comprehensive literature review and desk research. This step involved scouring academic papers, reports, and publications related to agroecology, sustainable agriculture, and indicator frameworks. The aim was to identify existing frameworks that have been used or proposed in similar contexts or regions. This literature review helped in understanding the state of the art in agroecological assessment and provided insights into the indicators and methodologies that have been previously employed. It also allowed for the identification of any gaps or limitations in existing frameworks.

b. Consultations with Regional Experts and Practitioners

To gain a deeper understanding of the specific challenges and opportunities in East Africa, consultations with regional experts and practitioners are crucial. This step involved engaging with individuals who have direct experience and knowledge of agriculture and agroecology in the region. These experts included researchers, agricultural extension workers, representatives from non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and local farmers. Through interviews, surveys, and workshops, their insights were collected regarding the unique agroecological characteristics of East Africa, as well as the challenges and goals of local communities. These consultations helped in identifying the specific criteria and priorities that should guide the selection of indicator frameworks.

c. Initial Screening and Shortlisting

Based on the findings from the literature review and insights from regional experts and practitioners, the next step involved initial screening and shortlisting of potential indicator frameworks. This involved evaluating the identified frameworks against a set of predefined criteria. These criteria included: the relevance of the framework to East African agroecological contexts, its alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and its adaptability to diverse agroecological zones.

During the initial screening, frameworks that did not meet the essential criteria or were not adaptable to the region's diverse agroecological contexts were eliminated. The goal was to create a shortlist of candidate frameworks (Table 1) that have the potential to effectively assess and promote agroecological practices in East Africa.

TABLE 1: A SHORTLIST OF CANDIDATE FRAMEWORKS THAT HAVE THE POTENTIAL TO EFFECTIVELY ASSESS AND PROMOTE AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES IN EAST AFRICA

Name of the Indicator Framework included	Country of development	Countries it has been used	References
Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework	Malawi	Central Malawi, Ghana	[101]
A Tool for Agro-ecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) framework	Lesotho (FAO)	Thailand, Kenya, Tanzania	[102]
The five-dimensional SF Presidia framework	Italy	Italy, Austria, Bulgaria	[103]
Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development (IDEA)	France	France, Europe, Brazil	[104]
MESMIS Framework	Mexico	Mexico, Europe, Latin America (Argentina, Peru, Brazil, Bolivia), Spain, Portugal, United States	[105]
SOCLA Framework			[106]
OASIS (Original agroecological Survey Indicator Systems)	Europe	Kyrgyzstan (Central Asia), Croatia, Greece, Italy, France, Belgium	[4]
SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment)	Belgium	Belgium	[107]
SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems)	FAO	Kenya, Tanzania, Ethiopia, Mexico, Columbia, India, Germany, United Kingdom, Ireland, Nepal, Spain, Switzerland, Argentina, Thailand, Peru, New Zealand, Bolivia, Sao tome & Principe, NC USA, Quebec (Canada), Harker's Island (North Carolina), Brazil, Kushtia (Bangladesh)	[108]

5. IN-DEPTH REVIEW OF SHORTLISTED FRAMEWORKS

5.1 Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework [101]

5.1.1 Overview

The Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework is a comprehensive tool designed to evaluate the sustainability of agroecological practices, with a focus on enhancing both economic and environmental aspects of agriculture. This framework has been developed to provide researchers, practitioners, and policymakers with a structured approach for assessing the impacts and outcomes of agricultural innovations and practices. The framework is organized into five key domains, each addressing specific aspects of sustainability: Productivity, Economic, Environmental, Human Condition, and Social domains. These domains encompass a wide range of indicators and metrics that enable the assessment of agroecological practices from various angles, facilitating a holistic understanding of their sustainability implications.

Under the Productivity domain, the framework emphasizes the assessment of crop and animal productivity, input use efficiency, yield gaps, and other factors crucial for agricultural productivity. The Economic domain delves into profitability, income diversification, and market participation, considering economic aspects at both the household and community levels. In the Environmental domain, the framework examines essential factors such as vegetative cover, soil health, greenhouse gas emissions, and water quality, highlighting the importance of sustainable land and resource management. The Human Condition domain focuses on nutrition, food security, and health, recognizing the vital role of agriculture in ensuring the well-being of individuals and communities. Gender equity is integrated throughout the framework, acknowledging the importance of equitable access to resources, decision-making power, and benefits within agricultural systems. Furthermore, social indicators in the framework explore issues related to social cohesion, collective action, and community-level factors.

The Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework provides detailed guidance on data collection methods, enabling users to select appropriate indicators and measurement techniques tailored to their specific context. By doing so, it offers a flexible and adaptable tool that can be customized to suit the unique conditions and challenges faced by agricultural systems in East Africa.

This framework offers a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners engaged in evaluating agroecological practices, enabling them to systematically assess the economic and environmental sustainability of these practices. It not only facilitates the identification of strengths and weaknesses but also helps inform decision-making processes aimed at promoting sustainable agriculture in the region.

5.1.2 Objectives and Scope

The Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework is designed with specific objectives and a well-defined scope aimed at facilitating the evaluation of agroecological practices with a focus on sustainability. Here, we outline the primary objectives and the scope of this framework:

Objective

The primary objective of the framework is to assess the sustainability of agroecological practices. It seeks to provide a structured approach for evaluating the impacts and outcomes of these practices in terms of productivity, economic viability, environmental health, human well-being, and social equity.

The framework also aims to offer a holistic assessment of sustainability, recognizing that agriculture is a complex system with interconnected economic, environmental, social, and human dimensions. This enables users to understand the broader implications of agroecological innovations.

Another key objective is to provide decision-makers, including researchers, policymakers, and practitioners, with valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of specific agroecological practices. This information can guide the development and adoption of sustainable agricultural interventions.

The framework also places a strong emphasis on gender equity. It aims to assess and promote gender-sensitive practices within agriculture by evaluating the equitable distribution of resources, benefits, and decision-making power among different genders.

The framework is designed to be adaptable to various agricultural contexts, including those found in East Africa. Its flexibility allows users to select relevant indicators and measurement methods based on the specific characteristics and challenges of their region.

Scope

Firstly, the framework covers five main domains: Productivity, Economic, Environmental, Human Condition, and Social. These domains collectively provide a comprehensive assessment of sustainability, addressing key aspects related to agriculture and its impacts. Within each domain, the framework incorporates a wide range of indicators and metrics. These indicators are designed to capture various facets of sustainability, allowing users to tailor their assessments to specific objectives and contexts.

The framework also offers guidance on data collection methods, including techniques for measuring each indicator to ensure that users have the necessary tools and approaches to gather relevant data effectively. Gender equity and social dimensions are integrated throughout the framework, recognizing the importance of inclusive and equitable agricultural systems. The framework includes metrics and indicators related to gender access, control, and achievements.

The framework places significant emphasis on environmental sustainability, including factors such as soil health, greenhouse gas emissions, and water quality which reflect the growing importance of sustainable resource management in agriculture. Recognizing the diversity of agricultural systems, the framework is adaptable and can be customized to suit the specific needs of users in East Africa and beyond. It accommodates variations in data availability, expertise, and local conditions.

5.1.3 Structure and Components

The Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework is a comprehensive tool structured to facilitate the evaluation of agroecological practices through a multidimensional lens. It is organized into several key components, each contributing to a holistic understanding of the sustainability of agricultural innovations.

a. Sustainability Domains

At the core of the framework are five distinct sustainability domains, namely Productivity, Economic, Environmental, Human Condition, and Social. These domains serve as the foundational pillars for assessing the diverse aspects of agroecological practices. The framework ensures a comprehensive evaluation of sustainability that goes beyond mere yield measurements by categorizing indicators and metrics within these domains.

b. Indicators and Metrics

Within each sustainability domain, the framework incorporates a multitude of specific indicators and metrics. These indicators are carefully selected to capture essential aspects of sustainability relevant to agriculture. For instance, in the Productivity domain, indicators such as Crop Productivity, Yield Gap, and Cropping Intensity are utilized to assess agricultural productivity. Similarly, the Economic domain encompasses indicators like Profitability and Income Diversification. These indicators collectively offer a robust toolkit for sustainability assessment, allowing users to tailor their evaluations to specific contexts and objectives.

c. Data Collection Methods

An integral part of the framework is the guidance it provides on data collection methods. Recognizing the importance of accurate and reliable data, the framework outlines techniques and approaches for measuring each indicator. This ensures that users have the necessary tools to collect and analyze data effectively, helping them make informed decisions about agroecological practices.

d. Gender Equity Integration

One distinctive feature of the framework is its strong focus on gender equity. Gender-sensitive indicators and metrics are embedded throughout the structure, reflecting the importance of equitable resource distribution, control, and achievements in agriculture. This integration of gender dimensions ensures that sustainability assessments consider the diverse roles and contributions of different genders in agricultural systems.

e. Environmental Emphasis

The framework places significant emphasis on environmental sustainability, recognizing the critical role of agriculture in resource management and climate change. Environmental indicators cover aspects such as soil health, greenhouse gas emissions, water quality, and biodiversity. This reflects the growing importance of sustainable resource use and conservation in agricultural practices.

f. Gender Equity Index

An essential component of the framework is the Women Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI). This index assesses gender empowerment within agricultural communities, focusing on production, resources, income, leadership, and time. While demanding in terms of data collection, the WEAI provides valuable insights into gender-related aspects of sustainability at the community or regional scale.

g. Social Dimensions

Beyond gender equity, the framework also considers broader social dimensions, including social cohesion and collective action. These elements help assess the societal impacts of agroecological practices and their implications for community well-being and resilience.

5.1.4 Applicability in East Africa

The Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework exhibits a high degree of relevance and applicability to the agricultural landscapes of East Africa. This region is characterized by diverse agroecological zones, from highland areas to arid lowlands. The framework's flexibility and adaptability are well-suited to capture this diversity. Users can select indicators and metrics that align with the specific conditions of their respective agro-ecological zones, enabling a nuanced assessment of sustainability.

The majority of agricultural activities in East Africa are carried out by smallholder farmers who cultivate relatively small plots of land. The framework's emphasis on resource efficiency, productivity, and income diversification resonates with the challenges and opportunities faced by these farmers. It provides a means to evaluate how agroecological practices impact the livelihoods of smallholders. Gender disparities in access to resources and decision-making power are prevalent in East African agriculture. The framework's integration of gender-sensitive indicators and the Women Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) align with the region's need to address gender equity issues in farming communities. This is particularly relevant as women play a significant role in agricultural production in East Africa.

East Africa faces environmental challenges such as soil degradation, deforestation, and water scarcity. The framework's strong focus on environmental indicators, including soil health, water quality, and biodiversity, provides a valuable tool for assessing the environmental impacts of agroecological practices and identifying strategies for sustainable resource management. The framework also offers guidance on data collection methods, which can be adapted to suit the capacity and resources available in East African contexts. While some aspects may require more extensive data collection efforts, the framework's modular structure allows for a gradual and context-specific approach to data collection.

East African governments and development agencies are increasingly promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The framework aligns with these initiatives by offering a structured approach to assess the impacts of policy interventions and innovations in agriculture. It provides a means to monitor progress toward sustainability goals.

The framework's consideration of social dimensions, including social cohesion and collective action, is particularly relevant in East Africa's communal farming settings. It allows for the evaluation of how agroecological practices impact community dynamics and resilience. Further, East Africa places a strong emphasis on community-based and participatory approaches to agricultural development. The framework's customizability and adaptability empower local stakeholders to take ownership of the assessment process, ensuring that it aligns with their priorities and aspirations.

5.1.5 Strengths and limitations

Strengths

One of the framework's primary strengths is its holistic approach to sustainability assessment. By encompassing economic, environmental, human condition, and social domains, it offers a comprehensive view of the impacts of

agroecological practices, ensuring that no critical aspect is overlooked. The framework's modular structure also allows users to tailor assessments to specific contexts and priorities. This flexibility makes it applicable to a wide range of agroecological zones, farming systems, and development objectives.

The incorporation of gender-sensitive indicators and the Women Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) is a significant strength. It acknowledges the importance of gender equity in sustainable agriculture and provides a means to assess and address gender disparities. Further, the framework's adaptability empowers local stakeholders, including farmers and communities, to actively engage in the assessment process. This local ownership enhances the relevance and credibility of sustainability evaluations.

The framework aligns with the goals of governments and development agencies promoting sustainable agriculture. It provides a structured approach to assess the impacts of policy interventions and inform decision-making.

Given the growing environmental challenges in agriculture, the framework's inclusion of a wide range of environmental indicators, from soil health to greenhouse gas emissions, equips users with the tools to evaluate the ecological sustainability of practices.

Limitations

Some of the indicators and metrics require extensive data collection efforts, which may pose challenges in resource-constrained settings. In East Africa, where capacity and resources for data collection can be limited, this could be a barrier to widespread adoption.

The framework's comprehensiveness may also be seen as a limitation, particularly for users seeking a quick and simple assessment tool. Its complexity may require specialized training and technical expertise.

In some cases, the interpretation of certain indicators, especially those related to human conditions and social dimensions, may be subjective. This subjectivity can introduce variability in assessments and may require careful consideration during data collection and analysis.

Conducting a thorough assessment using the framework can be time-intensive. This may limit its feasibility for organizations or projects with tight timelines.

The framework assumes the availability of certain resources, such as technology and financial resources, for implementing agroecological practices. In resource-constrained settings, these assumptions may not hold, affecting the accuracy of assessments.

While the framework emphasizes scientific data, it may not fully capture the contributions of indigenous knowledge systems, which are often integral to sustainable practices in some East African communities.

The framework primarily operates at the household or community scale. This may limit its ability to capture broader landscape-level dynamics, which are increasingly recognized as critical in sustainable agriculture.

5.2 The Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) [102]

5.2.1 Overview of the Framework

The Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) is a comprehensive and multidimensional framework designed to assess and evaluate the economic and environmental sustainability of agroecological practices. It offers a systematic approach to measuring the performance of agroecological systems, taking into account the intricate relationships among various elements within these systems. TAPE has been developed with the goal of promoting sustainable agricultural practices globally and is currently undergoing pilot testing in diverse regions.

At its core, TAPE aims to provide a structured methodology for assessing the sustainability of agroecological systems. It emphasizes the interconnectedness of different aspects within these systems, recognizing that evaluating sustainability requires a holistic perspective. The framework seeks to facilitate a deeper understanding of agroecological practices by considering ten core criteria and ten elements of agroecology, making it a powerful tool for comprehensive evaluation.

TAPE's design encourages stakeholder engagement and participation. It promotes the integration of local knowledge and insights into the assessment process, recognizing the importance of involving the community and harnessing their expertise. This participatory approach ensures that the evaluation process is contextualized and relevant to the specific agroecological contexts in which it is applied.

5.2.2 Objectives and scope

Objectives

TAPE aims to provide a comprehensive and multidimensional assessment of agroecological systems. It seeks to go beyond narrow, single-dimensional evaluations and instead offers a holistic understanding of sustainability.

One of TAPE's primary objectives is to engage and involve the local community in the assessment process. It recognizes the importance of integrating traditional and local knowledge, ensuring that the assessment is contextually relevant.

The framework acknowledges the interconnectedness of various elements within agroecological systems. It aims to assess how different elements interact and influence each other, leading to a deeper understanding of these complex systems.

TAPE is designed to promote and encourage the adoption of sustainable agroecological practices. It provides insights and recommendations for improving sustainability, making it a practical tool for farmers and policymakers.

Scope

- a. **Ten Core Criteria:** TAPE focuses on ten core criteria that are essential for evaluating the economic and environmental sustainability of agroecological practices. These criteria cover aspects such as land tenure, productivity, income, exposure to pesticides, dietary diversity, women's empowerment, youth employment, agricultural biodiversity, soil health, and more.

- b. Ten Elements of Agroecology: The framework considers ten elements of agroecology, emphasizing their significance in the sustainability assessment. These elements encompass biodiversity, recycling, soil management, energy, water, a circular and solidarity economy, knowledge and innovation, governance, health and well-being, and culture and food traditions.
- c. Contextual Relevance: TAPE recognizes the importance of adapting to local contexts. It is designed to be flexible and applicable in various agroecological settings, making it relevant for regions like East Africa with diverse farming systems.
- d. Participatory Approach: The framework promotes a participatory approach to assessment, involving local stakeholders and integrating their insights. This approach ensures that the assessment is contextually meaningful and that the community is an active participant in the process.
- e. Global Applicability: While initially developed as a pilot framework, TAPE has the potential for global applicability. It can be used in different regions and agroecological contexts to assess and enhance the sustainability of farming practices.

5.2.3 Structure and components

The Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) is structured in a systematic and comprehensive manner, incorporating various components that facilitate its use in assessing the economic and environmental sustainability of agroecological practices. This section outlines the key structural elements and components of the TAPE framework:

Contextual Information

TAPE begins with the collection of contextual information, which includes data on the local environment, socio-economic conditions, and enabling factors. This information provides the necessary background to understand the specific context in which agroecological practices are implemented.

Ten Core Criteria

TAPE focuses on ten core criteria that serve as the foundation for sustainability assessment. These criteria encompass critical aspects of agroecological practices and their impact on economic and environmental sustainability. The criteria include:

- Secure land tenure
- Productivity
- Income
- Exposure to pesticides
- Dietary diversity
- Women's empowerment
- Youth employment
- Agricultural biodiversity
- Soil health

- Optional advanced criteria

Ten Elements of Agroecology

TAPE recognizes the importance of ten elements within agroecological systems. These elements provide a framework for understanding the diverse components that contribute to sustainability. The elements include:

- Biodiversity
- Recycling
- Soil management
- Energy
- Water
- Circular and solidarity economy
- Knowledge and innovation
- Governance
- Health and well-being
- Culture and food traditions

Data Collection Methods

The framework incorporates a range of data collection methods drawn from various disciplines, including anthropology, ethnobiology, genetics, botany, biogeography, and ecology. These methods include household surveys, focus group discussions, and participatory approaches to gather information on agroecological practices and their impact.

Aggregation and Analysis

TAPE aggregates data collected from multiple sources and applies analytical methods to assess the sustainability of agroecological systems. It calculates indices and indicators to provide a comprehensive evaluation of performance.

Participatory Interpretation

TAPE places a strong emphasis on participatory interpretation. It encourages engagement with local communities and stakeholders to verify results, discuss findings, and identify synergies and trade-offs within agroecological systems.

Advanced Methodologies

The framework offers advanced methodologies for in-depth analysis, such as the Index of Agrobiodiversity (IDA) and Soil Organic Matter assessment. These methods provide additional insights into biodiversity and carbon sequestration.

5.2.4 Applicability in East Africa

The Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) holds great promise for assessing the economic and environmental sustainability of agroecological practices in East Africa. Its adaptability and flexibility make it particularly well-suited for the diverse farming systems in the region. This adaptability allows for effective application in various agroecological contexts, accommodating the different socio-economic and environmental conditions prevalent in East Africa. East Africa faces a host of sustainability challenges, including issues related to land tenure, productivity, biodiversity, and soil health [109]. TAPE addresses these critical aspects through its comprehensive set of ten core criteria and ten elements of agroecology, aligning well with the multifaceted sustainability challenges in East African agriculture. The framework's broad scope ensures that these challenges are systematically evaluated, providing valuable insights.

TAPE employs adaptable data collection methods such as household surveys, focus group discussions, and participatory approaches, which are well-suited for East African communities. Moreover, it emphasizes participatory interpretation, aligning with the region's community-based approaches to agriculture, which ensures that local knowledge and practices are integrated into the assessment process.

East Africa's diverse agroecological zones, including highlands, lowlands, and arid regions, are reflected in TAPE's recognition of the ten elements of agroecology, such as soil management, water, and biodiversity. This acknowledgment underscores the importance of these factors in East African agriculture. Furthermore, TAPE's applicability in the region contributes to its broader utility, enabling comparisons and assessments across regions, and aligning with East African countries' focus on sustainability goals related to food security, climate resilience, and environmental conservation. TAPE's core criteria, including soil health and agricultural biodiversity, align with these goals, making it a valuable tool for monitoring progress within East Africa and beyond. For more in-depth assessments, TAPE offers advanced methodologies such as the Index of Agrobiodiversity (IDA) and Soil Organic Matter assessment, providing valuable insights into specific sustainability challenges faced in East Africa.

5.2.5 Strengths and limitations

Strengths

One of TAPE's primary strengths lies in its comprehensive nature. It considers a wide range of factors, including land tenure, productivity, income, soil health, and biodiversity. This breadth ensures that the framework can address the multifaceted challenges faced by East African agriculture, providing a holistic view of sustainability.

TAPE's flexibility is another key asset. It can be customized to suit diverse agroecological contexts, accommodating variations in farming systems, socio-economic conditions, and environmental challenges. This adaptability allows for meaningful assessments across different regions.

The participatory nature of TAPE is a significant advantage, particularly in the East African context. Agriculture in the region often involves close collaboration between farmers, communities, and local stakeholders. By engaging these key actors in the assessment process, TAPE ensures that local knowledge and practices are considered, enhancing the framework's relevance and acceptance.

TAPE offers advanced methodologies, such as the Index of Agrobiodiversity (IDA) and Soil Organic Matter assessment, which can provide in-depth insights into specific sustainability issues. These tools allow for a more nuanced understanding of the economic and environmental dynamics in East African agro-ecosystems.

The TAPE framework aligns with sustainability goals, both at the global and regional levels. It addresses critical issues such as food security, climate resilience, and environmental conservation, which are priorities for East African countries. This alignment facilitates the monitoring of progress toward achieving these goals.

Limitations

TAPE requires substantial data collection efforts, including household surveys and participatory methods. In resource-constrained settings common in East Africa, the data collection process can be resource-intensive and time-consuming, posing a potential challenge.

The comprehensive nature of TAPE can be seen as both a strength and a limitation. While it offers a holistic view of sustainability, its complexity may require substantial training and capacity building for those conducting the assessments. Ensuring that assessors are adequately prepared is essential for reliable results.

The participatory interpretation process, while valuable, can introduce subjectivity and interpretation challenges. Different stakeholders may have varying perspectives on sustainability, leading to potential disagreements during the analysis phase.

Implementing advanced methodologies like the IDA or Soil Organic Matter assessment may require additional resources and technical expertise, which may not be readily available in all East African settings. Further, TAPE's effectiveness relies on its ability to monitor changes in sustainability over time. Establishing a robust long-term monitoring system may be challenging in some regions of East Africa.

5.3 The five-dimensional SF Presidia framework [103]

5.3.1 Overview

The Five-Dimensional Slow Food (SF) Presidia Framework offers a comprehensive approach to evaluating the sustainability of agri-food systems, particularly those under the purview of Slow Food Presidia projects. These projects are designed to champion and preserve traditional and sustainable food production practices. This framework delves into five key dimensions: Product Quality, Cultural Sustainability, Social Sustainability, Environmental Sustainability, and Economic Sustainability. Each dimension is underpinned by a set of specific indicators, collectively providing a well-rounded perspective on sustainability.

Product Quality, as the first dimension, zooms in on the intrinsic quality of food products. This entails assessing whether the products adhere to specific production rules, boast distinctive tastes, are nutritionally rich, and meet stringent food safety standards. Furthermore, it examines the proximity of production to local areas and seasons, eschewing practices like the use of heated greenhouses.

The second dimension, Cultural Sustainability, prioritizes the preservation and celebration of cultural identities interwoven with food production. Indicators within this dimension gauge the depth of cultural identity alignment,

the efficacy of knowledge transfer among producers and communities, the utilization of traditional processing and conservation methods, and the authenticity of gastronomic usage within local contexts.

Social Sustainability, as the third dimension, casts a spotlight on the social facets of food production and community dynamics. Here, indicators encompass aspects like external and internal relationships, the roles of producers within society, social inclusivity, community influence, producer gatherings, and educational outreach efforts. These indicators delve into the extent of interaction, organizational formalization, inclusivity, and education within the producer community.

Environmental Sustainability, the fourth dimension, revolves around the environmental impact of production practices and the preservation of biodiversity. This dimension scrutinizes indicators such as ecosystem diversity, species diversity, genetic diversity, water quantity and quality, air quality, soil health, energy sources, and packaging practices. It probes into the presence of ecological infrastructure, genetic diversity, responsible resource usage, and packaging sustainability.

Economic Sustainability, the fifth dimension, hones in on the economic underpinnings of food production. Indicators in this dimension encompass the diversification of the supply chain, fluctuations in product prices, the bundling of products, and changes in production areas. It evaluates the economic progress of producers, their potential market influence through alliances, and the overall economic resilience of the system.

5.3.2 Objectives and Scope

Objectives

The Five-Dimensional Slow Food (SF) Presidia Framework is designed with specific objectives aimed at comprehensively evaluating and promoting the sustainability of agri-food systems, particularly those supported by Slow Food Presidia initiatives.

The foremost objective of the SF Presidia Framework is to provide a holistic and multidimensional assessment of the sustainability of food production practices. It goes beyond traditional economic assessments to consider the broader dimensions of sustainability, including cultural, social, environmental, and economic aspects.

This framework seeks to capture the intricate interplay between food production, cultural heritage, societal dynamics, environmental impact, and economic viability. It aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the complexities of agri-food systems by examining these five key dimensions.

One of the central objectives is to assess the intrinsic quality of food products within the context of sustainability. This includes evaluating whether products adhere to specific production rules, possess distinctive taste characteristics, meet nutritional standards, and ensure food safety. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of local and seasonal production.

Cultural sustainability is a key focus, aiming to preserve and celebrate the cultural identities woven into food production. It seeks to assess the degree to which food production practices align with cultural identities, promote knowledge transfer within producer communities, utilize traditional processing and conservation methods, and uphold authentic gastronomic traditions.

The framework also aims to examine the social dimensions of food production by evaluating interactions within producer communities. It assesses the formalization of producer groups, inclusivity in decision-making processes,

educational initiatives, and external relationships. Additionally, it scrutinizes the roles of producers within society and their ability to foster community inclusion.

Environmental sustainability is a critical objective, focusing on the ecological footprint of food production. It evaluates factors such as ecosystem diversity, species diversity, genetic diversity, water and air quality and quantity, soil health, energy sources, and packaging practices. It emphasizes responsible resource usage and biodiversity conservation.

Economic sustainability is another central objective, aiming to assess the economic viability of food production systems. It evaluates supply chain diversification, market price fluctuations, product bundling practices, and changes in production areas. The objective is to gauge the resilience and progress of producers within the economic landscape.

Beyond assessment, the framework is intended to serve as a tool for promoting sustainable agricultural and food production practices. By highlighting areas for improvement and providing a comprehensive view of sustainability, it encourages the adoption of practices that benefit society, culture, the environment, and the economy. Ultimately, the SF Presidia Framework aims to facilitate informed decision-making in the realm of food production. It provides a structured approach to assess and prioritize sustainability indicators, aiding stakeholders in making choices that align with broader sustainability goals.

Scope

The scope of the Five-Dimensional Slow Food (SF) Presidia Framework is both broad and adaptable, making it a versatile tool for assessing and promoting the sustainability of agri-food systems. At its core, the framework aims to comprehensively evaluate the sustainability of these systems by considering five key dimensions: quality, cultural sustainability, social sustainability, environmental sustainability, and economic sustainability. This holistic approach ensures that sustainability is assessed from multiple angles, providing a nuanced understanding of the agri-food systems under scrutiny.

One essential aspect of the framework's scope is its applicability to diverse agri-food systems, transcending specific stages of the food supply chain. It is not limited to a particular segment but rather encompasses the entire spectrum of activities involved in food production, from cultivation and harvesting to processing, distribution, and consumption. This adaptability allows the framework to be tailored to various contexts, including East Africa, where agri-food systems may exhibit unique characteristics and challenges.

Furthermore, the scope of the SF Presidia Framework is particularly well-suited for assessing Slow Food Presidia initiatives. These initiatives focus on preserving traditional and culturally significant food products, aligning closely with the framework's emphasis on cultural identity preservation. By evaluating adherence to cultural traditions, knowledge transmission, and gastronomic authenticity, the framework aids in safeguarding these unique food systems. Overall, the scope of the framework extends to the promotion of sustainable practices, informed decision-making, and the resilience of agri-food systems, making it a valuable resource for advancing sustainability goals in diverse contexts.

5.3.3 Structure and Components

Its components are designed to capture various facets of sustainability, ensuring a holistic evaluation. At the core of the framework are the five distinct dimensions: quality, cultural sustainability, social sustainability, environmental sustainability, and economic sustainability. These dimensions serve as the foundational pillars for assessing the sustainability of agri-food systems.

Within each dimension, the framework further delineates specific indicators that facilitate a detailed evaluation. These indicators are carefully chosen to reflect the key aspects relevant to each dimension. For instance, within the dimension of "quality," indicators encompass rules of production, taste, nutritional content, food safety, and local and seasonal attributes. This granular approach allows for understanding of the quality dimension's various facets.

To operationalize the framework, each indicator is associated with levels of assessment, ranging from Level 1 to Level 3. These levels enable a structured evaluation process, with Level 3 representing the most detailed and comprehensive assessment. Additionally, each indicator is assigned a unit of measurement, scores, and values, ensuring a standardized approach to evaluation. For example, the "Taste" indicator may be assessed on a scale of 0 to 10, with a value of 0 indicating "No" and 10 indicating "Yes."

The framework's structure fosters flexibility and adaptability, allowing users to tailor assessments to specific agri-food systems and contexts. It provides a systematic and organized approach to sustainability evaluation, ensuring that all relevant dimensions and indicators are considered. This structured framework is a valuable tool for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners seeking to assess and enhance the sustainability of agroecological practices.

5.3.4 Applicability in East Africa

The applicability of the Five-Dimensional Slow Food (SF) Presidia Framework in East Africa holds significant promise for assessing and enhancing the sustainability of agroecological practices in the region. While the framework was initially developed within the context of Slow Food Presidia, its adaptability and relevance extend to East Africa's unique agri-food systems and environmental conditions.

One of the key strengths of the SF Presidia Framework is its flexibility, which allows it to be tailored to diverse agricultural contexts. East Africa is characterized by a wide range of agroecological zones, cropping systems, and cultural practices. The framework's multidimensional approach ensures that it can accommodate this diversity by considering quality, cultural sustainability, social sustainability, environmental sustainability, and economic sustainability. This adaptability enables researchers, policymakers, and practitioners in East Africa to apply the framework to various agricultural settings, from smallholder farms to community-based initiatives.

Furthermore, the framework's emphasis on cultural sustainability aligns with the rich cultural heritage and traditions prevalent in East Africa. The region is known for its diverse cultural practices related to food production, consumption, and preservation. By incorporating cultural dimensions into the assessment, the SF Presidia Framework acknowledges the significance of preserving and promoting traditional knowledge and practices in East African agriculture.

In terms of economic sustainability, East Africa faces challenges related to market access, income generation, and value chain development. The framework's inclusion of economic indicators offers a valuable tool for evaluating and improving the economic aspects of agroecological practices. It allows stakeholders to assess factors such as price,

supply chain diversification, and forms of bundling, which are critical for enhancing economic sustainability in the region.

5.3.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

One of the primary strengths of this framework is its comprehensive approach. It covers five key dimensions of sustainability: quality, cultural sustainability, social sustainability, environmental sustainability, and economic sustainability. This breadth allows for a holistic evaluation of agroecological practices, ensuring that no critical aspects are overlooked.

The framework's flexibility makes it adaptable to various agricultural contexts and systems, which is particularly valuable in the diverse agroecological landscape of East Africa. It can be customized to suit the specific needs and priorities of different regions and communities.

The inclusion of cultural sustainability as a core dimension aligns with the rich cultural heritage of East Africa. It recognizes the importance of preserving traditional knowledge and practices related to food production and consumption, promoting cultural identity, and enhancing community engagement. Further, the framework's participatory approach involves stakeholders, including farmers and local communities, in the assessment process. This engagement fosters ownership and ensures that the assessment reflects the perspectives and priorities of those directly impacted by agroecological practices.

Limitations

The SF Presidia Framework relies on data collection and assessment, which can be resource-intensive and time-consuming. In East Africa, where data availability and quality may vary, collecting sufficient and accurate information for all indicators could be a challenge.

The framework's multidimensional nature may be perceived as complex, requiring expertise in sustainability assessment. This complexity can pose challenges for its practical implementation, especially in resource-constrained settings.

Involving stakeholders in the assessment process is valuable, but it may introduce subjectivity into the evaluation. Different stakeholders may assign varying weights to indicators, potentially leading to divergent assessments.

While the framework has demonstrated its effectiveness in the context of Slow Food Presidia, its applicability and validity in East Africa need validation through empirical studies and case-specific adaptations. Ensuring that the indicators are culturally and contextually relevant is crucial.

5.4 Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development (IDEA) [104]

5.4.1 Overview

The Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development (IDEA) framework is a comprehensive method designed to assess the sustainability of farms. Developed through multi-disciplinary research conducted in France since 1998, IDEA provides a practical means of operationalizing the concept of sustainable agriculture. This framework is based on 41 sustainability indicators that cover three fundamental dimensions of sustainability: economic, environmental, and socio-territorial. The IDEA framework serves as a self-assessment tool not only for farmers but also for policymakers, facilitating the promotion and support of sustainable agriculture practices.

The scientific foundation of the IDEA framework rests on identifying and measuring three distinct scales of sustainability. These scales encompass agroecological sustainability, socio-territorial sustainability, and economic sustainability. Each scale consists of a set of components and indicators that collectively represent key aspects of sustainability. For instance, agroecological sustainability assesses a farm's capacity to efficiently utilize its environment while minimizing ecological impacts, with indicators addressing diversity of production, organization of space, and farming practices. Socio-territorial sustainability evaluates how a farm integrates into its landscape and society, examining aspects like the quality of life for farmers and the services provided to the community. Economic sustainability, on the other hand, considers the viability, independence, transferability, and production process efficiency of farming systems.

The IDEA framework is particularly versatile, allowing for the evaluation of various farming systems and practices. Tests have demonstrated its practicality and effectiveness, with farmers and advisory officers being able to implement the method easily. The framework offers the flexibility to adapt indicators to local contexts, ensuring relevance across different agricultural settings. Additionally, it supports comparisons between farms of similar types and local conditions, highlighting variations in sustainability scores and aiding discussions among farmers to work towards greater sustainability.

The IDEA framework's structure emphasizes the importance of assessing sustainability across multiple dimensions and recognizing that there is no single model of farm sustainability. Instead, it promotes the idea that sustainability indicators should be tailored to local farming conditions to provide meaningful insights. The framework's utility extends to policymaking as it aligns with the evolving agricultural landscape, where sustainable practices are essential not only for farm viability but also for environmental protection and socio-territorial integration.

5.4.2 Objectives and Scope

Objectives

The IDEA framework aims to translate the abstract concept of sustainability into concrete, measurable terms. It seeks to provide a practical means for assessing the sustainability of farming practices by quantifying key aspects related to economic viability, environmental impact, and socio-territorial integration.

IDEA is designed to evaluate farm sustainability across three fundamental dimensions: agroecological, socio-territorial, and economic. By addressing these dimensions, it enables a comprehensive understanding of sustainability that goes beyond mere economic considerations.

IDEA serves as a self-assessment tool that can be used by farmers themselves. It empowers farmers to assess the sustainability of their own practices, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions about their farming operations.

While valuable for individual farm-level assessment, IDEA also serves as a tool for policymakers and agricultural authorities. It aids in shaping policies that promote sustainable agriculture by providing data-driven insights into the sustainability of different farming systems.

Scope

The scope of the IDEA framework is defined by the following parameters:

- i. **Three Dimensions of Sustainability:** IDEA comprehensively covers three primary dimensions of sustainability: agroecological, socio-territorial, and economic. Each of these dimensions is further subdivided into specific components and indicators that collectively assess sustainability.
- ii. **Diverse Farming Systems:** The IDEA framework is adaptable and can be applied to various farming systems and practices. It does not limit itself to a specific type of agriculture but rather offers flexibility to evaluate sustainability in different contexts.
- iii. **Localization:** IDEA recognizes the importance of local context in assessing sustainability. It encourages the adaptation of indicators to suit the specific conditions and practices of a given region, acknowledging that sustainability solutions are not one-size-fits-all.
- iv. **Comparative Analysis:** The framework allows for comparisons between farms with similar types of production and local conditions. It helps identify variations in sustainability scores, fostering discussions among farmers and advisory officers to work collectively towards greater sustainability.
- v. **Policy Implications:** IDEA extends its scope to inform policy decisions related to agriculture. It aids policymakers in designing and implementing strategies that support sustainable farming practices, aligning with broader environmental and socio-economic goals.

5.4.3 Structure and Components

Structure

IDEA is structured around three primary sustainability scales, each focusing on a distinct dimension of sustainability. These scales collectively provide a holistic view of farm sustainability.

- a. **Agroecological Sustainability Scale:** This scale assesses the ecological impact of farming practices, including aspects related to biodiversity, resource use, and environmental impact.
- b. **Socio-Territorial Sustainability Scale:** This scale evaluates the integration of the farm within its broader social and territorial context. It considers factors such as the quality of life for farmers, social contributions, and the farm's impact on the landscape.
- c. **Economic Sustainability Scale:** Economic viability is crucial for long-term farm sustainability. This scale assesses economic factors, including income, financial autonomy, and the efficiency of the production process.

Each sustainability scale is further broken down into specific components. These components capture various aspects relevant to the respective dimension of sustainability.

- i. *Agroecological Sustainability Scale Components*: Diversity of production, organization of space, and farming practices are key components. These assess aspects like crop diversity, ecological practices, and resource protection.
- ii. *Socio-Territorial Sustainability Scale Components*: Quality of products and land, organization of space, ethics, and human development are components. They consider factors such as product quality, architectural heritage, and contributions to society.
- iii. *Economic Sustainability Scale Components*: Economic viability, independence, transferability, and production process efficiency are the components. These assess economic factors like income, financial autonomy, and succession planning.

Components

- o *Diversity of Production*: This component evaluates the diversity of crops, including annual or temporary crops, perennial crops, associated vegetation, and animal diversity. It assesses how farming practices contribute to a diversified production system.
- o *Organization of Space*: This component focuses on aspects related to the spatial arrangement of farming operations. It includes considerations such as cropping patterns, field dimensions, organic matter management, ecological buffer zones, and measures to protect the natural heritage.
- o *Farming Practices*: Farming practices play a significant role in sustainability. This component assesses various practices, including fertilization, effluent processing, pesticide and veterinary product use, animal well-being, soil and water resource protection, and energy dependence.
- o *Quality of Products and Land*: Within the socio-territorial sustainability scale, this component evaluates the quality of food products, enhancement of buildings and landscape heritage, processing of non-organic waste, accessibility of space, and social involvement.
- o *Organization of Space (Socio-Territorial)*: This component considers aspects related to short trade, services, multi-activities, contribution to employment, collective work, and probable farm sustainability.
- o *Ethics and Human Development*: Ethics and human development indicators include contribution to the world food balance, training, labor intensity, quality of life, isolation, reception, hygiene, and safety.
- o *Economic Viability*: This component assesses economic sustainability, focusing on available income per worker compared with the national legal minimum wage, economic specialization rate, financial autonomy, and reliance on direct subsidies.

5.4.4 Applicability in East Africa

East Africa comprises a wide range of agroecological zones, from arid and semi-arid regions to highland areas with varying climates. The IDEA framework's flexibility allows for adaptation to different environmental conditions. It would need customization to account for the specific crops, livestock, and farming practices prevalent in East Africa.

East Africa also has diverse farming systems, including subsistence farming, cash crop agriculture, pastoralism, and agroforestry. The IDEA framework can be adapted to suit each of these systems, considering the specific indicators and components relevant to the local context.

Sustainable resource management is critical in East Africa, where issues like soil erosion, water scarcity, and land degradation are common challenges. The framework's agroecological sustainability scale can be particularly valuable in assessing practices related to soil and water conservation, crop diversity, and resource protection. East Africa's farming communities often play significant roles in shaping local landscapes and societies. The socio-territorial sustainability scale of IDEA can help evaluate the impact of farming activities on the broader community, including factors like quality of life, social involvement, and contributions to the local economy. Economic viability is also essential for farm sustainability in East Africa. The framework's economic sustainability scale can assess income levels, financial autonomy, and the efficiency of production processes, which are critical for the region's farmers.

To apply the IDEA framework effectively in East Africa, it's crucial to customize the indicators and components to reflect the specific goals and priorities of the region. This may involve engaging local experts, farmers, and stakeholders to tailor the framework to the East African context. In addition, the availability of data and information needed to calculate the IDEA indicators is a practical consideration. In some areas of East Africa, data collection and monitoring systems may need improvement to support the framework's application.

The IDEA framework can serve as a valuable tool for policymakers, NGOs, and agricultural extension services in East Africa. It can aid in making informed decisions related to agricultural development, land management, and sustainable practices.

5.4.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

First and foremost, its multidimensional approach stands out as a key strength. By encompassing ecological, socio-territorial, and economic aspects of sustainability, IDEA provides a holistic view of farming systems. This multidimensionality aligns well with the complexity of agricultural practices in East Africa, where environmental, social, and economic factors are closely intertwined.

Another strength of the IDEA framework is its flexibility and adaptability. It can be customized to suit the diverse agroecological zones and farming systems prevalent in East Africa. This adaptability ensures that the framework remains relevant across different regions, where varying crops, livestock, and farming practices require tailored assessment criteria. It allows stakeholders to address local challenges effectively.

Furthermore, IDEA's emphasis on self-assessment is a notable strength. Farmers, policymakers, and local communities can actively engage with the framework to evaluate sustainability. This participatory approach fosters ownership and empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions about their farming practices. It also promotes dialogue and knowledge sharing among different actors in the agricultural sector.

Limitations

One limitation is the need for comprehensive data and information to calculate the sustainability indicators accurately. In many parts of East Africa, data collection and monitoring systems may be underdeveloped or

fragmented. This limitation can hinder the effective application of IDEA, particularly in regions with limited access to data.

Another limitation lies in the potential subjectivity of certain indicators. IDEA includes qualitative assessments, such as quality of life and social involvement, which can be challenging to measure objectively. This subjectivity may introduce variability in the results and necessitate careful consideration when interpreting findings.

Additionally, the framework's reliance on scoring and weighting of indicators may raise questions about the fairness of these assessments. Determining the appropriate weights and scoring scales requires consensus among experts and stakeholders. Variations in these decisions may lead to different sustainability assessments, which could be perceived as biased or inconsistent.

5.5 MESMIS Framework [105]

5.5.1 Overview

The MESMIS framework is a comprehensive and adaptable tool designed for assessing and improving the sustainability of complex systems, particularly agroecological practices and natural resource management systems (NRMS). It offers a structured approach to evaluate these systems, with a specific focus on their economic and environmental aspects.

The framework consists of six distinct steps, each contributing to a comprehensive evaluation process. The initial step involves defining the scope and objectives of the evaluation. This entails clearly delineating the system's boundaries, specifying objectives, identifying stakeholders, and determining the evaluation's scale.

Following the scope definition, the second step revolves around selecting the system attributes that will be assessed. These attributes represent the fundamental characteristics of the system and can include aspects like productivity, stability, resilience, adaptability, equity, and self-reliance. The choice of attributes depends on the specific goals and context of the evaluation.

The third step of the MESMIS framework involves the selection and clustering of indicators that align with the chosen system attributes. Indicators are concrete metrics or measurements used to assess the system's performance in relation to its attributes. These indicators cover a wide range of areas, including productivity, biodiversity, soil properties, and more.

Once the indicators are identified, the fourth step focuses on the practical aspect of measurement and monitoring. Various methods are employed for data collection, such as direct field measurements, surveys, literature reviews, simulation models, and interviews. The selection of measurement methods depends on the type of data required, whether it's socio-economic or environmental.

In the fifth step, results are integrated to provide a holistic view of the system's performance. This integration is facilitated through tools like the AMOEBA diagram, which visually represents the system's performance across different sustainability dimensions. It enables comparisons between the analyzed system and optimal values for each indicator.

The final step of the MESMIS framework involves drawing conclusions and formulating recommendations. Conclusions are based on the analysis of system performance, while recommendations are aimed at enhancing the

system's sustainability. These recommendations can range from modifications in management strategies to the design of alternative systems or initiating further research.

In essence, the MESMIS framework offers a structured and flexible approach for assessing and enhancing the sustainability of agroecological practices and NRMS. It underscores the importance of considering economic, environmental, and social dimensions and encourages stakeholder involvement to facilitate effective decision-making in pursuit of sustainability. The framework's systematic approach and its ability to capture the complexity of these systems make it a valuable tool for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners seeking to promote sustainable practices in East Africa and beyond.

5.5.2 Objectives and Scope

The MESMIS framework's objectives and scope are fundamentally centered around the evaluation and enhancement of sustainability in complex systems, with a particular emphasis on agroecological practices and natural resource management systems (NRMS). It serves as a versatile and adaptable tool designed to facilitate comprehensive assessments of these systems, aiming to foster a deeper understanding of their economic and environmental dimensions.

One of the primary objectives of MESMIS is to provide a structured and systematic approach for evaluating the sustainability of agroecological practices. It seeks to enable stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and practitioners, to assess the performance of these practices in a holistic manner, to identify areas where sustainability can be improved and provide actionable recommendations for achieving more sustainable outcomes.

The scope of MESMIS is intentionally broad, recognizing the inherent complexity of agroecological systems and NRMS. It accommodates a wide range of sustainability dimensions, including but not limited to productivity, stability, resilience, adaptability, equity, and self-reliance. This breadth allows for a comprehensive evaluation that considers multiple facets of sustainability, ensuring that important aspects are not overlooked.

Furthermore, MESMIS acknowledges the importance of stakeholder involvement in the evaluation process. It encourages the engagement of diverse stakeholders, such as farmers, community members, researchers, and governmental bodies, to ensure that the evaluation reflects the perspectives and priorities of those directly impacted by agroecological practices and NRMS.

5.5.3 Structure and Components

The structure and components of the MESMIS framework are integral to its effectiveness in evaluating and enhancing the sustainability of agroecological practices and natural resource management systems (NRMS).

Phases

MESMIS is structured into a series of phases, each serving a distinct purpose in the evaluation process. These phases include:

- a. **Phase 1: Problem Formulation and Stakeholder Involvement:** This initial phase involves identifying the specific sustainability issues to be addressed and engaging stakeholders to ensure that their perspectives and priorities are considered from the outset.
- b. **Phase 2: System Description:** Here, a comprehensive description of the agroecological system or NRMS under evaluation is provided. This includes collecting data on various attributes and dimensions relevant to sustainability.

- c. Phase 3: Identification of System Attributes: In this phase, the key attributes that contribute to sustainability are identified. These attributes encompass aspects such as productivity, stability, resilience, adaptability, equity, and self-reliance.
- d. Phase 4: Measurement and Monitoring of Indicators: The framework emphasizes the importance of selecting appropriate indicators for each attribute and dimension. Various methods, including direct measurements, surveys, and simulation models, are employed to collect data.
- e. Phase 5: Integration of Results: This phase involves synthesizing the data and presenting it in an integrated manner, often using tools like the AMOEBA diagram to facilitate comparisons and assessments.
- f. Phase 6: Conclusions and Recommendations: The final phase focuses on drawing conclusions about the sustainability of the evaluated system and making recommendations for improvements.

Attributes and Dimensions

MESMIS places a strong emphasis on the identification of system attributes and dimensions relevant to sustainability. These attributes encompass economic, environmental, and social dimensions and are carefully selected based on the specific context of the evaluation.

Indicators

Indicators play a crucial role in MESMIS, as they are used to quantify and assess the various attributes and dimensions of sustainability. The framework provides flexibility in selecting indicators that are appropriate for the system under evaluation. These indicators range from measures of productivity and efficiency to biodiversity and soil properties.

Stakeholder Involvement

A central component of MESMIS is the active involvement of stakeholders throughout the evaluation process. This ensures that the perspectives, knowledge, and priorities of those directly affected by the agroecological practices or NRMS are taken into account.

Integration Tools

MESMIS employs tools like the AMOEBA diagram to integrate results and provide a comprehensive view of the system's sustainability performance. These tools facilitate comparisons between the evaluated system and an idealized benchmark.

5.5.4 Applicability in East Africa

East Africa exhibits a wide range of agroecological zones, from arid and semi-arid regions to highland areas with diverse cropping systems. MESMIS's adaptability allows it to accommodate this diversity by tailoring attribute selection and indicator choices to specific ecological contexts. Further, the region faces pressing sustainability concerns related to soil degradation, water scarcity, loss of biodiversity, and climate change impacts. MESMIS's focus on attributes like soil properties, (agro)biodiversity, and adaptability aligns well with the region's sustainability priorities.

East Africa's agriculture is not only ecologically diverse but also socially and economically complex. The framework's consideration of economic and social dimensions, including income, equity, and stakeholder involvement, aligns with the region's multifaceted challenges.

In East Africa, smallholder farmers, local communities, and indigenous groups play pivotal roles in agroecological practices and NRMS. MESMIS's emphasis on stakeholder involvement is particularly relevant, as it acknowledges the importance of local knowledge and participation in decision-making processes. Data availability can be a challenge in East Africa, but MESMIS's flexibility allows for the use of a variety of data sources, including direct measurements, surveys, and existing literature. This adaptability can help overcome data constraints in the region.

Many East African countries are actively working to integrate sustainable practices into agricultural policies and decision-making. MESMIS provides a structured approach to evaluating the effectiveness of these policies and identifying areas for improvement. In addition, East Africa has a vibrant research and innovation community focused on sustainable agriculture. MESMIS can serve as a valuable tool for researchers and practitioners in the region to assess the impacts of innovative agroecological practices.

5.5.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

Firstly, MESMIS stands out for its holistic approach to sustainability assessment. It encompasses a wide array of attributes, spanning economic, environmental, and social dimensions. This comprehensive perspective ensures that the framework captures the multifaceted nature of sustainability challenges, enabling a more thorough evaluation of NRMS. Another key strength lies in MESMIS's flexibility and adaptability. It is designed to accommodate diverse contexts, making it applicable across various agroecological systems and regions. This adaptability is particularly valuable as it allows the framework to address the unique needs, dynamics, and challenges of different areas. MESMIS's ability to be tailored to specific contexts enhances its relevance and utility.

Additionally, MESMIS places a strong emphasis on stakeholder engagement throughout the evaluation process. This participatory approach ensures that local knowledge, perspectives, and priorities are integrated into the assessment. Involving stakeholders enhances the credibility and acceptance of the evaluation outcomes, making them more actionable for decision-makers and communities.

Limitations

One notable challenge is the substantial data requirements. The framework relies on a wealth of data, which can be resource-intensive to collect, manage, and analyze. In regions with limited data availability and infrastructure, meeting these data demands can pose significant hurdles. Further, MESMIS's comprehensiveness, while valuable, can also be a drawback. Its complexity may present challenges for users, especially those new to sustainability assessments. Adequate training and guidance are essential to ensure that the framework is effectively implemented and that users can navigate its intricacies.

Additionally, conducting a MESMIS evaluation, particularly when incorporating longitudinal components, can be time-consuming. This extensive time commitment may limit its feasibility for projects or organizations with tight timelines. Furthermore, the participatory nature of MESMIS, while beneficial, can demand significant resources, including personnel, funding, and community engagement efforts. This may present a limitation for projects with

constrained resources. Moreover, MESMIS has seen limited adoption, resulting in a relatively small number of case studies. This limited pool of practical experiences and best practices may constrain its widespread use and limit the availability of guidance for users.

5.6 SOCLA Framework [106]

5.6.1 Overview

The SOCLA (Sociedad Científica Latinoamericana de Agroecología) framework is a comprehensive methodology designed to assess and evaluate the sustainability of agroecological practices within vineyard systems. The framework is particularly focused on vineyard systems but can be adapted to a broader range of agroecosystems in various eco-regions. Its primary aim is to provide a practical, farmer-friendly approach to rapidly assess soil quality and crop health while involving both farmers and researchers collaboratively.

The key objectives of the SOCLA framework are to offer a systematic way to assess agroecosystems, promote sustainability in agriculture, and empower farmers with the knowledge to make informed decisions. It emphasizes the importance of reducing dependence on external inputs, enhancing the natural resources of farms, and creating resilient and biodiverse agricultural systems.

The framework comprises two main categories of indicators: soil quality and crop health. Soil quality indicators assess various aspects such as soil structure, compaction, depth, residues, color, organic matter, water retention, soil cover, erosion, presence of invertebrates, and microbiological activity. Crop health indicators evaluate appearance, growth, disease incidence, insect pest incidence, natural enemy abundance and diversity, weed competition, potential yield, vegetational diversity, natural surrounding vegetation, and management system.

Each indicator is assigned a value between 1 and 10 based on observations and measurements conducted on the farm. A lower value indicates a less desirable condition, while a higher value signifies a more favorable attribute. These indicators help in assessing the overall health of the agroecosystem, both in terms of soil quality and crop health. Furthermore, the SOCLA framework uses an amoeba-type graph to visualize the status of soil quality and crop health. The closer the amoeba approaches the full diameter length of the circle, the more sustainable the system is considered. This graphical representation enables farmers to identify weak indicators and prioritize interventions to enhance soil, crop, or system deficiencies.

In practice, the SOCLA framework has been applied to real vineyard systems, with case studies providing insights into the assessment process and the potential for improving sustainability. The framework's strength lies in its simplicity, precision, practicality for decision-making, and the capability to integrate various soil and crop attributes, which are crucial for fostering sustainable agricultural practices.

5.6.2 Objectives and Scope

The objectives and scope of the SOCLA framework are underpinned by a strong commitment to promoting sustainable agricultural practices and assessing agroecosystems within the context of vineyards and beyond. This methodology is designed to serve as a practical and farmer-friendly tool for evaluating the sustainability of agroecological systems.

One of the core objectives of the SOCLA framework is to provide a structured approach to assess and monitor the health of agroecosystems, particularly focusing on the interplay between soil quality and crop health. By offering a

systematic way to evaluate these critical components, the framework aims to empower farmers with valuable insights into the conditions of their farms, enabling them to make informed decisions that enhance sustainability.

Furthermore, the framework emphasizes the reduction of external inputs and the conservation and enhancement of natural resources within agroecosystems. It aspires to help farmers transition from conventional monoculture systems to more diversified organic systems, ultimately reducing production costs while maintaining or improving soil, water, and biodiversity. Researchers involved in promoting organic vine management techniques also strive to design agroecosystems characterized by resilience to pests and diseases, nutrient retention, and high biodiversity levels.

The SOCLA framework acknowledges that sustainability in agriculture is not a one-size-fits-all concept. Hence, it seeks to be adaptable and applicable to a broad range of agroecosystems found in various eco-regions. While the framework was initially developed with a focus on vineyards in northern California, its inherent flexibility allows for adjustments and modifications to suit different geographical, climatic, and agricultural contexts, including those in East Africa.

5.6.3 Structure and Components

The structure and components of the SOCLA framework are carefully designed to facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of agroecosystems. This methodology provides a systematic approach to assess both soil quality and crop health, recognizing their interdependence within sustainable agricultural practices. The framework begins by identifying specific indicators related to soil quality and crop health. These indicators are chosen for their simplicity, ease of use by farmers, precision, and practicality in guiding management decisions. The framework ensures that the assessments can effectively capture the dynamics of agroecosystems, by focusing on indicators that are sensitive to environmental changes and management practices.

- In the context of *soil quality*, indicators encompass attributes such as soil structure, compaction, depth, residue status, color, odor, organic matter, water retention, soil cover, erosion, presence of invertebrates, and microbiological activity. These indicators provide insights into the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil, reflecting its overall health and functionality.
- On the other hand, *crop health indicators* evaluate the appearance of crops, pest and disease incidence, tolerance to weeds, crop growth, and potential yield. These indicators enable the assessment of the overall health and vitality of the cultivated plants, considering factors that influence their well-being and productivity.
- The framework also recognizes the importance of *ecological infrastructure within agroecosystems*. It considers plant diversity levels, surrounding natural vegetation, and system management types as critical components of sustainability assessments. These components help evaluate the ecological context in which agroecosystems operate, emphasizing the role of biodiversity and system management practices in promoting sustainability.

To assess agroecosystem sustainability, the SOCLA framework assigns values to each indicator based on observations and measurements. These values are typically on a scale from 1 to 10, with 1 representing the least desirable condition and 10 signifying the most preferred state. The assigned values reflect the observed attributes of soil quality and crop health, allowing for a quantitative assessment.

One of the distinctive features of the SOCLA framework is the use of amoeba-type graphs to visualize the status of soil quality and crop health. These graphs provide a clear and intuitive representation of the overall condition of agroecosystems. Farmers can easily identify weak indicators (those below 5) and prioritize interventions to improve

deficient attributes. The graphs also facilitate comparisons between different agroecosystems, highlighting those that exhibit higher levels of sustainability.

5.6.4 Applicability in East Africa

The applicability of the SOCLA framework in East Africa holds substantial promise for addressing the unique challenges and opportunities within the region's agroecological landscape. While the framework was initially developed with a focus on vineyard systems in Northern California, its core principles and methodology can be adapted and extended to diverse agroecosystems, including those found in East Africa.

East Africa encompasses a rich tapestry of agroecological zones, from highland regions to arid plains, each characterized by distinct soil types, cropping systems, and environmental conditions. The flexibility of the SOCLA framework allows for the adjustment of specific indicators to align with the particular context of East African agroecosystems. By replacing indicators that may be less relevant and incorporating locally meaningful metrics, the framework can be tailored to effectively evaluate soil quality and crop health in this region.

One of the strengths of the SOCLA framework is its farmer-friendly approach, emphasizing the active involvement of farmers in the assessment process. In East Africa, where smallholder farming is prevalent, this participatory aspect becomes particularly relevant. Farmers' indigenous knowledge and observations can complement the framework's indicators, enhancing the accuracy and contextual understanding of agroecosystem dynamics.

The framework's adaptability extends to its use of amoeba-type graphs for visualizing agroecosystem health. Such graphical representations can be easily understood by farmers in East Africa, aiding them in assessing their own agroecosystems. These visual tools empower farmers to identify areas of improvement and make informed decisions about resource allocation and management practices.

Furthermore, the SOCLA framework aligns with the sustainability goals and challenges facing East African agriculture. It recognizes the importance of ecological infrastructure, which resonates with the region's growing interest in agroforestry, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable land management practices. By assessing the diversity of natural vegetation, soil cover, and management approaches, the framework can contribute to the promotion of agroecological principles in the region.

Given East Africa's vulnerability to climate change and its impact on agriculture, the SOCLA framework's capacity to capture environmental changes through its indicators is invaluable. Farmers can use this information to adapt their practices to shifting climatic conditions and promote resilience in their agroecosystems.

5.6.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

One of its foremost strengths is its adaptability. The framework's flexibility allows for its effective use in different agroecological settings, making it a versatile tool for evaluating soil quality and crop health. Whether applied to vineyard systems in California or agroecosystems in East Africa, the framework's core principles can be customized to align with local conditions and priorities.

An inherent strength of the SOCLA framework is its farmer-friendly approach. By actively involving farmers in the assessment process, the framework empowers them to take ownership of their agroecosystems' sustainability. This participatory aspect is particularly advantageous in regions like East Africa, where smallholder farmers are central to agricultural production. The framework respects and integrates indigenous knowledge, enhancing the accuracy and relevance of its assessments.

Visual tools, such as the amoeba-type graphs, provide a distinct advantage by offering a clear and intuitive way to represent agroecosystem health. These graphical representations are accessible to farmers, researchers, and stakeholders, fostering better understanding and communication about soil quality and crop health. They enable farmers to identify areas that require improvement and guide decision-making regarding resource allocation and management practices.

The SOCLA framework's emphasis on ecological infrastructure aligns well with contemporary sustainability goals and challenges. It recognizes the importance of diverse natural vegetation, soil cover, and sustainable management practices. This alignment is particularly relevant in regions like East Africa, where agroforestry, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable land management are increasingly vital for ensuring food security and environmental resilience.

Limitations

However, the framework is not without its limitations. One notable limitation is that it was initially developed with a focus on specific agroecosystems, such as vineyards in California. Adapting it to different contexts requires careful consideration and customization of indicators. While its flexibility allows for this adaptability, it may necessitate more extensive modifications to suit certain agroecosystems.

The effectiveness of the SOCLA framework depends on the availability of relevant data and the capacity to gather accurate measurements for its indicators. In resource-constrained regions, such as parts of East Africa, data collection and analysis may pose challenges. Overcoming these limitations may require investments in training and capacity-building. Additionally, the framework's reliance on assigned values for indicators implies subjectivity to some extent. Assigning values based on observations and measurements can introduce variability in the assessment process. Ensuring consistency and reliability across different assessors and regions may require standardization and rigorous training.

5.7 OASIS (Original agroecological Survey Indicator Systems) [4]

5.7.1 Overview

The OASIS framework is designed to evaluate the sustainability of agroecological practices. It provides a systematic approach to assess various dimensions of agroecological systems, offering valuable insights into their economic and environmental viability. This framework is instrumental in understanding and addressing the complex challenges and opportunities within agriculture. The framework underscores the importance of transitioning towards more sustainable agricultural systems. One of the central aspects of the OASIS framework is Farm Systems Analysis, which delves into the specifics of agroecological farm systems. It evaluates the diverse practices, techniques, and strategies employed on farms, taking into account local factors such as climate, geography, and socio-economic conditions. It recognizes the need to tailor agroecological approaches to the unique characteristics of each farm.

The social dimension of agro-ecology is a key focus within the framework. It assesses the impact of agroecological practices on farmers' livelihoods and well-being, considering factors such as income, labor conditions, and gender equality. This dimension highlights the human aspect of sustainability. Economic sustainability is another critical facet addressed by the OASIS framework. It scrutinizes the financial viability of agroecological practices, assessing their cost-effectiveness, income-generating potential, and contribution to economic well-being. This section encourages a shift away from conventional practices towards more sustainable economic models.

The framework also places significant emphasis on the environmental dimension. It assesses the impact of agroecological systems on the ecosystem, addressing issues such as pollution, soil health, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity conservation. This dimension underscores the importance of sustainable land use and environmental stewardship in agroecology. Resilience is a central theme within the OASIS framework. It explores the capacity of agroecological practices to withstand shocks, adapt to changing conditions, and ensure the continued provision of ecosystem services. Resilience is particularly vital in the face of climate change and other challenges.

Participation and collaboration among stakeholders are key principles of the OASIS framework. It emphasizes the importance of involving farmers, advisers, and scientists in the evaluation process, promoting mutual learning and empowering farmers to take ownership of their practices. This inclusive approach fosters a deeper understanding of sustainability and encourages meaningful engagement in agricultural improvement.

5.7.2 Objectives and Scope

The objectives and scope of the OASIS framework are designed to address the multifaceted challenges and opportunities within agroecological practices. At its core, the framework seeks to promote sustainability in agriculture by providing a comprehensive evaluation system. One of its primary objectives is to assess and understand the diverse dimensions of agroecological systems, recognizing the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental factors. This aims to facilitate informed decision-making and guide the transition towards more sustainable farming practices.

The OASIS framework is not limited to a narrow scope; instead, it encompasses a wide range of aspects related to agroecological practices. It takes into account the local context, acknowledging that agriculture varies greatly across regions due to differences in climate, geography, and socio-economic conditions. This inclusiveness allows for a tailored approach to sustainability, recognizing that one size does not fit all in agriculture.

Economic sustainability is a significant focus of the framework. It aims to evaluate the financial viability of agroecological practices, considering factors such as cost-effectiveness, income generation, and economic well-being. This economic dimension is crucial for encouraging the adoption of sustainable practices by demonstrating their benefits to farmers.

Environmental sustainability is another central aspect of the OASIS framework. It seeks to assess the impact of agroecological systems on the environment, addressing issues like pollution, soil health, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity conservation. By doing so, it underscores the importance of environmentally responsible farming practices.

The framework also recognizes the importance of social sustainability. It aims to evaluate how agroecological practices impact farmers' livelihoods, labor conditions, and overall well-being. This social dimension emphasizes the human element of sustainability and seeks to ensure that farmers benefit from these practices.

Resilience is a key theme within the OASIS framework. It assesses the capacity of agroecological systems to withstand shocks, adapt to changing conditions, and continue providing essential ecosystem services. Resilience is vital, especially in the face of challenges such as climate change and economic uncertainties.

5.7.3 Structure and Components

The OASIS framework is structured with a set of components that collectively assess and evaluate agroecological practices comprehensively. These components are designed to capture the various dimensions of sustainability, ensuring a holistic evaluation.

- One of the key components of the OASIS framework focuses on the **economic aspects** of agroecological practices. This component delves into factors such as cost-effectiveness, income generation, and overall economic viability. By evaluating the financial aspects, the framework aims to demonstrate that sustainable practices can also be economically beneficial for farmers, thus incentivizing their adoption.
- **Environmental sustainability** is another critical component. It assesses the environmental impact of agroecological systems, examining issues like pollution, soil health, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity conservation. By evaluating these aspects, the framework highlights the importance of environmentally responsible farming practices and their role in preserving natural resources.
- **Social sustainability** is an integral part of the OASIS framework. This component evaluates how agroecological practices impact the well-being and livelihoods of farmers. It considers factors such as labor conditions, access to resources, and overall quality of life. Social sustainability underscores the human dimension of sustainability, ensuring that farmers benefit from these practices.
- **The resilience** component within the framework assesses the capacity of agroecological systems to withstand shocks, adapt to changing conditions, and continue providing essential ecosystem services. Resilience is crucial, especially in the face of challenges like climate change and economic uncertainties. This component helps identify strategies to enhance the resilience of farming systems.

Another significant aspect of the OASIS framework is the participatory approach. It emphasizes active engagement and collaboration among farmers, advisers, and scientists. This component encourages mutual learning, empowers farmers by valuing their traditional knowledge, and ensures that their needs and insights are integrated into decision-making processes.

The framework also incorporates indicators and criteria that facilitate the evaluation process. These indicators help quantify and measure the performance of agroecological practices in each of the aforementioned dimensions. They provide a systematic way to assess sustainability and track progress over time.

Furthermore, the OASIS framework acknowledges the importance of local context. It recognizes that agriculture varies significantly across regions due to differences in climate, geography, and socio-economic conditions. This contextual consideration allows for a tailored approach to sustainability, ensuring that strategies are relevant and effective in specific locations.

5.7.4 Applicability in East Africa

The OASIS framework, designed to assess the sustainability of agroecological practices, offers a comprehensive approach that is well-suited for application in East Africa. This region is characterized by diverse agro-ecosystems, varying climate conditions, and a range of socio-economic factors that influence agricultural practices and outcomes. The primary objective of the OASIS framework is to evaluate agroecological practices comprehensively, considering economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Its scope encompasses a wide range of criteria and indicators that

capture the multifaceted aspects of sustainability, making it relevant to the complex agricultural landscapes of East Africa. The framework's five dimensions cover crucial aspects such as agroecological practices, socio-economic factors, soil health, biodiversity, and resilience.

When applied in East Africa, the OASIS framework demonstrates its relevance and adaptability to diverse agro-ecosystems. East Africa's agriculture varies from highland areas with temperate climates to arid regions and coastal plains with distinct challenges and opportunities. The framework can be tailored to suit these varying contexts, providing valuable insights into the sustainability of local farming practices.

One of the critical challenges in East Africa is climate variability, including irregular rainfall patterns and prolonged droughts. The OASIS framework's focus on resilience is particularly pertinent in this context. It can help identify strategies to enhance the adaptive capacity of farming systems, ensuring food security in the face of climate change. Moreover, the majority of farmers in East Africa are smallholders who rely on agriculture for their livelihoods. The framework's economic and social sustainability components are essential for assessing the well-being of these farmers. It can evaluate the economic viability of agroecological practices for smallholders and assess their social impacts, including labor conditions and income generation.

East Africa is renowned for its rich biodiversity, including unique flora and fauna. The OASIS framework's environmental sustainability component can evaluate the impact of farming practices on biodiversity conservation. It can promote the adoption of agroecological practices that protect and enhance local biodiversity, aligning with conservation efforts in the region. Additionally, soil degradation is a significant concern in many parts of East Africa. The OASIS framework's focus on soil health and carbon sequestration is highly relevant. It can encourage practices that improve soil fertility and structure, such as agroforestry and organic farming, addressing soil degradation challenges.

A participatory approach is central to the OASIS framework, emphasizing collaboration among farmers, advisers, and scientists. This approach aligns well with existing initiatives in East Africa that promote farmer involvement in decision-making processes and knowledge sharing. Furthermore, the data-driven nature of the OASIS framework can provide valuable insights to East African governments and policymakers. It can inform policy decisions related to agriculture, resource management, and rural development, contributing to more sustainable and resilient agricultural systems in the region.

5.7.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

One of its primary strengths lies in its comprehensive and multidimensional approach. By encompassing economic, environmental, and social dimensions across the various distinct dimensions, the framework offers a holistic perspective on sustainability. This breadth allows it to capture the complex interplay of factors that influence agricultural systems, making it suitable for addressing multifaceted challenges in East Africa's diverse agro-ecosystems.

The framework's adaptability is another significant strength, enabling it to be tailored to various agricultural contexts within East Africa. The region's agro-ecosystems vary widely, from highlands to arid lowlands, and the framework's flexibility allows for context-specific assessments. It can accommodate diverse farming practices, crops, and livestock systems, ensuring that it remains relevant and applicable to the region's agricultural diversity.

Additionally, the OASIS framework's focus on participatory evaluation aligns with the region's existing efforts to involve farmers, advisers, and scientists in decision-making processes. This participatory approach fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing, empowering local farmers and enhancing the relevance of assessment outcomes. It recognizes the value of indigenous knowledge and traditional practices, promoting their inclusion in sustainability assessments. The framework's attention to resilience is particularly valuable in East Africa, where climate variability poses significant challenges to agriculture. By evaluating the capacity of farming systems to withstand and adapt to shocks and stresses, the OASIS framework can inform strategies for building climate resilience. This is crucial for ensuring food security in a region where many rely on rain-fed agriculture.

Moreover, the OASIS framework's emphasis on biodiversity and soil health aligns with East Africa's rich natural heritage. It promotes practices that protect and enhance local biodiversity while addressing soil degradation, critical issues in the region. This environmental focus resonates with conservation efforts and sustainable land management initiatives in East Africa.

Limitations

One key limitation is the need for extensive data collection and analysis. Gathering data for all the dimensions and numerous indicators can be resource-intensive and may pose challenges in data-scarce regions of East Africa. Adequate capacity and resources are necessary to implement the framework effectively. Another limitation is the potential subjectivity of certain indicators and criteria. Assessments of social and economic dimensions, in particular, may involve qualitative data that can be influenced by interpretation. Ensuring consistency and objectivity in data collection and analysis is essential to maintain the framework's credibility.

The complexity of the OASIS framework may also pose a challenge, especially for smallholder farmers and local communities with limited technical capacity. Training and support may be required to facilitate their participation effectively. Furthermore, the framework's success relies on the willingness of stakeholders to engage in the participatory process. If farmers and other stakeholders perceive the process as tokenistic or lacking tangible benefits, their participation may be limited, affecting the quality of assessment outcomes.

5.8 SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment) [107]

5.8.1 Overview

The SAFE framework offers a holistic and hierarchical methodology designed to evaluate the sustainability of agro-ecosystems, making it particularly relevant for assessing the economic and environmental sustainability of agroecological practices in East Africa. This framework takes a comprehensive approach, recognizing that sustainability in agriculture encompasses economic, environmental, and social dimensions. It is structured around three fundamental pillars: environmental, economic, and social aspects, providing a well-rounded assessment of sustainability.

In the environmental pillar, the SAFE framework delves into five critical natural resources: air, soil, water, energy, and biodiversity. For each of these resources, it examines both their quantity and quality. Additionally, it emphasizes the need for adequate buffering mechanisms to manage the fluxes or flows associated with these resources. SAFE ensures a robust evaluation of the ecological sustainability of agro-ecosystems in East Africa, by addressing these environmental factors.

On the social front, the framework prioritizes the well-being of the farming community. It assesses various aspects, including labor conditions, health, education, gender equality, and access to infrastructure and activities. By taking into account the social dimensions, SAFE acknowledges the importance of ensuring that agroecological practices enhance the quality of life for those engaged in farming activities. This is a crucial consideration in regions like East Africa where agriculture plays a central role in livelihoods.

Economic sustainability is another critical dimension within the SAFE framework. It places an emphasis on farm income, aiming to ensure that agricultural activities are economically viable. The framework also strives to minimize dependency on external finance, optimize agricultural and market activities, and secure the inter-generational continuation of farming. These economic criteria align with the need to promote financial stability and independence among farming communities in East Africa.

One of the notable strengths of the SAFE framework is its multi-scale approach. It operates at various spatial levels, ranging from the field to the farm and landscape/administrative unit levels. This multi-scale perspective allows for a comprehensive evaluation that considers both local impacts and broader regional or national implications. In East Africa, where agro-ecosystems can vary significantly within relatively short distances, this multi-scale approach is particularly valuable. Moreover, the SAFE framework is designed for universal applicability, offering adaptability to different agro-ecosystem contexts. While it maintains a structured and holistic foundation, it acknowledges the need for flexibility in selecting sustainability indicators. This recognition of context-specific considerations is essential in a region as diverse as East Africa, where agroecological practices can vary widely.

5.8.2 Objectives and Scope

Objectives

At its core, the SAFE framework aims to evaluate and enhance the sustainability of farming practices by considering three fundamental pillars: environmental, economic, and social aspects. These pillars reflect the multidimensional nature of sustainability, recognizing that successful agricultural systems must balance ecological, economic, and social goals.

Within the environmental pillar, the SAFE framework has a primary objective to ensure the maintenance or enhancement of essential natural resources. This involves assessing critical resources such as air, soil, water, energy, and biodiversity. The framework's scope extends to evaluating both the quantity and quality of these resources, acknowledging their fundamental roles in agricultural production and ecological stability. Additionally, the framework emphasizes the need to buffer and manage the flow of these resources to prevent adverse impacts on agro-ecosystems.

In the economic dimension, the SAFE framework is driven by the objective of ensuring economic viability within farming communities. It seeks to assess and improve farm income, minimize dependency on external financial support, and optimize agricultural and market activities. The framework recognizes that economic sustainability is essential for the long-term success of agro-ecosystems and aims to enhance the financial well-being of farmers.

Social objectives within the SAFE framework are centered on improving the quality of life for farming communities. This includes assessing labor conditions, health, education, gender equality, and access to essential infrastructure and activities. The scope extends to ensuring the well-being and integration of farming families within their local and agricultural societies. In regions like East Africa, where agriculture is a cornerstone of livelihoods, these social considerations are of paramount importance.

Scope

The SAFE framework operates at multiple spatial scales, encompassing the field, farm, and landscape/administrative unit levels. This multi-scale approach broadens its scope and allows for a more nuanced evaluation of sustainability. It recognizes that agroecosystems can vary significantly within regions, and impacts must be assessed at various spatial levels to capture local and regional dynamics adequately.

Importantly, the SAFE framework is designed with universal applicability in mind. While it maintains a structured and holistic foundation, it also allows for flexibility in the selection of sustainability indicators. This flexibility accommodates the diverse contexts and agroecosystems found in different regions, including East Africa. By providing a universally applicable yet adaptable framework, SAFE can be a valuable tool for assessing and improving the sustainability of agroecological practices in a variety of settings.

5.8.3 Structure and Components

The SAFE framework is characterized by its well-structured and hierarchical design, which comprises distinct components aimed at facilitating a comprehensive assessment of agroecosystem sustainability.

Pillars of Sustainability: At the core of the SAFE framework are three interconnected pillars, each representing a fundamental dimension of sustainability: environmental, economic, and social. These pillars serve as the foundational framework for evaluating the sustainability of agroecosystems, recognizing that success in farming practices hinges on achieving a harmonious balance across these dimensions.

- a. **Environmental Pillar:** This pillar is dedicated to assessing and enhancing the environmental aspects of agroecosystems. It encompasses a range of functions related to natural resources, including air, soil, water, energy, and biodiversity. The environmental dimension of SAFE focuses on the quantity and quality of these resources, with an emphasis on buffering and managing the flow of resources to prevent adverse ecological impacts. The objective is to maintain or enhance these resources to ensure the long-term sustainability of agriculture.
- b. **Economic Pillar:** Within the economic dimension, the SAFE framework aims to evaluate the economic viability of farming practices. Key objectives include ensuring farm income, minimizing dependency on external financial support, optimizing agricultural and market activities, and enhancing the overall economic efficiency of farming systems. Economic sustainability is recognized as a critical factor in the success and resilience of agro-ecosystems.
- c. **Social Pillar:** The social dimension of the SAFE framework is centered on improving the quality of life for farming communities. It encompasses a wide range of factors, including labor conditions, health, education, gender equality, access to infrastructure and activities, and community integration. Ensuring the well-being and social acceptability of farming families within their local and agricultural societies is a central objective.

5.8.4 Applicability in East Africa

In the context of East Africa, where agriculture plays a pivotal role in livelihoods and food security, the SAFE framework offers a structured and holistic approach to evaluating the sustainability of farming practices. The region's agricultural landscape encompasses a wide range of farming systems, from smallholder subsistence farming to larger commercial enterprises. SAFE's multi-scale assessment, spanning from field to landscape levels, is particularly relevant for capturing the nuances of these diverse systems.

East Africa faces pressing environmental challenges, including soil degradation, water scarcity, and biodiversity loss. SAFE's environmental pillar, which emphasizes managing and conserving natural resources such as soil, water, and biodiversity, aligns with the region's need to address these issues. By assessing the quantity and quality of these resources and their buffering functions, the framework can help identify strategies to mitigate environmental degradation and enhance resource sustainability.

The economic pillar of SAFE resonates with East Africa's quest for economic viability in agriculture. Farm income and reducing dependency on external financial support are paramount concerns in the region. SAFE's focus on optimizing agricultural and market activities, enhancing economic efficiency, and promoting farmer training aligns with East Africa's goals of improving economic prospects for farming communities.

The social pillar of SAFE is of particular relevance in East Africa, where the well-being of farming families and communities is central to sustainable development. Issues such as labor conditions, health, education, gender equality, and access to social infrastructure are vital considerations. SAFE's comprehensive approach to social sustainability can help address these challenges and contribute to improved quality of life for East Africa's farming communities. Furthermore, the flexibility inherent in the SAFE framework makes it well-suited for adaptation to the specific contexts and conditions of East Africa. While the framework provides a structured foundation, it accommodates the customization of sustainability indicators to align with the unique characteristics of agro-ecosystems in the region. This flexibility empowers local stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers to tailor assessments to East Africa's diverse farming landscapes.

5.8.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

One of the significant strengths of SAFE is its holistic and systematic approach to sustainability assessment. By considering three pillars—environmental, economic, and social—it ensures a comprehensive evaluation of agro-ecosystems. This holistic perspective aligns with the complex and interconnected nature of sustainability challenges in East Africa, where environmental degradation, economic viability, and social well-being are interlinked.

The multi-scale assessment capability of SAFE, ranging from the field to landscape levels, is another strength. This feature allows for the consideration of diverse farming systems prevalent in East Africa, from smallholder subsistence farming to larger commercial enterprises. It enables stakeholders to tailor assessments to specific contexts and scales, accommodating the region's agricultural diversity. Further, SAFE's structured framework provides a clear and organized foundation for sustainability assessment. The definition of principles and criteria, along with indicators and thresholds, offers a structured approach that helps in guiding assessments and decision-making processes. This clarity enhances the framework's usability for a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and farming communities.

Moreover, the flexibility inherent in SAFE is an advantage, particularly in East Africa. The framework can be adapted and customized to suit local conditions and priorities. This adaptability empowers stakeholders to select indicators that are most relevant to their specific agroecosystems and sustainability goals, making it a versatile tool.

Limitations

One notable limitation is the need for data and information to support the assessment. In many parts of East Africa, data availability and quality can be challenging, which may hinder the implementation of the framework. Efforts to improve data collection and accessibility are crucial to overcome this limitation.

Another limitation is the potential complexity of the framework, especially for users who are not familiar with sustainability assessments. SAFE's multi-dimensional approach, with its various principles, criteria, and indicators, can be overwhelming for some stakeholders. Adequate training and capacity building are essential to ensure effective use.

Additionally, the participatory nature of SAFE, while a strength, can also be a limitation. Engaging various stakeholders in the assessment process requires time, resources, and coordination. In contexts with limited resources, such as many parts of East Africa, achieving meaningful participation can be challenging.

5.9 Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems (SAFA) [108]

5.9.1 Overview

The SAFA framework is a comprehensive tool developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in collaboration with the ISEAL Alliance. It was created in response to the proliferation of sustainability policies, instruments, and initiatives across various sectors, including supply chains. These efforts often lacked a unified understanding of sustainability, leading to the need for a practical and operational definition of sustainability, which SAFA aims to provide.

SAFA's primary objective is to contribute to the sustainable development of agricultural systems and food chains, with a focus on environmental, social, and economic dimensions, all underpinned by principles of good governance. The framework is designed to help move agriculture and food production towards a development model that is environmentally benign, socially just, and economically viable through models of good governance.

At its core, SAFA is built upon four essential pillars that play pivotal roles in creating conditions for sustainable development. These pillars include:

- a. **Environmental Integrity:** This pillar emphasizes the responsible management of natural resources, covering issues such as water conservation, biodiversity, land and soil preservation, and efforts to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.
- b. **Economic Resilience:** Economic sustainability is addressed through aspects like secure livelihoods, resilience to economic risks, and sustainable production practices that minimize resource use and emissions over the product life cycle.
- c. **Social Well-Being:** SAFA places a strong emphasis on social sustainability, focusing on labor rights, non-discrimination and equity, education, health and safety, and social commitment to benefit society as a whole.
- d. **Good Governance:** Governance is considered an enabling concept for sustainability in the SAFA framework. It encompasses accountability, adherence to the rule of law, and transparency in decision-making processes and activities.

Within each of these pillars, SAFA identifies specific core issues that are crucial for evaluating sustainability. These core issues serve as the foundation for assessing sustainability in a practical context. For example, core issues under the "Environmental Integrity" pillar include water quantity and quality, biodiversity and ecosystems, land and soil maintenance, and greenhouse gas emissions reduction.

To facilitate assessment, SAFA proposes a set of draft headline indicators and indicators for each core issue. These indicators are primarily aimed at food chains and are intended to measure and evaluate the performance of food businesses in relation to sustainability. SAFA provides a comprehensive "map" of existing indicators for each sustainability pillar, aiding stakeholders in assessing and improving their sustainability efforts. Furthermore, SAFA offers a flexible and dynamic assessment framework that allows stakeholders to assess the inter-linkages and trade-offs between core sustainability issues and different indicators. This visualization provides insights into a company's or organization's strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement, ultimately contributing to enhanced sustainability in food chains.

5.9.2 Objectives and Scope

Objectives

One primary objective of SAFA is to define a comprehensive Sustainability Framework that encompasses an agreed set of core sustainability issues. This framework can be applied at various levels, including the national, supply chain, or operational unit level. By establishing this common framework, SAFA seeks to provide a practical and operational understanding of what sustainability means in the context of food and agriculture. This objective is pivotal in addressing the challenge of diverse and often fragmented sustainability efforts across sectors.

A second key goal is the development of International Guidelines on Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems (SAFA). These guidelines are meant to facilitate full sustainability assessments, making food chains more transparent, measurable, and verifiable. The guidelines aim to translate a universally agreed-upon definition of sustainability, along with core issues for each sustainability pillar, into a set of core and additional indicators specifically applicable to food chains. Additionally, they provide solid guidance for the calculation of these indicators. This objective serves to standardize and streamline sustainability assessments in the food industry.

The third objective centers on the creation of an International Tool for the Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems. This tool is intended for use by food businesses to assess and improve their own sustainability efforts and contributions. By leveraging the guidelines and indicators, the tool provides a means to assess food chains and companies in a more quantitative and standardized manner, aligning with the principles of corporate social responsibility reporting.

Scope

In terms of scope, the SAFA framework casts a wide net. It encompasses all actors along the food chain, from farm to final sales, recognizing their potential to generate significant sustainability impacts, both actual and potential. This inclusive approach covers entities over which the reporting organization exercises control or significant influence with regard to financial and operating policies and practices, adhering to the scoping principle adopted from Global Reporting Initiatives (GRI) Guidelines. Sustainability impacts are considered across economic, environmental, social, and governance parameters.

In addition to its broad coverage, SAFA outlines the temporal and spatial scope of its assessments. The temporal scope typically focuses on the most recent year for which all core data are available. However, for some indicators, such as greenhouse gas emissions, several years may be necessary to reliably identify trends. The spatial coverage extends to all production facilities and their immediate surroundings, as far as the entities involved in the food chain directly or indirectly control the utilization of these areas.

5.9.3 Structure and Components

Framework Structure

The SAFA framework is structured around four main pillars, each representing a critical dimension of sustainability in food and agriculture:

- a. **Environmental Integrity:** This pillar focuses on the responsible management of natural resources and the environment. It includes core issues such as water quantity and quality, biodiversity and ecosystems, land and soil maintenance, and efforts to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.
- b. **Economic Resilience:** Economic sustainability is a key dimension, addressing aspects such as secure livelihoods, resilience to economic risks, and sustainable production practices that minimize resource use and emissions over the product life cycle.
- c. **Social Well-Being:** SAFA places a strong emphasis on social sustainability. This pillar encompasses core issues related to labor rights, non-discrimination and equity, education, health and safety, and social commitment to benefit society as a whole.
- d. **Good Governance:** Governance is considered an enabling concept for sustainability in the SAFA framework. This pillar focuses on issues related to accountability, adherence to the rule of law, transparency in decision-making processes, and participation in activities that contribute to sustainability.

Components of the Framework

Within each of these four pillars, SAFA identifies specific core issues that serve as the foundational components for sustainability assessment. These core issues are critical aspects that contribute to the overall sustainability of food and agriculture systems. Some examples of core issues include:

- a. **Environmental Integrity:** Core issues within this pillar include water quantity and quality, biodiversity and ecosystems, land and soil maintenance, and efforts to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions.
- b. **Economic Resilience:** Core issues under economic resilience encompass secure livelihoods, resilience to economic risks, and sustainable production practices that minimize resource use and emissions.
- c. **Social Well-Being:** This pillar covers core issues such as labor rights, non-discrimination and equity, education, health and safety, and social commitment.
- d. **Good Governance:** Core issues related to governance include accountability, adherence to the rule of law, transparency, and participation in decision-making processes.

In addition to core issues, SAFA provides a set of draft headline indicators and indicators for each core issue. These indicators are primarily aimed at food chains and are intended to measure and evaluate the performance of food businesses in relation to sustainability. They serve as practical tools for assessing and improving sustainability efforts.

SAFA also offers a flexible and dynamic assessment framework that allows stakeholders to visualize the inter-linkages and trade-offs between core sustainability issues and different indicators. This visualization provides insights into a company's or organization's strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement, ultimately contributing to enhanced sustainability in food chains.

5.9.4 Applicability in East Africa

The applicability of the SAFA framework in East Africa holds great potential for addressing the unique sustainability challenges and opportunities within the region. While SAFA is a globally relevant tool, its principles and components can be tailored to align with the specific characteristics of East Africa's agricultural and food systems. East Africa is known for its rich agricultural diversity, encompassing various crops and livestock, and it plays a significant role in the region's economy and food security. However, the region also faces sustainability challenges related to climate change, resource management, social equity, and governance, making the application of the SAFA framework particularly pertinent.

One key advantage of SAFA in the context of East Africa is its adaptability to diverse agricultural practices. The framework's core pillars, which cover environmental integrity, economic resilience, social well-being, and good governance, provide a comprehensive lens through which to assess the sustainability of agroecological practices in the region. This flexibility allows stakeholders to evaluate a wide range of farming systems, from smallholder subsistence agriculture to large commercial operations.

The core issues identified within the SAFA framework align with many of the sustainability concerns in East Africa. For example, issues related to water quantity and quality, biodiversity, land and soil conservation, and greenhouse gas emissions are directly relevant to the region's agricultural practices. East Africa is vulnerable to climate change impacts, including shifting rainfall patterns and increased drought frequency, making the assessment of sustainable water and resource management crucial. Moreover, the social well-being pillar of SAFA addresses labor rights, non-discrimination, education, health, and social commitment. These aspects resonate with the region's goals of promoting equitable access to resources, improving livelihoods, and enhancing social inclusivity, particularly among marginalized groups and women farmers. Good governance, another fundamental pillar of SAFA, is of paramount importance in East Africa. Transparent and accountable governance mechanisms are essential for addressing issues such as land tenure, resource allocation, and conflict resolution, all of which play a pivotal role in sustainable agriculture and food systems.

The SAFA framework's structured approach, core issues, and indicators provide a systematic and standardized method for evaluating the economic and environmental sustainability of agroecological practices in East Africa. It can serve as a valuable tool for various stakeholders, including government agencies, NGOs, research institutions, and agricultural producers, to assess, monitor, and enhance sustainability efforts in the region. Furthermore, the flexibility of SAFA allows for the incorporation of region-specific indicators and contextual factors, ensuring that the framework remains relevant and adaptable to the evolving needs and challenges of East Africa's agricultural sector. By utilizing SAFA, stakeholders in East Africa can work collaboratively to promote sustainable agricultural practices that improve food security, protect natural resources, and enhance the well-being of local communities.

5.9.5 Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

One of the notable strengths of SAFA is its flexibility and adaptability. It can be tailored to diverse agricultural and food systems, making it applicable to various scales of operation. This adaptability is particularly valuable when assessing sustainability in regions with unique challenges and opportunities, such as East Africa. SAFA's clear core issues and indicators within each pillar provide a structured and systematic approach to sustainability assessment. Stakeholders can use these indicators to identify specific areas for improvement and track progress over time, promoting transparency and accountability.

Another distinctive feature of SAFA is its emphasis on good governance as a core pillar. Good governance principles, including transparency, accountability, and equitable decision-making, are often overlooked in sustainability assessments but are essential for ensuring fair and responsible practices in food and agriculture systems.

Limitations

Its comprehensive nature can be complex and may pose challenges for those new to sustainability assessments. Collecting and verifying the substantial amount of data required by SAFA can be resource-intensive, which may be particularly challenging in regions with limited resources, like some parts of East Africa.

Some indicators within SAFA involve subjective assessments, especially in the areas of social well-being and good governance. This subjectivity can lead to varying interpretations and judgments, potentially affecting the consistency of assessments. Additionally, as sustainability concepts and priorities evolve over time, SAFA may require periodic updates to remain aligned with the latest trends and issues. Ensuring that the framework remains relevant and up-to-date is essential for its continued effectiveness.

6. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FRAMEWORKS

6.1 Indicators under each framework and the target groups/audience

TABLE 2: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS SHOWING INDICATORS UNDER EACH FRAMEWORK AND THE TARGET AUDIENCE

Name of the Indicator Framework included	Indicator frameworks	Target groups/audience
<p>Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework [101]</p>	<p>a. Productivity Domain</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Crop productivity, Crop biomass productivity, Animal productivity, Variability of production, Input use efficiency, Yield gap, Cropping intensity, Post-harvest losses</p> <p>b. Economic Domain</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Profitability, Variability of profitability, Income diversification, Returns to land, labor, and input, Input use intensity, Labour requirement, Poverty, Market Participation, Market orientation</p> <p>c. Environment Domain</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Vegetative cover, Plant biodiversity, Pest levels, Insect biodiversity, Fuel availability, Water availability, Water quality, Erosion, Soil biology, Soil chemical quality, Soil physical quality, GHG emissions, Pesticide use.</p> <p>d. Human Condition Domain</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Nutrition, Food security, Food safety, Human health, Capacity to experiment</p> <p>e. Social Domain</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Gender equity, Equity (generally), Social cohesion, Collective cohesion, Collective action</p>	<p>The framework targets researchers (Agricultural scientists) who are involved in generating and assessing SI developments. It was designed especially for use in smallholder farming situations where changes in agricultural productivity can have a positive or negative impact on development goals such as boosting food and nutrition security and preventing land degradation.</p>
<p>A Tool for Agro-ecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) framework [15]</p>	<p>a. Governance</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Secure land tenure</p> <p>b. Economy</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Productivity, Income, Value added</p> <p>c. Health and Nutrition</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Exposure to pesticides, dietary diversity</p> <p>d. Society and culture</p> <p><i>Indicators:</i> Women’s empowerment, Youth employment opportunities</p>	<p>TAPE focuses on global and regional agroecological communities of practise, which comprise scientists, activists, farmers, and extension workers.</p>

	<p>e. Environment</p> <p>Indicators: Agricultural biodiversity, & Soil health</p>	
<p>The five-dimensional SF Presidia framework [103]</p>	<p>a. Product quality</p> <p>Indicators: Rules of production, Taste, Nutrient content, Food safety, Local and seasonal</p> <p>b. Cultural sustainability</p> <p>Indicators: Cultural identity, Transmitting knowledge, Traditional processing, Traditional conservation technique, Traditional gastronomy.</p> <p>c. Social sustainability</p> <p>Indicators; Educational meeting, Knowledge sharing, Relationship with local institution, Organizational formalization of the presidium, Democratic nature of the group, Social inclusion, & Community power, Meeting between producers, Meeting with SF⁺ head office, Educational activity, Pride and social gratification, Producer number</p> <p>d. Environmental sustainability</p> <p>Indicators: Ecosystem biodiversity, species diversity, Genetic diversity, Water quantity, Water quality, Air quality, Erosion (soil cover index and green manure), Crop rotation, Energy and waste (Renewable source, packaging)</p> <p>e. Economic sustainability</p> <p>Indicators: Supply chain, Price, Aggregation, Production area.</p>	<p>Small and local agro-food systems</p>
<p>Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development (IDEA) [104]</p>	<p>Uses three scales;</p> <p>a. THE AGRO ECOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY SCALE</p> <p><i>i. Diversity</i></p> <p>Indicators: Diversity of annual or temporal crops, Diversity of perennial crops, Diversity of associated vegetation, Animal diversity, Enhancement and conservation of genetic heritage</p> <p><i>ii. Organization of space</i></p> <p>Indicators: Cropping patterns, Dimension of fields, Organic matter management, Ecological buffer zones, Measures to protect the natural heritage, Stocking rate, Fodder area management</p> <p><i>iii. Farming practice</i></p> <p>Indicators: Fertilization, Effluent processing, Pesticides and veterinary products, Animal well-being, Soil resource protection, Energy dependence.</p> <p>b. THE SOCIO-TERRITORIAL SCALE</p> <p><i>i. Quality of the products and land</i></p>	<p>Farmers supported by advisory officers</p>

	<p>Indicators: Quality of foodstuffs produced, Enhancement of buildings and landscape heritage, Processing of non-organic waste, Accessibility of space, Social involvement</p> <p>ii. Organization of space</p> <p>Indicators: Short trade, Services, and multiactivities, Contribution to employment, Collective work, Probable farm sustainability.</p> <p>iii. Ethics and human development</p> <p>Indicators: Contribution to world food balance, Training, Labour intensity, Quality of live, Isolation, Reception, hygiene and safety,</p> <p>c. THE ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY SCALE</p> <p>i. Economic viability</p> <p>Indicators: Available income per worker compared with the national legal minimum wage, economic specialization rate</p> <p>ii. Independence</p> <p>Indicators: Financial autonomy, Reliance on direct subsidies from CAP and indirect economic impact of milk and sugar quotas</p> <p>iii. Transferability</p> <p>Indicators: Total assets minus lands value by non-salaried worker unit</p> <p>iv. Efficiency</p> <p>Indicators: Operating expenses as a proportion of total production value.</p>	
<p>MESMIS Framework [105]</p>	<p>a. Productivity</p> <p>Indicators: Yields, quality of products, Cost/benefit ratio, Economic return to labor</p> <p>b. Stability, resilience and reliability</p> <p>Indicators: Nutrient balances, Erosion levels, Biophysical characteristics of soils, yield trends, Number of species grown, income per species, Pest incidence, Diseases and weeds, Variation of input and output prices</p> <p>c. Adaptability</p> <p>Indicators: Adoption of new alternatives and/or farmers' permanence within a system, Capacity building activities, Proportion of area with an adopted technology.</p> <p>d. Equity</p> <p>Indicators: Initial investment costs, Share of benefits by different farmer groups</p> <p>e. Self-reliance</p>	<p>Farmers, development workers, researchers, decision makers</p>

	<p>Indicators: Participation in the design/implementation and evaluation of alternatives, degree of participation in the decision-making process, Cost of external inputs, and Use of external resources</p>	
<p>SOCLA Framework [106]</p>	<p>a. Soil quality</p> <p>Indicators: Structure, Compaction, Soil depth, Status of residues, Color, odor, and organic matter, Water retention, Soil cover, Erosion, Presence of invertebrates, Microbial activity.</p> <p>b. Crop health</p> <p>Indicators: Appearance, Crop growth, Disease incidence, Insect pest incidence, Natural enemy abundance and diversity, Weed competition and pressure, Actual or potential yield, Vegetation diversity, Natural surrounding vegetation, and Management system.</p>	<p>Farmers</p>
<p>OASIS (Original agroecological Survey Indicator Systems) [4]</p>	<p>a. Agroecological practices</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. <i>Crops</i> (Use of agroecological soil tillage techniques, Soil fertility management, crop pest management, Crop disease management, Weed management, Maximization of soil cover, Use of plant reproductive material adapted to low input systems) ii. <i>Animals and grasslands</i> (High level of animal welfare, livestock management, grassland management) iii. <i>Natural Resources and Agroforestry</i> (Efficient water management, Favorable microclimate management, High level of adoption of agroforestry) <p>b. Economic viability</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Productions costs (Minimized variable costs, Minimized fixed costs-investments) ii. Revenue (High proportion of quality enhancement product valorization practices, High proportion of locally or self-processed products, Short marketing chain, Local marketing chain, High level of diversification of activities) iii. Income (Satisfaction with economic benefits from farming activities, Similar or higher benefits compared to other farmers) <p>c. Socio-political aspects</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Labour conditions and job creation (Human and safe working conditions, Fair wages, high job stability, solid provision of social protection, High level of gender equity, Large comparative contribution to job creation, High ratio of employment of people at risk of poverty and social exclusion). ii. Cooperation and Networks (Substantial and continuous participation in networks, collectives, and organizations, Substantial and continuous participation in social and solidarity economy, Substantial and 	<p>Farmers</p>

	<p>continuous advocacy and education on agroecology, Transparent communication, and high level of accountability).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> iii. Local culture and knowledge (Substantial use and promotion of traditional local seeds and heritage breeds, Strong involvement in preservation of traditional foods) iv. Quality of life (satisfactory work levels, Low-stress work environment, Sufficient time for family and social relationships, Sufficient time for knowledge and new skills, Finding work meaningful, Good level of self-consumption of food products) v. Farm viability (Farmers optimistic perspective on farm’s future, Young farmer or presence/high chances of successor) <p>d. Environment and biodiversity</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Environmental impact (Minimal pollution, Soil carbon budget optimization, Soil erosion minimization, Soil salinization minimization, Soil compaction) ii. Biodiversity impact (Maximization of ecological networks, High nature value farming (HNVf), Maximization of agro biodiversity) <p>e. Resilience</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Climate resilience (Maximization of soil cover, Efficient water management, Favorable microclimate management, Soil carbon budget optimization, Maximal use of stress-tolerant species, breeds, and cultivars. ii. Economic resilience (High level of diversification of activities, Short and local food marketing chains, High level of diversification of products, High level of diversification of clients, Good temporal distribution of revenue, Low share of subsidies in gross farm income, Ability to attract and keep motivated workforce, High level of autonomy from commercial inputs). 	
<p>SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment) [107]</p>	<p>Environmental pillar</p> <p>Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Air <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Supply of quality air function (Air quality is maintained or enhanced, ii) Air flow buffering function (Wind speed is adequately buffered) b. Soil <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Supply of soil function (Soil loss is minimized) ii) Supply of quality soil function (Soil chemical and physical quality is maintained) iii) Soil flow buffering function (Soil mass flux, i.e., mudflows, and landslides are adequately buffered) c. Water 	<p>Farmers</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Supply of water function (Adequate amount of water, soil moisture and groundwater is supplied). ii) Supply of quality water function (Surface water, soil water, and groundwater of adequate quality is supplied). iii) Water flow buffering function (Flooding and runoff regulation of the agroecosystem is maintained) <p>d. Energy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Supply of energy function (Adequate amount of energy is supplied) ii) Energy flow buffering function (Energy flow is adequately buffered) <p>e. Biodiversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Supply of biotic resource function (Planned biodiversity, Functional and heritage part of spontaneous biodiversity are maintained) ii) Supply of habitat function (Diversity of habitats, Functional quality of habitats and Flow of biotic resources is adequately maintained) <p>Economic pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Viability, i.e. economic function (Farm income is ensured, Dependency on direct and indirect subsidies is minimized, Dependency on external finance is optimal, Agricultural activities are technically efficient, Market activities are optimal, Farmer’s professional training is optimal, Intergenerational continuation of farming activity is ensured, Land tenure arrangements are optimal, Adaptability of the farm is sufficient) <p>Social pillar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Food security and safety, i.e., Production function (Production capacity is compatible with society’s demand for food, Quality of food and raw materials is increased, Adequate amount of agricultural land is maintained) b) Quality of life (Physical well-being of the farming community function (Labor conditions are optimal, Health of the farming community is acceptable) c) Physiological well-being of the farming, i.e., community function (Education of farmers and farm workers is optimal, Internal family situation including equality in the man-woman relation is acceptable, Family access to use of social infrastructures and services and participation in local activities is acceptable, Family integration in the local and agricultural society is acceptable, Farmers feeling of independence is satisfactory) d) Social acceptability, i.e., well-being of society function (Amenities are maintained or increased, pollution levels are reduced, Production methods are acceptable, Quality and taste of food is increased, Equity and stakeholder involvement is maintained or increased. e) Cultural acceptability, i.e., Information function (Educational and scientific value characteristics are maintained or increased, Cultural, spiritual and aesthetic heritage value features are maintained or increased) 	
<p>SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems) [108]</p>	<p>Good governance</p> <p>Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Corporate ethics (Mission explicitness, Mission driven, Due diligence) 	<p>Agriculturalists, foresters, fisherman, harvesters, input suppliers, processors, traders,</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Accountability (Holistic audits, Responsibility, Transparency) c. Participation (Stakeholder identification, stakeholder engagement, Engagement barriers, Effective participation, Grievance procedure, Conflict resolution) d. Rule of law (Legitimacy, Remedy, restoration and prevention, Civic Responsibility, Free, prior and informed consent, Tenure rights) e. Holistic management (Sustainability management plan, Full-cost accounting) <p>Environmental integrity</p> <p>Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Atmosphere (GHG reduction target, GHG mitigation practices, GHG balance, Air pollution reduction target, Air pollution prevention practices, Ambient Concentration of air pollutants) b. Water (Water conservation target, Water conservation practices, Ground and service water withdrawals, Clean water target, Water pollution prevention practices, Concentration of water pollutants, Wastewater quality). c. Land (Soil-improvement practices, Soil physical structure, Soil chemical quality, Soil biological quality, Soil organic matter, Land conservation and rehabilitation plan, Land conservation and rehabilitation practices, Net loss/gain of productive land) d. Biodiversity (Landscape/Marine habitat conservation plan, Ecosystem-enhancing practices, Structural diversity of ecosystems, Ecosystem connectivity, Land-use and land-cover change, Species conservation target, Species conservation practices, Diversity and abundance of key species, Diversity of production, Wild genetic diversity enhancing practices, Agro-biodiversity in-situ conservation, Locally adapted varieties/breeds, Genetic diversity in wild species, Saving of seeds and breeds) e. Materials and Energy (Material consumption practices, Nutrient balances, Renewable and recycled materials, Intensity of material use), Renewable energy use target, Energy-Saving practices, Energy consumption, Renewable energies, Waste reduction target, Waste reduction practices, Waste disposal, Food loss and waste reduction) f. Animal welfare (Animal health practices, Animal health, Humane animal handling practices, Appropriate animal husbandry, Freedom from stress) <p>Economic Resilience</p> <p>Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Investment (Internal investment, Community investment, Long term profitability, Business plan, Net income, Cost of production, Price determination). 	<p>wholesalers, retailers, and pastoralists</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Vulnerability (Guarantee of production levels, Product diversification, Procurement channels, Stability of supplier relationships, Dependence on the leading supplier, Stability of market, Net cash flow, Safety nets, Risk management) c. Product quality and information (Control measures, Hazardous Pesticides, Food contamination, Food quality, Product labeling, Traceability system, Certified production). d. Local economy (Regional workforce, Fiscal commitment, Local Procurement) <p>Social well-being</p> <p>Indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Decent livelihood (Right quality of life, Wage level, Capacity development, Fair access to Means of production) b. Fair Trading practices (Fair pricing and transparent contracts, Rights of suppliers) c. Labor rights (Employment relations, Forced labor, Child labor, Freedom of association and right to bargaining) d. Equity (Nondiscrimination, Gender equality, Support to vulnerable people) e. Human safety and health (Safety and health training, Safety of workplace, operations and facilities, Health coverage and access to medical care, Public Health) f. Cultural diversity (Indigenous knowledge, Food sovereignty) 	
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6.2 Socio-economic and environmental sustainability of the indicator frameworks

TABLE 3: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS BASED ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Name of the Indicator Framework included	socio-economic viability	Environmental sustainability
Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework [101]	<p>This framework addresses the dual facets of social and economic sustainability. The social dimension encompasses crucial aspects pertaining to the socio-economic landscape in East Africa (E.A). These aspects encompass equitable relationships between genders, various social groups, the level of collective engagement, and the capacity to resolve conflicts linked to the management of agricultural and natural resources.</p> <p>On the economic front, the emphasis is on ensuring agricultural viability and optimizing returns on production factors, namely land, labor, and capital. Moreover, within the economic sphere, we also consider key metrics related to output efficiency, such as the efficient utilization of water and nutrients.</p>	<p>The framework places its primary focus on the critical natural resource base that underpins agriculture, encompassing elements such as soil, water, and air. It also considers the environmental services directly influenced by agricultural practices, including factors like habitat preservation, soil water retention capacity, and the preservation of biodiversity. Furthermore, the framework assesses the extent of pollution stemming from agricultural activities, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental impact of agricultural practices.</p>
A Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) framework [15]	<p>The proposed framework addresses the social component by focusing on two key indicators: women's empowerment and youth employment. Women play a vital role in ensuring family food security, promoting dietary diversity, enhancing overall health outcomes, and contributing to the sustainable utilization and conservation of biological diversity. Additionally, their involvement is instrumental in the development of resilient livelihoods and the transformation of food systems.</p> <p>In the context of youth employment, rural areas often grapple with significant unemployment challenges. Agroecology emerges as a promising solution, offering opportunities for the creation of quality jobs for the youth population.</p> <p>Furthermore, the framework also encompasses the economic dimension, which is predominantly driven by profitability. This profitability metric gauges the net income that producers can derive from their farming operations in relation to their investments in land, labor, and other assets. The inclusion of economic performance indicators, particularly profitability, is intended to facilitate informed decision-making at both the micro and macro-economic levels.</p>	<p>The framework incorporates two crucial indicators within the realm of environmental sustainability: Agricultural biodiversity and soil health. The assessment of agricultural biodiversity draws from the sub-indicators 8.1, 8.6, and 8.7 of SDG indicator 2.4.1 (FAO, 2018), relying on the compilation of comprehensive inventories encompassing all species, varieties, and breeds utilized in agricultural practices.</p> <p>In addition, the framework attaches significant importance to soil health, considering factors such as soil structure, residue status, and degree of compaction.</p>
The five-dimensional SF Presidia framework [103]	<p>The methodology employed by the SF presidia offers a strategic pathway for farmers to not only sustain their presence on the land but also to reassert a degree of influence and control over their productive relationships. In doing so, the framework effectively fulfills its social objectives, which are centered around empowering farmers and promoting their well-being.</p>	<p>In each Presidia production protocol, producers are required to adhere to certain guidelines aimed at promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly practices. These guidelines include avoiding or minimizing the use of chemical treatments, prioritizing animal welfare in animal husbandry practices, and</p>

	<p>Within the framework's overarching goals, achieving an optimal equilibrium between producers and consumers is a key aspiration. To realize this goal, the framework actively fosters the formation of alliances among producers. These alliances serve as a means to consolidate market power, thereby enabling producers to negotiate better terms and conditions, and ultimately ensuring a fairer and more balanced relationship between producers and consumers.</p>	<p>actively safeguarding local breeds and vegetable varieties whenever feasible. Furthermore, the protocols emphasize the adoption of breeds and varieties that are well-suited to the local environment. This approach serves to reduce or even eliminate the need for chemicals and excessive water consumption in agricultural practices.</p>
<p>Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development (IDEA) [104]</p>	<p>The framework's primary objective is to evaluate the well-being of farmers and the significance of both market and non-market services they provide to society. In the context of economic viability, the framework employs three essential criteria:</p> <p>Economic Independence: This criterion ensures that farming systems have the capacity to invest in their operations, securing their medium-term sustainability. Economic independence is pivotal for reducing reliance on public subsidies and enhancing resilience in production systems.</p> <p>Transferability: This factor focuses on the long-term sustainability of farming operations by examining their ability to be passed down from one generation to the next. It assesses the continuity and intergenerational sustainability of the production systems.</p> <p>Production Process Efficiency (Autonomy): This criterion evaluates the capacity of production systems to optimize the utilization of their own resources as inputs. It emphasizes the importance of self-sufficiency and autonomy in resource management within agricultural systems, promoting efficiency in the production process.</p>	<p>The environmental indicators within the framework serve as a means to assess the degree of autonomy exhibited by farms in their utilization of non-renewable energy and materials, as well as their propensity to generate pollution as a result of their agricultural activities. These indicators provide valuable insights into the sustainability and environmental impact of farming practices, helping to identify areas where improvements can be made to reduce resource consumption and mitigate pollution.</p>
<p>MESMIS Framework [105]</p>	<p>The framework has been carefully crafted to attain elevated levels of productivity by fostering the efficient and synergistic utilization of both natural and economic resources. It emphasizes the optimization of resource management to enhance agricultural output while minimizing waste.</p> <p>Furthermore, the framework incorporates a flexible approach that can adapt to evolving economic and biophysical conditions. It accommodates innovation and embraces continuous learning processes, allowing for the integration of novel techniques and technologies. Additionally, it promotes the use of diverse strategic options to ensure resilience and adaptability in the face of changing circumstances. This adaptability is a key feature of the methodology, enabling it to remain effective and relevant in dynamic agricultural contexts.</p>	<p>The framework is designed to maintain a consistent, dependable, and resilient production system over time, safeguarding access to and availability of production assets. It actively promotes the sustainable and renewable use, restoration, and conservation of local resources, ensuring their long-term viability.</p> <p>Furthermore, the approach emphasizes the integration of appropriate temporal and spatial diversity within the natural environment to harmonize with economic activities. This integration not only enhances environmental sustainability but also contributes to the overall resilience of the production system.</p>

		Moreover, the approach incorporates mechanisms for risk prevention and reduction, further enhancing its ability to adapt to and mitigate potential challenges and disruptions
SOCLA Framework [106]	The framework uses an amoeba-type graph to provide a visual means to assess indicators related to soil quality and crop health. This graphical representation allows for a clear visualization of the overall status of the system. As the amoeba approaches the full diameter length of the circle, it indicates a higher level of sustainability within the system. The amoeba graph effectively highlights weak indicators, enabling farmers to prioritize necessary agroecological interventions to address deficiencies in soil, crop, or system health.	The framework operates on the assumption that agroecosystems managed with diversity in mind, characterized by low external input usage, and featuring diverse vegetation margins, are poised to reap the advantages of biodiversity synergies. Consequently, these agroecosystems are expected to demonstrate a higher level of sustainability, as the interplay of various species and ecological components contributes to ecological balance and resilience within the agricultural landscape.
OASIS (Original agroecological Survey Indicator Systems) [4]	The framework encompasses socio-economic aspects that encompass labor conditions, job creation, cooperation and networks, local culture and knowledge, as well as the quality of life and farm viability. These factors collectively contribute to the social and economic well-being of the agricultural system. Moreover, the framework incorporates mechanisms for communicating food quality. This involves the use of certifications, labels, and quality schemes to convey information about the quality and attributes of food products. Additionally, it places a strong emphasis on creating a safe working environment free of toxic chemicals. It strives to ensure that workers not only feel secure but also receive fair compensation for their labor, aligning with principles of social equity and worker welfare. Furthermore, it seeks to gauge whether farmers perceive that they are receiving fair prices for their products and how their income relates to their perceived standing within the community. This aspect addresses the economic aspects of farmer well-being and their role within the broader societal context.	This Framework takes into account the broader ecosystem impacts stemming from farming practices. It operates on the fundamental principle that an agroecological farm's objective should be to actively contribute to the enhancement of the resources it interacts with. In line with this principle, it leverages High Nature Value (HNV) farmland, which contains a significant proportion of semi-natural vegetation, to create a landscape that is highly permeable to various species. This approach facilitates the movement of individual organisms, fostering greater connectivity within the habitat. Additionally, the framework underscores the significance of establishing ecological networks. These networks play a vital role in enhancing habitat connectivity and supporting the natural migration patterns of diverse species.
SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment) [107]	The framework comprehensively addresses the fundamental economic pillars, including maintenance, production, product processing, marketing, and financial activities. These pillars collectively aim to achieve both allocative and technical efficiency, with a focus on minimizing the inappropriate use of inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, animal feed, energy, water, mechanical work, building, labor, land, and information. Additionally, the framework strives to reduce the reliance on external financial support, including credit and subsidies, which can hinder innovation and self-sufficiency within the agricultural system. Under the domain of social viability, the approach places a strong emphasis on ensuring that farming activities are conducted while respecting the quality of life of the farmer and their family. This includes considerations of labor conditions	In SAFE (Sustainable Agriculture, Food, and Environment), the framework thoughtfully addresses the two key environmental aspects within agroecosystems: a) The Supply Function: This aspect is concerned with ensuring a consistent and sufficient supply of various resources, both in terms of quantity and quality, to support the needs of living organisms within the agroecosystem. This encompasses critical resources such as water, nutrients, and habitat for organisms, emphasizing their availability and suitability for sustaining life. b) The Buffer Function: The framework also takes into account the role of agroecosystems in mitigating and reducing the

	and health, promoting a holistic approach that encompasses the well-being of those engaged in agricultural practices.	potentially damaging impacts of environmental fluxes. This includes factors like radiation, water, and wind. By altering these environmental fluxes to a degree that diminishes their harmful effects on the agroecosystem, the buffer function aims to enhance the overall resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems.
SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems) [108]	<p>Within the SAFA framework, the subthemes pertaining to social well-being encompass various critical aspects. These include decent livelihoods, fair trading practices, labor rights, equity, human health and safety, and cultural diversity. These elements are central to the social sustainability domain, as they contribute to fulfilling basic human needs and ensuring individuals have the right and freedom to pursue their aspirations within the agricultural context.</p> <p>SAFA's emphasis lies more on economic resilience rather than solely on economic development. Under the subthemes associated with economic resilience, SAFA strives to ensure that agroecological systems maintain their economic sustainability. This involves their ability to meet financial obligations, generate positive cash flows, account for any negative externalities they may produce, and provide fair compensation to workers and shareholders. Additionally, it addresses the importance of establishing buffer mechanisms, such as savings and assets, to effectively cope with unforeseen changes and external shocks that may be beyond the control of the agroecological system.</p>	SAFA effectively tackles the preservation of environmental integrity by encompassing a range of sustainability themes. These themes, which include Biodiversity, Animal welfare, Atmosphere, Land, Water, Materials, and Energy, play a pivotal role in sustaining life support systems essential for human survival. The framework is designed to minimize adverse environmental impacts and promote positive contributions to ecological well-being, thus fostering a more sustainable and harmonious coexistence between agriculture and the environment.

6.3 AE Framework Applicability and Practicality

TABLE 4: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS BASED ON THEIR APPLICABILITY AND PRACTICALITY

Name of the Indicator Framework included	AE Applicability	AE Practicality
Sustainable Intensification Assessment Framework [101]	The framework was conceived with the primary aim of enhancing researchers' capacity to comprehensively evaluate the impact of an innovation, considering both the direct and indirect consequences across various domains. Consequently, it serves as a valuable conceptual tool that provides insights into the intricate dynamics of complex systems, rather than being limited to a static label or definition.	<p>Collecting the complete set of data for a full SI indicator can indeed be a time-intensive process. However, the framework addresses this challenge by relying on proxy indicators in situations where direct measurements are unavailable or prohibitively expensive. This pragmatic approach makes the framework adaptable and cost-effective for use in various contexts.</p> <p>Given that the framework was primarily developed with smallholder farming contexts in mind, it is well-suited for application in East Africa. Smallholder farming forms the foundation of food production in the region, and changes in agricultural practices can</p>

	<p>Moreover, the SI indicators featured in the framework can also prove instrumental in guiding monitoring and evaluation endeavors within development projects. These indicators offer a structured approach to assessing the social impact and effectiveness of innovative solutions, facilitating more informed decision-making and the continuous improvement of development initiatives.</p>	<p>significantly impact development goals, including poverty alleviation, increased food and nutrition security, and the promotion of equity across gender, age, and class. Therefore, the framework's flexibility and relevance make it a valuable tool for addressing the specific challenges and opportunities within the East African agricultural landscape.</p>
<p>A Tool for Agro-ecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) framework [15]</p>	<p>This tool has been crafted to serve as a framework for governments and public actors. Its purpose is to aid in the adaptation and re-design of research and development programs, as well as the evaluation of policies, rural advisory services, and extension programs. The overarching goal is to ensure that these initiatives are appropriately aligned with the principles of sustainable agriculture within the context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).</p>	<p>The tool has been deliberately designed to maintain simplicity and minimize the need for extensive training and data collection. Its user-friendly nature ensures that it can be applied effectively with minimal resource and time investment. Moreover, the method's versatility is evident in its applicability to various levels of analysis. It can be adapted to evaluate different geographic areas, which may include municipalities, watersheds, provinces, regions, or other defined regions. When faced with budget or time constraints, the method accommodates a random exclusion/inclusion approach for surveying observation units after determining the appropriate sample size. Preliminary results from pilot studies have underscored the tool's adaptability, demonstrating its suitability for application in diverse geographic regions and across various agroecosystems. Furthermore, these studies have shown that the method enables assessments of performance across a wide range of criteria, extending beyond traditional indicators. In doing so, it contributes to the development of a comprehensive evidence base for agroecology and supports the transformation towards sustainable agricultural production and food systems.</p>
<p>The five-dimensional SF Presidia framework [103]</p>	<p>The tool takes a holistic approach by monitoring various dimensions of sustainability, including economic, ecological, social, and cultural aspects, in addition to quality. Its primary purpose is to assess the sustainability of small-scale and local agro-food systems comprehensively. By examining these multiple dimensions, the tool assists growers in enhancing the sustainability of their products while ensuring that quality standards are met. This integrated approach empowers growers to make informed decisions and improvements that positively impact their products and the broader agro-food systems they are a part of.</p>	<p>The framework offers a truly integrated perspective on sustainability within small-scale systems. By considering a comprehensive range of criteria and utilizing sustainability indicators, it provides a holistic view that encompasses economic, ecological, social, and cultural dimensions, promoting a well-rounded assessment of sustainability.</p>
<p>Indicators of Sustainable Farm Development (IDEA) [104]</p>	<p>The framework is intentionally developed as a self-assessment tool, serving not only farmers but also policy makers, to promote and support sustainable agriculture. The IDEA method is particularly valuable for making meaningful comparisons between farms that share the same type of production and operate within similar local contexts, including factors like soil and climate conditions. This approach provides a reliable means of gauging variations in farm situations and management practices, making it capable of pinpointing significant disparities in sustainability among farms situated within the same small farming region and operating under similar production systems. This capacity</p>	<p>The framework builds upon the adaptation of sustainability indicators from the IDEA method, with a focus on analyzing the sustainability of major types of farming in France. This foundational work can serve as a valuable model for extending the framework's application to the East African region. By adapting the indicators to suit the specific conditions and contexts of individual countries within East Africa, the framework can be effectively customized to assess and promote sustainability within the diverse agricultural landscapes of the region. This adaptability allows for a tailored approach that addresses the unique challenges and opportunities presented by East African farming systems.</p>

	for precise differentiation underscores the framework's utility in both individual farm self-assessment and broader policy-making initiatives geared towards sustainable agriculture.	
MESMIS Framework [105]	<p>The framework holds particular significance within the context of peasant Natural Resource Management Systems (NRMS). These systems, while diverse and resilient, often rely on the sustainable utilization of local natural resources. Unfortunately, they have historically been deprioritized, primarily because prevailing criteria and indicators have placed excessive emphasis on short-term economic gains.</p> <p>Furthermore, the framework finds its primary application in family-based agricultural systems, placing a strong emphasis on activities grounded in ecological principles. This orientation aligns with the sustainable management of natural resources and ecological balance.</p> <p>Additionally, the framework is adaptable and facilitates the conduction of agricultural sustainability assessments across various socio-ecological contexts. It does so through a long-term, participatory, interdisciplinary, and multi-institutional approach, ensuring that sustainability evaluations are comprehensive and inclusive of diverse perspectives and stakeholders.</p>	<p>The framework's applicability to peasant agriculture is particularly noteworthy, as peasant agriculture serves as the primary source of staple food in East Africa, sustaining the livelihoods of a significant portion of the population. Given the critical role of peasant agriculture in the region, the framework's adaptability and relevance to this context make it a valuable tool for assessing and enhancing the sustainability of smallholder farming systems. It can aid in improving agricultural practices, promoting food security, and supporting the well-being of the local communities that depend on these systems for their livelihoods and sustenance.</p>
SOCLA Framework [106]	<p>The framework's applicability extends beyond its specific origins in California. While the indicators may have been initially developed with a focus on agro ecosystems in California, they can indeed be adapted and applied to a broader range of ecosystems, including those in East Africa. This adaptability highlights the framework's versatility and underscores its potential as a valuable tool for assessing soil quality and crop health in diverse agricultural and ecological contexts.</p>	<p>The framework is specifically designed to facilitate the development of agroecosystems that exhibit several key characteristics, including high resilience to pests and diseases, effective recycling and nutrient retention capacity, and elevated levels of biodiversity. These attributes collectively contribute to the ecological sustainability of the agroecosystem.</p> <p>One of the notable strengths of the SOCLA framework is its ability to generate measurements that are comparable over time. This feature enables the tracking of changes within the same agroecosystem over a timeline or facilitates comparisons between farms at different stages of transition towards sustainability.</p> <p>Furthermore, the framework provides individual farmers with a valuable tool for assessing the conditions of their farms. By visualizing soil and plant attributes and comparing them against predefined thresholds, farmers gain insights into areas where their farms excel or where improvements are needed. This enables farmers to make informed decisions about enhancing the ecological performance of their farms and to understand the factors that contribute to variations in ecological performance among different farms.</p>
OASIS (Original agroecological Survey Indicator Systems) [4]	<p>The methodology has demonstrated its robustness by being applicable across a diverse array of farms and contexts, consistently delivering reliable results. Simultaneously, it allows for the efficient training of evaluators within a reasonable time frame. This dual capability makes the framework a practical and effective tool for assessing and improving</p>	<p>The development of the OASIS framework was guided by several methodological principles, one of which is the efficient and timely evaluation of agroecosystems. OASIS was designed to collect sufficient data within a relatively short timeframe, ensuring that the assessment process is both efficient and effective.</p> <p>Another key principle was cost-effectiveness. The framework was intentionally designed to be affordable and accessible to various stakeholders, making it suitable for large-scale</p>

	agricultural sustainability in various settings while ensuring that evaluators can acquire the necessary skills efficiently.	evaluations. The data gathering process in OASIS primarily relies on interviews with farmers and farm workers, supplemented by transect walks. This approach minimizes the need for expensive laboratory tests and complex analyses, further contributing to its cost-effectiveness and widespread applicability.
SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment) [107]	<p>SAFE (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture) offers a unique amalgamation of advantages from both system-based and content-based frameworks. By scrutinizing the agroecosystem as a whole, it ensures its applicability in assessing sustainability universally. Simultaneously, it employs a content-based approach by defining specific functions or attributes for various components within the system, facilitating quantification and a more nuanced analysis.</p> <p>Moreover, SAFE operates effectively across three distinct spatial scales, encompassing the field, farm, and landscape/administrative unit. This scalability allows for a comprehensive assessment of sustainability at various levels, providing valuable insights for decision-makers and stakeholders.</p> <p>The framework employs a systematic, step-by-step approach to defining sustainability, supported by a strong theoretical foundation for each concept. This robust theoretical basis ensures the broad applicability of the system, making it accessible and useful for diverse stakeholders, including farmers, advisors, researchers, and decision-makers.</p>	<p>The efficiency of the framework is further enhanced by its use of a limited number of indicators, which effectively cover the three most critical dimensions of sustainability: social, economic, and environmental. This streamlined approach significantly reduces the time required for data collection and processing. Simultaneously, it contributes to cost savings, making the framework a practical and accessible tool for assessing and promoting sustainability within agricultural systems.</p>
SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems) [108]	<p>SAFA offers wide-ranging applicability across all entities within supply chains. It encompasses enterprises, whether they are large companies or small-scale producers, engaged in primary production, processing, distribution, and marketing of various goods related to agriculture, livestock, fisheries, aquaculture, and forestry. This inclusive approach ensures that sustainability considerations are harmonized across the entire food value chain.</p> <p>The primary aim of SAFA is to promote transparency and good practices by providing a transparent and aggregated framework for sustainability assessment. It primarily serves as a tool for self-evaluation and internal communication on sustainability performance, fostering self-improvement within organizations. Additionally, the SAFA performance report can be used for external communication, facilitating dialogue and understanding on sustainability aspects with other businesses and stakeholders along the supply chain.</p>	<p>SAFA is characterized by its focus on transparency in data collection procedures. While it does not provide specific global data protocols, it mandates transparency regarding the timing, content, and type of data collected. This approach ensures that users of the framework have a clear understanding of the data collection process.</p> <p>It's worth noting that the collection of primary data under SAFA can be comprehensive due to the extensive number of themes, sub-themes, and indicators (21 themes, 58 sub-themes, and 118 indicators). This may require a significant investment of time and resources.</p> <p>To mitigate potential expenses, the framework suggests the use of secondary data when possible. This secondary data should come from reliable sources and be current. Additionally, the framework allows for the use of assumptions, provided they are made by the management or staff directly involved in the enterprise being assessed. These strategies help to reduce data collection costs while maintaining the reliability and integrity of the assessment process.</p>

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Key Findings and Insights

Throughout the comprehensive review, we have delved into the intricate landscape of agroecological practices in East Africa and the diverse range of indicator frameworks used to assess their economic, social, and agro-environmental sustainability. It is evident that East Africa's agricultural systems are profoundly dynamic, shaped by a myriad of influences including socio-economic factors, environmental conditions, and cultural practices. Agroecological approaches in this context have exhibited significant potential in addressing multifaceted challenges, particularly in relation to soil fertility, resource efficiency, and ecosystem resilience.

The frameworks prioritize a holistic and interconnected view of sustainability. They recognize the complex relationships between economic viability, social well-being, and environmental conservation, aligning with the multifaceted nature of East Africa's agricultural systems. The adaptability of frameworks to the diverse agroecosystems in East Africa is a crucial factor. The multi-scale approach and flexibility emerge as particularly relevant, allowing stakeholders to tailor assessments to the unique characteristics of different farming practices, from smallholder subsistence agriculture to larger commercial enterprises.

The significance of economic sustainability and social well-being is highlighted across frameworks. Prioritizing farm income, minimizing external dependency, and improving the quality of life for farming communities are recurring themes. These align with East Africa's goals of enhancing livelihoods and ensuring the well-being of agricultural practitioners. Environmental sustainability is a shared focus among the frameworks, addressing issues such as soil conservation, water management, biodiversity, and greenhouse gas emissions. The emphasis on resource use efficiency, and detailed examination of natural resources, by most frameworks and also SAFA's core pillar of environmental integrity collectively contribute to addressing East Africa's environmental challenges. The role of good governance as an enabling factor for sustainability is acknowledged. SAFA stands out for explicitly incorporating governance principles, emphasizing transparency, adherence to the rule of law, and equitable decision-making. This is particularly relevant in East Africa, where transparent governance mechanisms are critical for sustainable agriculture.

Common challenges across frameworks include the need for robust data and the potential subjectivity of certain indicators, especially in social and governance dimensions. These challenges pose practical considerations for implementation, particularly in regions with limited resources, underlining the importance of capacity building and data improvement initiatives. The flexibility of frameworks emerges as a strength. The ability to customize sustainability indicators to align with specific agroecosystem contexts is crucial in East Africa, where agricultural practices vary widely. The need for continuous updates to reflect evolving sustainability concepts is recognized. Additionally, capacity building efforts are deemed essential, particularly for stakeholders unfamiliar with sustainability assessments, to ensure effective and meaningful use of the frameworks. The key findings emphasize the importance of selecting or adapting frameworks based on their alignment with East Africa's unique agricultural landscape, sustainability goals, and the need for a holistic, adaptive, and transparent approach.

7.2 Recommendations for Utilizing Indicator Frameworks in East Africa

In light of the diverse and dynamic nature of agroecological practices in East Africa, the development and application of indicator frameworks require careful consideration and adaptability. To maximize the effectiveness of these frameworks in assessing economic, social, and agro-environmental sustainability, several key recommendations are proposed.

- a. The unique attributes of each agroecosystem in East Africa necessitate the development of context-specific indicator frameworks. These frameworks should be tailored to the specific agroecological and socio-economic conditions of the region, ensuring that they resonate with local realities. These frameworks can provide more accurate and relevant assessments of sustainability, by accounting for the diversity of agricultural systems in East Africa.
- b. Indicators should not be assessed in isolation. Rather, the interplay of economic, social, and agro-environmental indicators should be considered to capture the holistic dynamics of agroecological systems. Indicator frameworks should facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of these interconnected factors, acknowledging that changes in one area can have ripple effects in others.
- c. Enhancing the transparency, credibility, and legitimacy of indicator frameworks is essential. This can be achieved by involving local stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, and non-governmental organizations, in the design and implementation of these frameworks. Transparent processes that incorporate local knowledge and values will result in more relevant and widely accepted sustainability assessments.
- d. Building the capacity of local researchers and communities to understand and utilize indicator frameworks is crucial. Training programs and workshops should be organized to empower local stakeholders with the knowledge and skills necessary to interpret and apply these frameworks effectively. This will enable the active participation of communities in the assessment and improvement of agroecological practices.
- e. The paucity of long-term data on various variables within East African agroecosystems remains a significant challenge. Efforts should be made to establish data collection systems that provide reliable, long-term information on sustainability indicators. This will require investments in data infrastructure and coordination among various stakeholders to ensure the availability of accurate and up-to-date information.
- f. Sustainability assessments should be conducted at multiple levels, considering not only the household but also the community, district, and regional scales. Agroecological systems often exhibit intricate dynamics that transcend traditional boundaries. By assessing sustainability at various levels, a more comprehensive understanding of these systems can be achieved.
- g. Embracing innovation and adaptation is fundamental. Encouraging farmers' innovation and experimentation with agroecological practices that suit their specific circumstances is vital. Researchers should actively support these processes by developing tools and knowledge that enable farmers to explore and implement novel farm systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Behnassi *et al.*, “Enhancing resilience for food and nutrition security within a changing climate,” *Emerg. Challenges to Food Prod. Secur. Asia, Middle East, Africa Clim. Risks Resour. Scarcity*, pp. 1–42, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-72987-5_1.
- [2] M. Antar, D. Lyu, M. Nazari, A. Shah., “Biomass for a sustainable bioeconomy: An overview of world biomass production and utilization,” *Elsevier*, 2021, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032120309758>
- [3] M. Bosco, “Use of improved methods of crop farming and livelihoods of small holder farmers in Luuka district,” 2022, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://kyuspace.kyu.ac.ug/handle/20.500.12504/1176>
- [4] W. A. and M. P. Peeters A., Škorjanc K., “OASIS, the Original Agroecological Survey Indicator System. A simple and comprehensive system for agroecological transition assessment. Agroecology Europe, Brussels: 82 pages - Google Search,” 2021, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.google.com/search?q=Peeters+A.%252C+Škorjanc+K.%252C+Wezel+A.+and+Migliorini+P.%252C+2021.+OASIS%252C+the+Original+Agroecological+Survey+Indicator+System.+A+simple+and+comprehensive+system+for+agroecological+transition+assessment.+Agroecology+Europe%252>
- [5] N. Cojan, “The implications ‘global objectives’ implementation has on Romania’s economic security,” *Bull. “Carol I” Natl. Def. Univ.*, 2022, doi: 10.53477/2284-9378-22-87.
- [6] R. Bezner-Kerr, J. Liebert, M. Kansanga, and D. Kpienbaareh, “Human and social values in agroecology: A review,” *online.ucpress.edu R Bezner Kerr, J Liebert, M Kansanga, D Kpienbaareh Elem Sci Anth, 2022*•*online.ucpress.edu*, 2020, doi: 10.1525/elementa.2021.00090.
- [7] M. Leippert, F., Darmaun, M., Bernoux, M., Mpheshea, M., Müller, A., Geck, M., Herren, M., Irungu, W., Nyasimi, M., Sene, J.M. and Sow, “The potential of agroecology to build climate-resilient livelihoods and food systems,” *potential Agroecol. to build Clim. livelihoods food Syst.*, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.4060/CB0438EN.
- [8] F. Ratto *et al.*, “Biological control interventions and botanical pesticides for insect pests of crops in sub-Saharan Africa: A mapping review,” *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.*, vol. 6, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3389/FSUFS.2022.883975/FULL.
- [9] A. Ayantunde, J. De Leeuw, M. Turner, M. S.-L. Science, and undefined 2011, “Challenges of assessing the sustainability of (agro)-pastoral systems,” *Elsevier*, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1871141311001028>
- [10] J. Ojiem, N. De Ridder, ... B. V.-I. J. of, and undefined 2006, “Socio-ecological niche: a conceptual framework for integration of legumes in smallholder farming systems,” *Taylor Fr. Ojiem, N Ridder, B Vanlauwe, KE Giller/International J. Agric. Sustain. 2006*•*Taylor Fr.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 79–93, 2006, doi: 10.1080/14735903.2006.9686011.
- [11] E. Isgren and B. Ness, “Agroecology to promote just sustainability transitions: Analysis of a civil society network in the Rwenzori Region, Western Uganda,” *mdpi.com E Isgren, B Ness Sustainability, 2017*•*mdpi.com*, 2017, doi: 10.3390/su9081357.
- [12] M. Benegiamo and N. Borrelli, “The challenges and potential of small farmers in driving an agroecological food system transition. A study of collective grassroots actions in Gilgil, Kenya,” *Rass. Ital. Sociol.*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 563–589, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1423/98561.
- [13] P. Tittonell, E. Scopel, N. Andrieu, ... H. P.-F. C., and undefined 2012, “Agroecology-based aggradation-conservation agriculture (ABACO): Targeting innovations to combat soil degradation and food insecurity in semi-arid Africa,” *Elsevier*, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378429011004151>
- [14] S. Bakalis, V. Valdramidis, ... D. A.-C. R. in, and U. 2020, “Perspectives from CO+ RE: How COVID-19 changed our food systems and food security paradigms,” *ncbi.nlm.nih.gov S Bakalis, VP Vald. D Argyropoulos, L Ahrne, J Chen, PJ Cullen, E Cummins Current Res. Food Sci. 2020*•*ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*, 2020, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7265867/>

- [15] FAO, "TAPE Tool for Agro ecology Performance." Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=FAO+%282019%29.+TAPE+Tool+for+Agro+ecology+Performance+Evaluation+2019+Process+of+development+and+guidelines+for+application.+Test+version.+Rome.+&btnG=
- [16] P. Chatzinikolaou and B. M.-B. Summer, "Review of existing methodologies and tools for measuring sustainability in rural areas," *Res. Chatzinikolaou, B ManosBelpasso Int. Summer Sch. Environ. Resour. 2012*•*researchgate.net*, 2012, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Kulvir-Singh/post/I_am_developing_research_proposal_on_sustainable_supply_chains_in_case_of_Sudan_do_you_have_any_information_about_role_of_private_sector_here2/attachment/5a5384e9b53d2f0bba49c227/AS%253A580540097101824%25
- [17] M. Resler, S. H.-A.-A. and Sustainable, and undefined 2021, "Augmenting agroecological urbanism: the intersection of food sovereignty and food democracy," *Taylor Fr. Resler, SE Hagolani-AlbovAgroecology Sustain. Food Syst. 2021*•*Taylor Fr.*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 320–343, 2020, doi: 10.1080/21683565.2020.1811829.
- [18] U. Niggli, M. Sonneveld, and S. Kummer, "Pathways to advance agroecology for a successful transformation to sustainable food systems," *agroavances.com*, 2023, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://agroavances.com/img/publicacion_documentos/ScGroup_Reader_UNFSS2021_compressed.pdf#page=400
- [19] U. Adhikari, ... A. N.-F. and E., and undefined 2015, "Climate change and eastern Africa: a review of impact on major crops," *Wiley Online Libr. Adhikari, AP Nejadhashemi, SA WoznickiFood Energy Secur. 2015*•*Wiley Online Libr.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 110–132, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1002/fes3.61.
- [20] P. I. Palmer *et al.*, "Drivers and impacts of Eastern African rainfall variability," *nature.comPI Palmer, C. Wainwright, B Dong, RI Maidment, KG Wheel. N Gedney, JE HickmanNature Rev. Earth Environ. 2023*•*nature.com*, vol. 4, pp. 254–270, 2023, doi: 10.1038/s43017-023-00397-x.
- [21] A. Salami, A. B. Kamara, and Z. Brixiova, *Smallholder agriculture in East Africa: Trends, constraints and opportunities.* 2010. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://docs.igihe.com/IMG/pdf/working_105_pdf_d.pdf
- [22] A. Autio, T. Johansson, L. Motaroki, ... P. M.-A., and U. 2021, "Constraints for adopting climate-smart agricultural practices among smallholder farmers in Southeast Kenya," *Elsevier*, 2021, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308521X21002377>
- [23] K. C. Kamanthe, "Implication Of Household Land Size And Land Use On Sustainable Food And Livelihood Security In A Maize Farming System Of Kalongo Sub-Location, Makueni," 2019, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/107310>
- [24] K. Ngunzo, K. Wanjala, K. W. Mbutia, F. K. Ngunzo, and K. B. Wanjala, "Economic Determinants To Household Food Security In Kyangwithya West Location Of Kitui County," *Res. Ngunzo, KB Wanjalaresearchgate.net*, vol. 5, no. 5, 2017, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Kezia-Mbutia/publication/319905642_Economic_Determinants_to_Household_Food_Security_in_Kyangwithya_West_location_Kitui_County/links/59c114ce458515af305c5237/Economic-Determinants-to-Household-Food-Security-in-Kyangwit
- [25] N. Fengying and F. Chen, "An Analysis of Factors Affecting Smallholder Rice Farmers' Level of Sales and Market Participation in Tanzania; Evidence from National Panel Survey Data," *core.ac.ukNSBN Fengying, F Chencore.ac.uk*, 2014, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234646670.pdf>
- [26] G. Kimaru and B. Jama, "Improving land management in eastern and southern Africa: A review of practices and policies," 2006, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://econpapers.repec.org/paper/rafwpaper/2006113.htm>
- [27] S. Block, C. Peter Timmer, T. Hobgood, E. Simmons, and J. Westley, "Agriculture and economic Growth: Conceptual Issues and the Kenyan Experience," 1994, doi: 10.22004/AG.ECON.294048.
- [28] K. O. Obiero, H. Waidbacher, B. Otieno Nyawanda, J. M. Munguti, J. O. Manyala, and B. Kaunda-Arara, "Predicting uptake of aquaculture technologies among smallholder fish farmers in Kenya," *SpringerKO Obiero*,

- H Waidbacher, BO Nyawanda, JM Munguti, JO Manyala, B Kaunda-Arara *Aquaculture Int.* 2019•Springer, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 1689–1707, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10499-019-00423-0.
- [29] M. Kichawele, “Performance of Semi-Formal Microfinance Institutions in Tanzania: A case study of selected SACCOs and BRAC Tanzania,” 2020, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://nodai.repo.nii.ac.jp/record/820/files/博士%28国際バイオビジネス学%29795 : Msuya Rahel Kichawele.pdf>
- [30] H. A. C. Lohman *et al.*, “Advancing sustainable sanitation and agriculture through investments in human-derived nutrient systems,” *ACS Publ.*, vol. 54, no. 15, pp. 9217–9227, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1021/acs.est.0c03764.
- [31] C. Peacock, A. Jowett, A. Dorward, C. Poulton, and I. Urey, “Reaching the poor: a call to action Investment in smallholder agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa,” 2004, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://eprints.soas.ac.uk/5141>
- [32] V. Pernechele, F. Fontes, R. Baborska, and J. Nkuingoua, *Public expenditure on food and agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa: trends, challenges and priorities.* 2021. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=9nQxEAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR9&dq=Pernechele,+V.,+Fontes,+F.,+Baborska,+R.,+Nkuingoua,+J.,+Pan,+X.,+%26+Tuyishime,+C.+\(2021\).+Public+expenditure+on+food+and+agriculture+in+sub-Saharan+Africa:+trends,+challenges+and+priorities.+Food+%26+Agriculture+Org..&ots=gV2f2eVFun&sig=2vEL3TTnta5z872jQmroboxe4dk](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=9nQxEAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR9&dq=Pernechele,+V.,+Fontes,+F.,+Baborska,+R.,+Nkuingoua,+J.,+Pan,+X.,+%26+Tuyishime,+C.+(2021).+Public+expenditure+on+food+and+agriculture+in+sub-Saharan+Africa:+trends,+challenges+and+priorities.+Food+%26+Agriculture+Org..&ots=gV2f2eVFun&sig=2vEL3TTnta5z872jQmroboxe4dk)
- [33] H. Dos-Santos, “Value addition of agricultural production to meet the sustainable development goals,” *SpringerMJPL Dos-SantosZero Hunger. 2020•Springer*, 2020, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-69626-3_55-1.
- [34] G. Hilson and C. Garforth, “‘Agricultural Poverty’ and the Expansion of Artisanal Mining in Sub-Saharan Africa: Experiences from Southwest Mali and Southeast Ghana,” *Popul. Res. Policy Rev.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 435–464, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1007/S11113-012-9229-6.
- [35] S. V. Of, “Do remittances promote fertilizer use? The case of Ugandan farmers,” *Wiley Online Libr. VeljanoskaAmerican J. Agric. Econ. 2022•Wiley Online Libr.*, vol. 104, no. 1, pp. 273–293, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1111/ajae.12214.
- [36] N. Mbizana and A. Obi, “Identifying Appropriate Paths for Establishing Sustainable Irrigated Crop Based Farming Business on Smallholder Irrigation Schemes: A Case of Ncora,” 2014, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/145042257.pdf>
- [37] UNDP, “Uganda Human Development Report 2007, Rediscovering Agriculture for Human Development, Kampala, Uganda, United Nations Development Programme. - Google Search,” 2007, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://www.google.com/search?q=UNDP+\(2007\)%2C+Uganda+Human+Development+Report+2007%2C+Rediscovering+Agriculture+for+Human+Development%2C+Kampala%2C+Uganda%2C+United+Nations+Development+Programme.&dq=UNDP+\(2007\)%2C+Uganda+Human+Development+Report+2007%2C+R&AWG](https://www.google.com/search?q=UNDP+(2007)%2C+Uganda+Human+Development+Report+2007%2C+Rediscovering+Agriculture+for+Human+Development%2C+Kampala%2C+Uganda%2C+United+Nations+Development+Programme.&dq=UNDP+(2007)%2C+Uganda+Human+Development+Report+2007%2C+R&AWG)
- [38] R&AWG, “Poverty and Human Development Report 2007, Research and Analysis Working Group, United Republic of Tanzania, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. - Google Search.” Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://www.google.com/search?q=R%26AWG-Research+and+Analysis+Working+Group+\(2007\).+Poverty+and+Human+Development+Report+2007%2C+Research+and+Analysis+Working+Group%2C+United+Republic+of+Tanzania%2C+Dar+es+Salaam%2C+Tanzania.&dq=R%26AWG-Research+and+Analy](https://www.google.com/search?q=R%26AWG-Research+and+Analysis+Working+Group+(2007).+Poverty+and+Human+Development+Report+2007%2C+Research+and+Analysis+Working+Group%2C+United+Republic+of+Tanzania%2C+Dar+es+Salaam%2C+Tanzania.&dq=R%26AWG-Research+and+Analy)
- [39] C. O. Dwasi, “Factors influencing adoption of greenhouse farming technology among small scale horticulture farmers in Gem Sub-county, Kenya,” 2017, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/104147>
- [40] B. Shiferaw, J. Hellin, G. M.-F. security, and undefined 2011, “Improving market access and agricultural productivity growth in Africa: what role for producer organizations and collective action institutions?,” *SpringerB Shiferaw, J Hellin, G MurichoFood Secur. 2011•Springer*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 475–489, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s12571-011-0153-0.
- [41] A. Raimi, A. Roopnarain, R. A.-S. African, and U. 2021, “Biofertilizer production in Africa: Current status, factors impeding adoption and strategies for success,” *Elsevier*, 2021, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available:

- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468227621000028>
- [42] S. Staal, A. N. Pratt, M. J.-F. P. W. Paper, and U. 2008, "Dairy development for the resource poor. Part 2: Kenya and Ethiopia. Dairy development case studies," *cgspace.cgiar.org*, 2008, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/handle/10568/1314>
- [43] J. P. Platteau, "Physical infrastructure as a constraint on agricultural growth: The case of sub-Saharan Africa," *Oxford Dev. Stud.*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 189–219, 1996, doi: 10.1080/13600819608424113.
- [44] AfDB/IFAD, "AFDB/IFAD Joint Evaluation of their agricultural operations and policies in Africa, Draft Report, Rome and Tunis, African Development Bank.," 2009, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ioe.ifad.org/en/w/afdb-ifad-joint-evaluation-on-agriculture-and-rural-development-in-africa>
- [45] W. Ntinyari, J. G.-O.-28th-31st M. 2017| S. P. Hotel, and U. 2017, "Post-harvest Losses in Banana Production Value Chain in Meru and Kisii Counties of Kenya: The Role of Socio-Cultural Diversity," *fao.org, Safari Park Hotel. Nairobi, Kenya, 2017*, 2017, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/user_upload/food-loss-reduction/Nairobi_congress/Peer-reviewed_conference_proceedings_-_All_Africa_PH_Congress_and_Exhibition__003_.pdf#page=171
- [46] J. Omiti, D. Otieno, T. Nyanamba, E. M. Cullough, J. M. Omiti, and D. J. Otieno, "Factors influencing the intensity of market participation by smallholder farmers: A case study of rural and peri-urban areas of Kenya," *ageconsearch.umn.eduJM Omi. DJ Otieno, TO Nyanamba, EB McCulloughAfrican J. Agric. Resour. Econ. 2009*•*ageconsearch.umn.edu*, vol. 3, 2009, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/record/56958/>
- [47] W. Amjad *et al.*, "Decentralized solar-powered cooling systems for fresh fruit and vegetables to reduce post-harvest losses in developing regions: a review," *Acad. Amjad, A Munir, F Akram, A Parmar, M Precoppe, F Asghar, F MahmoodClean Energy, 2023*•*academic.oup.com*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 635–653, 2023, doi: 10.1093/ce/zkad015.
- [48] T. Nyakweba, G. Gongera, and I. Asianga, "Physical Proximity and Awareness of Financial Service Access Strategy on Farmers Economic Empowerment in Kenya: A Case of Small Scale Agricultural Tea," *World J. Innov. Res.*, no. 5, pp. 17–23, 2018, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://ir.kabarak.ac.ke/handle/123456789/335>
- [49] S. Benin, B. Y.-R. A. T. and O. Report, and undefined 2012, "Complying with the Maputo Declaration Target: Trends in public agricultural expenditures and implications for pursuit of optimal allocation of public agricultural," *Akad. Benin, B YuReSAKSS Annu. Trends Outlook Report, 2012*•*akademiya2063.org*, 2010, doi: 10.2499/9780896298415.
- [50] C. Recha, "Local and regional variations in conditions for agriculture and food security in Kenya," *AgriFoSe2030*, vol. Report 7, 2018, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://pub.epsilon.slu.se/16590/1/recha_c_w_200121.pdf
- [51] UNDP, "Human Development Report 2001: Making New Technologies Work for Human Development. New York: United Nations Development Programme. - Google Search." Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://www.google.com/search?q=UNDP+\(2001\).+Human+Development+Report+2001%3A+Making+New+Technologies+Work+for+Human+Development.+New+York%3A+United+Nations+Development+Programme.&eq=UNDP+\(2001\).+Human+Development+Report+2001%3A+Making+New+Technologies+Wo](https://www.google.com/search?q=UNDP+(2001).+Human+Development+Report+2001%3A+Making+New+Technologies+Work+for+Human+Development.+New+York%3A+United+Nations+Development+Programme.&eq=UNDP+(2001).+Human+Development+Report+2001%3A+Making+New+Technologies+Wo)
- [52] S. Barrientos, P. Knorringa, ... B. E.-... and P. A., and undefined 2016, "Shifting regional dynamics of global value chains: Implications for economic and social upgrading in African horticulture," *journals.sagepub.comS Barrientos, P Knorringa, B Evers, M Viss. M OpondoEnvironment Plan. A Econ. Space, 2016*•*journals.sagepub.com*, vol. 48, no. 7, pp. 1266–1283, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1177/0308518X15614416.
- [53] J. Nzuma, M. Radeny, ... J. K.-C. W., and U. 2014, "A review of agricultural, food security, food systems and climate change adaptation policies, institutions and actors in East Africa," 2014. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/handle/10568/51716>
- [54] F. Nassiwa, J. Kwonyike, D. K.-I. J. of Weather, and U. 2022, "Government Agricultural Support Programs and Livelihood of Smallholder Vegetable Farmers in Kampala, District Uganda," *tudr.org*, 2022, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://tudr.org/id/eprint/684/>
- [55] O. B. Adekoya, G. E. Ajayi, M. Suhrab, and J. A. Oliyide, "How critical are resource rents, agriculture, growth,

- and renewable energy to environmental degradation in the resource-rich African countries? The role of institutional quality,” *Energy Policy*, vol. 164, p. 112888, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.ENPOL.2022.112888.
- [56] T. Che, T. Kompas, N. V.-C. economic studies, and undefined 2006, “Market reform, incentives and economic development in Vietnamese rice production,” *SpringerTN Che, T Kompas, N VousdenComparative Econ. Stud. 2006•Springer*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 277–301, Jun. 2006, doi: 10.1057/palgrave.ces.8100113.
- [57] H. Amani, “Making agriculture impact on poverty in Tanzania: The case on non-traditional export crops,” *Econ. Soc. Res. Found.*, pp. 1–12, 2005, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: http://www.tanzaniagateway.org/docs/making_agriculture_impact_on_poverty.pdf
- [58] D. Mitchell, “A note on rising food prices,” 2008. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1233058
- [59] M. Wik, P. Pingali, and S. Broca, “Global agricultural performance: past trends and future prospects,” 2008, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/9122>
- [60] B. Oyelaran-Oyeyinka and P. G. Sampath, “Innovation in African Development. Case Studies of Uganda, Tanzania and Kenya. A World Bank Study.,” <http://info.worldbank.org/etools/docs/library>, 2007, 2014, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Padmashree-Gehl-Sampath/publication/42795516_Innovation_in_African_Development_Case_Studies_of_Uganda_Tanzania_and_Kenya_A_World_Bank_Study/links/00b4953ba78ff23be7000000/Innovation-in-African-Development-Case-Studies-
- [61] IFAD, “Soaring Food Prices and the Rural Poor: Feedback from the Field, <http://www.ifad.org/operations/food/food.htm>, accessed on 23/03/2010 - Google Search.” Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://www.google.com/search?q=IFAD+\(2010\)%2C+Soaring+Food+Prices+and+the+Rural+Poor%3A+Feed+back+from+the+Field%2C+http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ifad.org%2Foperations%2Ffood%2Ffood.htm%2C+accesse+d+on+23%2F03%2F2010&oq=IFAD+\(2010\)%2C+Soaring+Food+Prices+and+the+Rural+](https://www.google.com/search?q=IFAD+(2010)%2C+Soaring+Food+Prices+and+the+Rural+Poor%3A+Feed+back+from+the+Field%2C+http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ifad.org%2Foperations%2Ffood%2Ffood.htm%2C+accesse+d+on+23%2F03%2F2010&oq=IFAD+(2010)%2C+Soaring+Food+Prices+and+the+Rural+)
- [62] T. Afifi, R. Govil, P. Sakdapolrak, and K. Warner, *Climate change, vulnerability and human mobility: Perspectives of refugees from the East and Horn of Africa*. 2012. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/download/28925740/East_and_Horn_of_Africa_final_web.pdf
- [63] J. Pender, F. Place, and S. Ehui, “Strategies for sustainable agricultural development in the East African highlands,” 1999, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ageconsearch.umn.edu/record/16061/>
- [64] B. M. Dillon and C. B. Barrett, “Global Oil Prices and Local Food Prices: Evidence from East Africa,” *Am. J. Agric. Econ.*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 154–171, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1093/AJAE/AAV040.
- [65] T. Akinlo, O. A.-B. J. of Economics, and U. 2015, “The impact of volatility of oil price on the economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa,” *Br. J. Econ. Manag. Trade*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 338–349, 2015, doi: 10.9734/BJEMT/2015/12921.
- [66] C. Madramootoo, ... H. F. D. T. journal of the, and undefined 2010, “Irrigation in the context of today’s global food crisis,” *Wiley Online Libr. Madramootoo, H FylesIrrigation Drain. J. Int. 2010•Wiley Online Libr.*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 40–52, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1002/ird.555.
- [67] L. Ngare, O. D.-I. J. of E. E. and, and undefined 2021, “The effect of fuel prices on food prices in Kenya,” *zbw.euLW Ngare, OW DerekInternational J. Energy Econ. Policy, 2021•zbw.eu*, doi: 10.32479/ijeep.10600.
- [68] P. Kristjanson *et al.*, “Are food insecure smallholder households making changes in their farming practices? Evidence from East Africa,” *SpringerP Kristjanson, H Neufeldt, A Gassner, J Mango, FB Kyazze, S Desta, G Sayula, B ThiedeFood Secur. 2012•Springer*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 381–397, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.1007/s12571-012-0194-z.
- [69] A. J. Vanbergen *et al.*, “Transformation of agricultural landscapes in the Anthropocene: Nature’s contributions to people, agriculture and food security,” *Elsevier*, 2020, doi: 10.1016/bs.aecr.2020.08.002.
- [70] B. K. Paul, J. Cj Groot, B. L. Maass, A. M. Notenbaert, M. Herrero, and P. A. Tittonell, “Improved feeding and forages at a crossroads: Farming systems approaches for sustainable livestock development in East Africa,” *journals.sagepub.comBK Paul, JCI Groot, BL Maass, AMO Notenbaert, M Herrero, PA TittonellOutlook Agric. 2020•journals.sagepub.com*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 13–20, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1177/0030727020906170.
- [71] N. Thakur *et al.*, “Host-mediated gene engineering and microbiome-based technology optimization for

- sustainable agriculture and environment,” *SpringerN Thakur, M Nigam, NA Mann, S Gupta, C. Hussain, SK Shukla, AA Shah, R CasiniFunctional Integr. Genomics, 2023•Springer*, vol. 23, no. 1, p. 57, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10142-023-00982-9.
- [72] S. Cordeau, “Conservation agriculture and agroecological weed management,” *Agronomy*, vol. 12, p. 867, 2022, doi: 10.3390/agronomy12040867.
- [73] E. Dupouy and M. Gurinovic, “Sustainable food systems for healthy diets in Europe and Central Asia: Introduction to the special issue,” *Elsevier*, 2020, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306919220301561>
- [74] M. Anderson and M. Rivera-Ferre, “Food system narratives to end hunger: extractive versus regenerative,” *Elsevier*, 2021, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187734352030124X>
- [75] N. Lokuruka M, “Food and nutrition security in east Africa (Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania): Status, challenges and prospects,” *Food Secur. Africa*, 2020, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=2mwtEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA93&dq=Lokuruka,+M.+N.+\(+2020\).+Food+and+nutrition+security+in+east+Africa+\(Kenya,+Uganda+and+Tanzania\):+Status,+challenges+and+prospects.+Food+security+in+Africa.&ots=3Q8cVtkEqD&sig=D6Nly](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=2mwtEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA93&dq=Lokuruka,+M.+N.+(+2020).+Food+and+nutrition+security+in+east+Africa+(Kenya,+Uganda+and+Tanzania):+Status,+challenges+and+prospects.+Food+security+in+Africa.&ots=3Q8cVtkEqD&sig=D6Nly)
- [76] E. Nchanji and C. Lutomia, “COVID-19 challenges to sustainable food production and consumption: Future lessons for food systems in eastern and southern Africa from a gender lens,” *Elsevier*, 2021, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352550921001639>
- [77] J. Komen and D. Wafula, “Authorizing GM crop varieties: policy implications for seed systems in sub-Saharan Africa,” *Agronomy*, vol. 11, no. 1855, 2021, doi: 10.3390/agronomy11091855.
- [78] J. Jacobi *et al.*, “Operationalizing food system resilience: An indicator-based assessment in agroindustrial, smallholder farming, and agroecological contexts in Bolivia and Kenya,” *Elsevier*, 2018, doi: 10.7892/boris.120265.
- [79] A. Mottet *et al.*, “Assessing Transitions to Sustainable Agricultural and Food Systems: A Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE),” *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.*, vol. 4, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3389/FSUFS.2020.579154/FULL.
- [80] C. Leeuwis, B. K. Boogaard, and K. Atta-Krah, “How food systems change (or not): governance implications for system transformation processes,” *Food Secur.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 761–780, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1007/S12571-021-01178-4.
- [81] A. Nguluma *et al.*, “Typology and characteristics of indigenous goats and production systems in different agro-ecological zones of Tanzania,” *SpringerA Nguluma, M Kyallo, GM Tarekegn, R Loina, Z Nziku, S Chenyambuga, R PelleTropical Anim. Heal. Prod. 2022•Springer*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 3, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11250-022-03074-1.
- [82] C. Wickramaratne, S. Jones, C. Lamanna, and M. Geck, “The measure of agroecology: Developing an assessment framework to capture economic, environmental and social impacts of agriculture and food systems,” 2022, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/handle/10568/127566>
- [83] M. Altieri, C. Nicholls, and A. Henao, “Agroecology and the design of climate change-resilient farming systems,” *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 869–890, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s13593-015-0285-2.
- [84] M. Sivakumar, “Climate Change, Agriculture Adaptation, and Sustainability,” *Clim. Resil. Environ. Sustain. Approaches Glob. Lessons Local Challenges*, pp. 87–109, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-0902-2_6.
- [85] M. Altieri and C. Nicholls, “Designing species rich pest suppressive agroecosystems through habitat management,” *Div. Insect Biol. Univ. California, Berkeley*, 2004, doi: 10.2134/agronmonogr43.c4.
- [86] C. Folke *et al.*, “Regime Shifts, Resilience, and Biodiversity in Ecosystem Management,” *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.*, vol. 35, pp. 557–581, Nov. 2004, doi: 10.1146/ANNUREV.ECOLSYS.35.021103.105711.
- [87] M. Kansanga, J. Kangmennaang, ... R. K.-S. S. &, and undefined 2021, “Agroecology and household production diversity and dietary diversity: Evidence from a five-year agroecological intervention in rural Malawi,” *Elsevier*, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277953620307693>
- [88] E. Fraser, A. Dougill, W. Mabee, ... M. R.-J. of environmental, and undefined 2006, “Bottom up and top down:

- Analysis of participatory processes for sustainability indicator identification as a pathway to community empowerment and sustainable,” *Elsevier*, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2005.04.009.
- [89] C. Turcu, “Re-thinking sustainability indicators: local perspectives of urban sustainability,” *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 695–719, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1080/09640568.2012.698984.
- [90] M. Reed, E. Fraser, A. D.-E. economics, and undefined 2006, “An adaptive learning process for developing and applying sustainability indicators with local communities,” *Elsevier*, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.11.008.
- [91] J. G. Karuga, “Agroecological farming impacts on livelihoods improvement to inform county government on enactment of agroecology policy: case study of Kiambu County, Central,” 2022. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://nmbu.brage.unit.no/nmbu-xmlui/handle/11250/2995687>
- [92] P. Koohafkan, ... M. A.-I. J. of, and undefined 2012, “Green agriculture: foundations for biodiverse, resilient and productive agricultural systems,” *Taylor Fr. Koohafkan, MA Altieri, EH GimenezInternational J. Agric. Sustain. 2012•Taylor Fr.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 61–75, 2011, doi: 10.1080/14735903.2011.610206.
- [93] J. Ford, L. Berrang-Ford, J. P.-C. change, and undefined 2011, “A systematic review of observed climate change adaptation in developed nations: A letter,” *SpringerJD Ford, L Berrang-Ford, J PatersonClimatic Chang. 2011•Springer*, vol. 106, no. 2, pp. 327–336, May 2011, doi: 10.1007/s10584-011-0045-5.
- [94] G. I. Tánago, J. Urquijo, V. Blauhut, F. Villarroya, and L. De Stefano, “Learning from experience: a systematic review of assessments of vulnerability to drought,” *Nat. Hazards*, vol. 80, no. 2, pp. 951–973, Jan. 2006, doi: 10.1007/s11069-015-2006-1.
- [95] M. Spires, S. Shackleton, G. C.-C. and Development, and undefined 2014, “Barriers to implementing planned community-based adaptation in developing countries: A systematic literature review,” *Taylor Fr. Spires, S Shackleton, G CundillClimate Dev. 2014•Taylor Fr.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 277–287, 2014, doi: 10.1080/17565529.2014.886995.
- [96] D. Moher *et al.*, “Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement,” *Ann. Intern. Med.*, vol. 151, no. 4, pp. 264–269, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-151-4-200908180-00135.
- [97] S. Von Wirén-Lehr, “Sustainability in agriculture — an evaluation of principal goal-oriented concepts to close the gap between theory and practice,” *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.*, vol. 84, no. 2, pp. 115–129, Apr. 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0167-8809(00)00197-3.
- [98] T. Dinku, P. Ceccato, and S. J. Connor, “Challenges of satellite rainfall estimation over mountainous and arid parts of east africa,” *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, vol. 32, no. 21, pp. 5965–5979, 2011, doi: 10.1080/01431161.2010.499381.
- [99] P. Thornton, P. Jones, ... G. A.-G. environmental, and U. 2009, “Spatial variation of crop yield response to climate change in East Africa,” *Glob. Environ. Chang.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 54–65, 2009, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959378008000812>
- [100] N. Rakotovao, ... T. R.-G. D. of, and undefined 2022, “Agricultural Soil and Water Conservation Issues in East Africa,” *SpringerNH Rakotovao, TM Razafimbelo, HR Razakamanarivo, JH Hewson, N RamifehiarivoGlobal Degrad. Soil Water Resour. Reg. Assess. Strateg. 2022•Springer*, pp. 29–48, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-7916-2_4.
- [101] M. Musumba, P. Grabowski, ... C. P.-A. at S., and U. 2017, “Guide for the sustainable intensification assessment framework,” *Fedd Futur. U.S Gov. Glob. Hunger Food Secur. Initiat.*, no. 4, 2017, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3906994
- [102] FAO, “The 10 elements of Agroecology. GUIDING THE TRANSITION TO SUSTAINABLE FOOD AND AGRICULTURAL SYSTEMS,” 2019, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=FAO.+%282019%29.+The+10+elements+of+A+groecology+Guiding+the+transition+to+sustainable+food+and+agricultural+systems.+Fao%2C+15.+http%3A%2F%2Fwww.fao.org%2F3%2FI9037EN%2FI9037en.pdf&btnG=
- [103] C. Peano, P. Migliorini, and F. Sottile, “A methodology for the sustainability assessment of agri-food systems: an application to the Slow Food Presidia project,” *Ecol. Soc.*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 24z, 2014, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26269668>

- [104] F. Zahm, P. Viaux, L. Vilain, P. Girardin, and C. Mouchet, "Assessing farm sustainability with the IDEA method—from the concept of agriculture sustainability to case studies on farms," *Wiley Online Libr. Zahm, P Viaux, L Vilain, P Girardin, C Mouch. Dev. 2008*•*Wiley Online Libr.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 271–281, 2008, doi: 10.1002/sd.380.
- [105] E. N. Speelman, S. López-Ridaura, N. A. Colomer, M. Astier, and O. R. Masera, "Ten years of sustainability evaluation using the MESMIS framework: Lessons learned from its application in 28 Latin American case studies," *Taylor Fr. Speelman, S López-Ridaura, NA Colomer, M Astier, OR MaseraThe Int. J. Sustain. Dev. World Ecol. 2007*•*Taylor Fr.*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 345–361, Aug. 2007, doi: 10.1080/13504500709469735.
- [106] C. I. Nicholls *et al.*, "A rapid, farmer-friendly agroecological method to estimate soil quality and crop health in vineyard systems," *Res. Nicholls, MA Altieri, A Dezanet, M Lana, D Feistauer, M OuriquesBiodynamics, 2004*•*researchgate.net*, 2004, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Bruno-Borsari/post/How-monitoring-restoration-ecology-and-agriculture-dinamic-processes-in-the-same-way-and-short-time-like-4-5-years/attachment/5ba3aaad3843b006753a4b00/AS%3A672939624116228%401537452717586/download/Nicholls_2004_Rapid_farmer_friendly_agroecological_method.pdf
- [107] N. Van Cauwenbergh, K. Biala, C. B.- Agriculture, U. Ecosystems, and U. 2007, "SAFE—A hierarchical framework for assessing the sustainability of agricultural systems," *Elsevier*, 2007, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167880906003331>
- [108] FAO, "SAFA (Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems) Tool. User manual (version 2.2.40) | FAO," 2014, Accessed: Jan. 16, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/284643/>
- [109] M. Mng'ong'o, L. K. Munishi, P. A. Ndakidemi, W. Blake, S. Comber, and T. H. Hutchinson, "Toxic metals in East African agro-ecosystems: Key risks for sustainable food production," *J. Environ. Manage.*, vol. 294, p. 112973, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112973.

APPENDIX A: FRAMEWORK EVALUATION AND CHECKLIST FOR LITERATURE REVIEW

Section and Topic		Checklist item
TITLE		
Questions Do existing indicator frameworks account for the smallholder AgroEcology farmer challenges in the East African region? (this answers the concerns of applicability, practicality, socio-economic viability, environmental sustainability in the EA region)		
Title		Identify the report as a systematic review (Check literature on the requirements for a systematic review process)
ABSTRACT		
Abstract		Summary of the document not exceeding 1 page, 11 font, arial style and single line.
INTRODUCTION		
Rationale		Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.
		Describe link of the indicator frameworks with SDGs .
		Describe the geographical emphasis of the indicator frameworks (at least the major one(s)).
		Identify and describe the AE challenges in the EA region which should be addressed to enable sustainable transitions.
		Indicate the indicator framework development, application gaps in the context of Africa and East Africa (with a focus on IAA).
Objectives		Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.
METHODS		
Eligibility criteria		Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses. Were there reasons necessitating the exclusion of some of the information/documents?
		Provide a schematic/map showing where the indicator frameworks have been developed and used in different parts of the world.
Information sources		Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.
Search strategy		Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used. [Keywords used]
Selection process		Specify the methods used to decide whether a framework met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.

Section and Topic		Checklist item
		[Interrater reliability/Member checking]
Data collection process		Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.
Data items		List and define all outcomes (elements/domains) for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.
		List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.
Study risk of bias assessment		Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.
Effect measures		Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.
Synthesis methods (Tabulation ensures ease of comparability of frameworks)		Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).
		Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.
		Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.
		Describe any method(s) used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.
		Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among indicator frameworks.
		Describe any analyses conducted to assess robustness of indicator frameworks.
Reporting bias assessment		Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).
Certainty assessment		Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.
RESULTS		
Study selection		Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow chart diagram.
		Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.
Study characteristics		Predominant characteristics of the indicator frameworks: by sector, by institution/organization, by element/domain emphasis, by indicator emphasis, by strategies for use, by topics (this can be presented using tables), [and should include comments for suitability in terms of AE applicability, practicality, socio-economic viability, environmental sustainability in the EA region]
Risk of bias in studies		Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.

Section and Topic		Checklist item
Results of individual studies		For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.
Results of syntheses		For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.
		Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect. [And in our case, meta-synthesis]
		Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.
		Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.
Reporting biases		Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.
Certainty of evidence		Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.
DISCUSSION		
Discussion		Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.
		Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.
		Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.
		Discuss the implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.

APPENDIX B: WORK PACKAGE 3, TASK 3.1 METHODOLOGY

Phase1 - Identification and Selection of Indicators:

1. **Stakeholder engagement:** Engaging with stakeholders from WP1, communication with the WP1 team
 - Stakeholder workshops (WP???)
 - Case studies (WP3, T3.2)
 - Data collection from practitioners using tools and from a variety of sources (secondary, primary): WP6
2. **Review of existing frameworks and indicators:** Taxonomy of Indicators Table + Local Indicators
 - Identification of sustainability indicator frameworks
 - Identification of indicator frameworks applied in the East African context + local indicators
 - Documentation of criteria/reasons for potential for determination of relevant frameworks (contextualization of indicators)
3. **Development of selection criteria:** Next step for WP3 (Availability, Accuracy, Measurability, Monitorability, Relevance, Cost...)?
 - Identification of criteria (Availability, Accuracy, Measurability, Relevance, Cost, Applicability, socio-economic viability, environmental sustainability, climate friendliness)
 - Definition of criteria in the context of East Africa
4. **Identification and selection of indicators:** Using the selection criteria and stakeholder input to identify and select a comprehensive set of indicators that cover different dimensions of agroecology in IAA smallholders in EA
 - WP3, T3.2: Analysis of success factors of selected case studies
 - Define typologies of farming systems in East Africa based on practices and agreed on criteria (by researchers and stakeholders)
 - Identify relevant and key agroecological dimensions, thematic areas... etc for indicator development covering the identified farm typologies (literature, researchers and stakeholder input)
 - Identification and development of indicators for farm typologies with inputs from literature, researchers and stakeholders: relevance, accuracy... etc parameters to be taken into account

Phase 2 - Testing and Validation of Indicators

1. **Selection of case studies:**
 - WP2, T2.3 (10 best practice examples screened from the T2.1 in terms of the agroecological elements from relevant frameworks)
 - Living laboratory data to be used as benchmarks for evaluation or assessment and weighting of indicators (specifically for IAA)
2. **Data collection and analysis:**

- Collecting data on the selected indicators in the case studies and analyzing the results. This can include using different data collection methods, such as surveys, interviews, site visits, sensors, governmental data, satellites, etc.
3. **Feedback from stakeholders:**
 - Engaging with stakeholders from WP1 to gather feedback on the selected indicators' relevance, cost-effectiveness, environmental sustainability, climatic friendliness, applicability, etc
 4. **Refinement and improvement of indicators:**
 - Based on the feedback from stakeholders and the results of the testing and validation, refining and improving the selected indicators to ensure that they are relevant, reliable, and applicable for the PrAectiCe objectives.
 5. **Production of Agroecological (PrAectiCe) Indicator framework that meets the criteria of relevance, applicability, practicality, minimal data collection costs, socio-economic viability, environmental sustainability (Document production)**